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Abstract:

This document is a periodic report presenting the project's progress in the second year of the SSHOC project. It includes an overview of planned and completed activities and use of resources of the project partners and defines the current status of the SSHOC work plan.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is the second annual report for the SSHOC project. It states the progress and status of work in the second year of the SSHOC project (M12-M24).

The report starts with a general plan for the SSHOC project in Year 2 (2020), and lists the main objectives set up to be achieved. The next section is the main part of this deliverable and focuses on the activities implemented in each Work Package, and describes the progress done in 2020. The section also contains a reference to the deviations from the DoA that happened in this period, and risk assessment status.

The final chapter contains the summary on the delivery of project outputs (namely deliverables), achievement of project milestones, and the use of resources. An overview of all the SSHOC 2020 relevant events is added to the document as an appendix.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AHRC	Arts and Humanities Research Council (UK)
API	Application Programming Interface
BBMRI	Biobanking and BioMolecular Resources Research Infrastructure
CAPI	Computer-Assisted Personal Interviewing
CARI	Computer Audio Recorded Interviewing
CentERdata	Institute for Data Collection and Research
CESSDA	Consortium of Social Sciences Data Archives
CIDOC	International Documentation Committee
CIDOC CRM	CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model
CKAN	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CMDI	Component Metadata Infrastructure
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Italian Research Council)
CNRS	Centre national de la recherche scientifique (French National Centre for Scientific Research)
DANS	Data Archiving and Networked Services, Netherlands
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DARIAH-ELDAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities - Ethics and Legality in the Digital Arts and Humanities
DBSS	Dried blood spot samples
DDI	Document Discover Interoperate
DELAD	Database Enterprise for Language And speech Disorders
DH	Digital Humanities
EAC	Encoded Archival Context
EAD	Encoded Archival Description
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESS	European Social Survey
ETHMIGSURVEY DATA	The International Ethnic and Immigrant Minorities' Survey Data Network
ETL	Extract-Transform-Load
EVS	European Values Study

FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse
FORTH	Foundation for Research and Technology -Hellas
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GESIS	GESIS - Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften e.v. (Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences)
GGP	Generations and Gender Programm
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums
ICCD	Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo e la Documentazione (Central Institute for Cataloguing and Documentation, Italy)
IPERION-CH	Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure ON Cultural Heritage
KNAW	Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen (The Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences, Netherlands)
LIBER	Association of European Research Libraries
LR4SSHOC	Language Research for Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
LTP	Linked Third Party
MAP	Models and Simulations for Architecture and Heritage
MCSQ	The Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires
MEA	Munich Center for the Economics of Aging
MT	Machine Translation
MVP	minimal viable product
NACE/ISIC	International Standard Industrial Classification of All Economic Activities
NLP	Natural language processing
NSD	Norwegian Centre for Research Data
OCR	Optical Character Recognition
OEAW	The Austrian Academy of Sciences
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OPERAS	OPen scholarly communication in the European Research Area for Social sciences and humanities
PCP	Public Consultation Platform
PMB	Project Management Board: CO + WP Leaders
PSNC	The Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center
RDM	Research Data Management
REST-API	Representational State Transfer-Application Programming Interface
RSA	Remote Secure Access
RUN	Radboud University (Nijmegen, NL)

SEADDA	Saving European Archaeology from the Digital Dark Age
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSH	Social Science and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Science and Humanities Open Cloud
SSHOCro	SSHOC Reference Ontology
SSK	Standardization Survival Kit
SWC	Semantic Web Company
TAPoR	Text Analysis Portal for Research
TiU-EVS	Stichting Katholieke Universiteit Brabant - European Values Study
TRAPD	Translation method: Translation, Review, Adjudication, Pretest, Documentation
TRIPLE	Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration
TRUST-IT	TRUST-IT SERVICES LIMITED
UCL	University College London
UFAL	Institute of Formal and Applied Linguistics. Charles University, Czech Republic
UGOE	The University of Goettingen
UL-ADP	Social Science Data Archives at University of Ljubljana
UL-FF	Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana
UNOTT	The University of Nottingham
UPF	Universitat Pompeu Fabra (Pompeu Fabra University)
UVA	University of Amsterdam
UVT	Tilburg University
WP	Work Package
WPSS	Web Panel Sample Service
WVS	World Value Survey
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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1. Introduction

The SSHOC project has three mandatory reporting periods. In addition to the official reports to be submitted to the EC, internal reporting has also been set up. This is to ensure that all project obligations are being fulfilled, and the progress of each Work Package is documented and on track. The practice of regular reporting has been set and the collected information is used to prepare three annual progress & activity reports planned as project deliverables covering each project year. These reports include the plan and objectives relating to the year, progress across WPs, risks and contingency plans, planned versus actual deliverable submission, and the use of resources status. This deliverable is the second SSHOC annual report, and focuses on the year 2020. It provides an overview of the work performed from M13 to M24 of the SSHOC project and all the challenges and successes of the implementation.

Year 2 of the SSHOC project

As the global situation of COVID-19 pandemic crisis left no part of the world unaffected, the constant health concerns related to the spread, the travel restrictions introduced, and the Europe-wide social restrictions did not bypass the 48 partners, and more than 230 people involved in this project. However, as it will be detailed in this report, after a closer look and risk assessment, the project has not suffered in terms of its impact and achievements, albeit having to adopt an agile approach, thanks also to partners' flexibility, to using digital virtual tools constantly, and was able to continue the work planned, mitigating the risks and finding solutions to the challenges that arose. Working in virtual areas, remotely, reformatting events, adapting activities, adjusting the timelines, and prioritising effective and constant communication among partners made this possible.

The situation requested immediate actions, thinking out of the box and adjustments, but not just that - as an EC project led by the EU Research Infrastructures, there was also the obligation to participate in the COVID-19 related discussions and act as a community that the project is creating. Thus, in April 2020 SSHOC described its specific actions towards creating a European data platform for COVID-19 which should *"enable the rapid collection and comprehensive sharing of available research data from different sources for the European and global research communities"* (COVID-19 Data Portal)¹ and provided its considerations to the EC², focusing on removing the barriers to high-quality reproducible science leading to evidence-based interventions as: non-availability of relevant data, need for a web-based data panel to collect actions, attitudes and behaviours of citizens, limited accessibility of data, difficulties of finding the data, and the extensive efforts needed to combine data.

In September 2020, a SSHOC article was published laying out the specific actions taken by the SSHOC partners to continue to serve their communities in the context of the Corona virus crisis³. Being aware of the implications of the pandemic, SSHOC issued a COVID-19 edition of the SSHOC Newsletter "SSHOC in the Time of COVID-19"⁴. These activities were realised to get closer to the community, making it aware of

¹ Covid-19 Data Portal: <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/about> [accessed 19.01.2021]

² Ron Dekker, & Laura Morales. (2020, April 30). Response from SSHOC on COVID-19. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4071701> [accessed 19.01.2021]

³ Article "How SSHOC is responding to COVID-19 ": <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/how-sshoc-responding-covid-19> [accessed 18.01.2021]

⁴COVID-19 edition of the SSHOC Newsletter "SSHOC in the Time of COVID-19"
<https://www.sshopencloud.eu/social-sciences-humanities-open-cloud-insights-4> [accessed 18.01.2021]

the potential and importance of the social sciences and humanities to contribute to better addressing the social, economic and political situations in global changes such as this one, but also everyday life.

After the basis for the work in SSHOC has been set up and functional, the timeline and activities intensified in 2020. Most of the Tasks lasted through the year and the Consortium planned a total of **28 Deliverables** and **21 Milestones**⁵ (see Figure 1 below), as well as completing the obligation of submitting the 1st Periodic Report to the EC. In addition, a big milestone was coming up in 2020 - the 1st EC review of the project.

Figure 1. Planned Deliverables, Milestones and EC report in Year 2 of the SSHOC project

⁵ This information includes the changes introduced by Amendment - AMD-823782-16 to the SSHOC GA as well as the Deliverables pending submission from the previous year.

2. Progress and activity reports per WP

2.1. WP1 - Project Management and Administration

In the second year of the project, WP1 focused on several tasks:

- 1) maintaining the established bases for **sound management of the project** and monitoring the project's progress and use of resources;
- 2) supporting the Consortium in implementing the tasks and reporting about the results;
- 3) implementing the procedures to maintain quality;
- 4) implementing and participating in activities that ensure SSHOC alignment with wider EOSC eco-system and cluster projects⁶.

As a result, partners submitted **2 deliverables** and the 1st EC periodic report, went through a successful 1st EC project review, and strengthened the SSHOC position in the EOSC context.

2.1.1. WP1 progress

2.1.1.1. TASK 1.1 ADMINISTRATIVE PROJECT MANAGEMENT

The Task 1.1 is led by CESSDA ERIC, as the project coordinator, in close cooperation with WP leaders coming mostly from the 1st Tier organisations (ESS ERIC, SHARE ERIC, CLARIN ERIC, DARIAH ERIC, E-RIHS, Trust-IT, LIBER, and the University of Nottingham in addition) forming the Project Management Board (PMB). The Work Package leaders have continued managing the work in their respective WPs and their teams since month one, while regularly reporting at the PMB meetings. To ensure that, **regular PMB meetings** were held fortnightly. In total, **24 virtual meetings** (via GoToMeeting platform) were organised in 2020.

Using the procedures and maintaining the tools set up for project management, the coordinating team continued monitoring the project work and use of resources in 2020. It also worked on improving the quality of collaboration and internal communication among project partners. In order to allow for basic project requirements to be satisfied, the Coordinator maintained the collaborative platform, regular management calls, internal project document repository and SSHOC Wiki, and **distributed the 2nd instalment** (interim payment by the EC in December 2020) to the Beneficiaries in a timely manner.

The team also organised two meetings to gather the entire Consortium. SSHOC **3rd Consortium meeting** was held on 24th and 25th of March 2020, with CLARIN ERIC as a host (supporting the Coordination team in organisation by providing the platform for the virtual meeting, and necessary technical support). The virtual Consortium meeting allowed for more representatives of each partner institution to join the discussions and presentations, not limiting the participation only on leadership

⁶ EOSC-Life, ESCAPE, ENVRI-FAIR, and PANOSC, financed through the same call (INFRAEOSC-04)

roles in the project. The **4th Consortium meeting** was held in the same manner, on 8th and 9th of September 2020, with ESS/UPF as the partner hosting and providing support in the organisation. The Consortium meetings thus had up to 124 participants joining seven different sessions, focused on work done in Work Packages, challenges and results, as well as collaboration between the different WPs.

One of important results of this task is the preparation and submission of **D1.6 Data Management Plan - DMP⁷** (June 2020); an extensive document which details the use and management of data in the project, and will be updated with every periodic report. This plan provides a structured description of data collected, created, and used for and by the SSHOC project. It also describes the procedures and policies as well as data protection and preservation mechanisms used in the project and planned in the period after the project is finalised.

The **Scientific Board**, formed from the 1st Tier partners, discussed strategic issues related to the project and continued to advise the Coordinator of the project. The Board held **12 on-line meetings** in the course of 2020, 2 of them jointly with the Project Management Board (PMB) as part of the virtual consortium meetings (held in March and September 2020). The group focused on a number of strategic issues (here are the main ones):

- Governance model for EOSC & SSHOC ERICs considerations,
- BREXIT: risk analysis, possible scenarios and implications of possible actions,
- A forward look: Horizon Europe programme and upcoming opportunities for SSHOC partners,
- Cooperation with relevant stakeholders (DG RTD and units of importance),
- INFRAEOSC-03 proposal (EOSC Future),
- EOSC legal entity (Association) and ERICs position; membership,
- EOSC Executive Board and Working Groups -coordination and relationship with EOSC,
- Related EOSC projects; collaboration and alignment with INFRAEOSC-04 (cluster) projects; joint EOSC position paper,
- EOSC onboarding of tools and services - challenges,
- ERA strategy, DG RTD strategy, SRIA document, ESFRI White paper - consultations,
- Joint response to COVID-19 pandemic,
- Sustainability WG (Strawman, Tinman, and Iron Lady documents) - consultations,
- Global cooperation in SSH.

In 2020, the SSHOC Scientific Board welcomed a new scientific community into SSHOC through an amendment to the Grant Agreement that entered into force on 7 May 2020: EURhisFIRM⁸, a H2020 project and related scientific community aiming at designing a world-class research infrastructure to collect, merge, extract, collate, align and share detailed historical high-quality firm level data for Europe with historic economic data, represented by **3 new beneficiaries** in the SSHOC consortium:

- ECOLE D'ECONOMIE DE PARIS (EEP PSE)
- LEIBNIZ INSTITUT FÜR FINANZMARKTFORSCHUNG SAFE EV (SAFE)
- UNIVERSITEIT ANTWERPEN (Uantwerp).

⁷ Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Vanja Komljenovic, Martina Drascic, Irena Vipavc Brvar, Elizabeth Lea Bishop, Daan Broeder,... Kea Tijdens. (2020). D1.6 SSHOC Data Management Plan. Zenodo. DOI [10.5281/zenodo.393140](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.393140)

⁸ EURhisFIRM: <https://eurhisfirm.eu> [accessed 10.01.2021]

During 2020 SSHOC Coordinator has also started discussion with another scientific community to join the consortium - RESILIENCE⁹, research infrastructure for all Religious Studies, building a high-performance platform, supplying evolving tools and big data to scholars from all the scientific disciplines crossing religions. This community should be added to SSHOC in the coming period.

The work of the Scientific Board resulted in now regular connections established between the SSHOC project bodies and all the projects and stakeholders relevant for timely and efficient adaptation of SSHOC to the developments in the EOSC landscape, both on governance and strategic level. This network will remain relevant throughout and after the project implementation.

A relevant milestone for the Task 1.1 team, one of great importance for the entire Consortium, was the planning, preparation and successful execution of the first **SSHOC Review meeting** in October 2020, which was a part of the **1st project review by the European Commission**. The highly positive and productive meeting resulted in an encouraging and constructive project review report, which evaluated the project as “impactful by design” and highlighted the significant progress made, as well as the level of organisation and management, and creating of a strong project brand.

2.1.1.2. TASK 1.2 QUALITY ASSURANCE & RISK ASSESSMENT

Task 1.2 is led by the coordinator CESSDA ERIC with the same partners as in Task 1.1 - members of the Project Management Board and the 1st Tier Strategic Board. Following the procedures set in the *D1.2 Quality Assurance & Risk Assessment Plan*¹⁰ the partners continued the monitoring work in 2020, with the focus on maintaining high-quality of the project structure as well as the continuation of the risk monitoring.

Due to the world-wide COVID-19 pandemic, risk management was considered as one of the priorities, and partners were especially focused on revising the work in the pipeline, making sure any possible risks are foreseen, and the implications of the pandemic mitigated. This was done in several ways: suitably using the procedures established, adjusting teams and efforts as needed, providing help for partners, adjusting timelines, reformating events, and maintaining the different communication channels among the 48 partners and over 230 participants of the project.

To make sure that SSHOC is visible to and aware of the related events/events of interest, and to align the dissemination and other activities with the EOSC related developments at all times, task partners continued the activities in the two engagement platforms set up in the project for alignment with the EOSC building projects:

- (1) cluster projects technical alignment team to make sure all the technical updates are taken into account, and services and tools to be onboarded to the EOSC Portal;
- (2) collaboration with other thematic clusters' communication and dissemination teams to achieve EOSC outreach alignment;

⁹ RESILIENCE: <https://www.resilience-ri.eu> [accessed 10.01.2021]

¹⁰ Martina Drascic, Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Carsten Thiel, Daan Broeder, Gianmaria Bottoni, Marieke Willems, ... Vasso Kalaitzi. (2019). SSHOC D1.2 Quality Assurance & Risk Assessment Plan (Version V1.2). DOI [10.5281/zenodo.3595453](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3595453)

- (3) strategic alignment among the cluster projects to make sure the expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC are a combined and synchronised effort;
- (4) training alignment with the other clusters in order to share the knowledge and collaborate on training events organisation.

2.1.1.3. TASK 1.3 PROJECT REPORTING

In the scope of Task 1.3 the Coordinator carried on with the activities of continuous reporting to the EC, maintaining communication with the EC officers, using and maintaining the procedures and tools for project reporting within the Consortium. During year 2 the Coordinator maintained regular **communication with the EC** Project Officer, Legal Officer, and Financial Officer, to inform and report any issues, delays and finalizing the 1st Amendment (May 2020).

As a result of the established monitoring and project reports, the second Deliverable of this task was submitted in January 2020, **D1.3 First Annual Progress & Activity Report¹¹**. The report contained summarised information on activities and results in the first year of SSHOC implementation, in the same way as this document is capturing the main activities and results of the year 2020.

The Consortium also continued with semi-annual internal reporting on the use of resources (the **second internal financial report** was prepared in January 2020, feeding into the D1.3). Continuous reporting was done during regular calls of the Task teams, Work Package teams, and the PMB. Gathered information was periodically presented to the Consortium at the 3rd and 4th Consortium meetings in dedicated sessions.

An important milestone for the project was the preparation and submission of the **1st SSHOC Periodic report to the EC** (August 2020). The report was approved by the EC in November 2020, following the positive evaluation of the 1st SSHOC Review by the EC. As a part of the review process, **all 27 deliverables** submitted by June 2020 (M18 of the project) were **approved by the EC**.

2.1.2. Note on deviations from the plan and risk monitoring

Despite the implications of the COVID-19 pandemic, the work in WP1 continued in 2020 without many deviations. The only deviation consisted of reformatting the Consortium meetings into virtual meetings, incurring more effort to be dedicated in re-organising. The escalating health concerns related to the spread of the COVID-19 and the travel restrictions introduced across Europe forced the Consortium to make changes. On the 12th of March it was decided to cancel the planned face-to-face Consortium meeting and hold a series of online meetings on same days, transforming the meetings to a virtual mode, instead of locating it in Utrecht, The Netherlands. Late cancellation caused some travel expenses to be incurred regardless of the decision. As the pandemic related restrictions continued towards the end of 2020, the 4th Consortium meeting was also virtual.

Information on risk monitoring in WP1 for Year 2 is presented in the table below:

¹¹ Draščić, Martina, Versic Ilijasic, Ivana, Willems, Marieke, Broeder, Daan, Eskevich, Maria, Bottoni, Gianmaria, ... van der Eijk, Cees. (2020). SSHOC D1.3 First Annual Progress & Activity Report (Version v1.0). Zenodo. DOI [10.5281/zenodo.3688662](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3688662).

Table 1. Risk monitoring in WP1 - Year 2

Risks monitoring WP1				
<i>Risk (DoA)</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Risk-mitigation measures applied?</i>	<i>Risk materialised so far?</i>	<i>Comments</i>
U7	No delivery or reformatting/adjusting of face-to-face activities due to COVID-19	Yes	Yes	Consortium meetings in 2020 were not able to be organised face-to-face, and they were both moved in a virtual environment, as well as some other meetings planned for this period.

2.2. WP2 - Communication, Dissemination and Impact

In the second year the WP2 tasks built on the results of year one, and the strategy set out in the D2.2 communication and outreach strategy. WP2 worked on wide promotion of the innovation and benefits of SSHOC to targeted stakeholders, maximizing visibility, activating end-user communities in a strong collaboration with WP6, disseminating results, and demonstrating impact. Regular social media activities were undertaken as well: communication via newsletter, the website and external channels.

WP2 worked on the SSHOC web platform continuous improvements and updates with the main outcome being the ***MS5 SSHOC web platform continuous marketplace integration with SSHOC service offer***. The milestone included the launch of the SSHOC service catalogue and the publication of the *SSH Open Marketplace Consultation Platform* for the tester community. In this period, WP2 Web Task Force also prepared for *MS6 SSHOC web platform continuous marketplace integration with SSHOC service offer 2-3*.

Furthermore, WP2 worked on strengthening the visual identity of SSHOC by maintaining the homogeneous design and branding of all tools, services and materials delivered under the SSHOC umbrella, including communication collaterals, online visuals and logos used in the promotion of the online Marketplace (WP7). All communication materials are SSHOC branded and tailored to stakeholder needs. In collaboration with WP6, WP2 promoted and supported the organisation of EU-wide workshops and actions in Europe, as well as webinars and training events, especially on data skills & other training in the project. In November 2020, WP2 and WP6 planned, organised and promoted the EOSC-hub, FREYA and SSHOC four-day conference *REALISING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD*, engaging with the full scope of SSHOC stakeholders, raising awareness and fostering uptake of SSHOC results and assets.

In addition, WP2 aligned with the ESFRI cluster projects on collaboration activities. In this line of thoughts a joint position paper was published, a joint session was organised at the *REALISING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD* and a joint booth proposal for ICT2020 was submitted (the event was cancelled due to COVID-19). Conversations started for a joint session at the online RDA Plenary 17.

The FAIR principles are also applied in this work package. It is an overall communication objective that the project's output is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. During the second year of the project, WP2 ensured all Deliverables and reports are Findable, Accessible and Reusable through the project ZENODO community and the SSHOC website.

2.2.1. WP2 progress

2.2.1.1. TASK 2.1 SSHOC CLUSTER COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

This task was completed in M6 of the project.

2.2.1.2. TASK 2.2 MAXIMISING IMPACT: SSH COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH AS PART OF EOSC

Task 2.2 was led by TRUST-IT with main partners participating CESSDA/AUSSDA, CLARIN ERIC, both TRUST-IT LTPs, CNRS, CNR and LIBER. In 2020 the task team continued to focus on the production and dissemination of content following the strategy set out in T2.1. This included web content for the SSHOC

web presence, social media, press releases and other outlets. SSHOC used various communication channels leveraging the project partner networks with the SSHOC website as the central channel.

Regular updates were published on the website focusing on SSHOC activities and results, as well as updates from the EOSC ecosystem, to which SSHOC actively contributes. Stakeholder Engagement on social media helps to build a strong SSH community, where proper engagement ensures effective impact. All social Media channels set-up in SSHOC are Twitter¹², LinkedIn¹³, Flickr¹⁴, Youtube¹⁵ were active in 2020. The team also worked on covering the implementation and maintenance of a “cluster” project identity and branding where each partner, all involved ERICs and landmark initiatives are represented and enhanced toward existing communities and new communities. For this purpose the team worked on creating appropriate branding solutions. Apart from that, the partners worked heavily to organise SSHOC and SSHOC-related events, participated in other relevant events and promoted them, joining forces with other projects, such as FREYA and EOSC-hub.

In alignment with the FAIR principles, all project **reports, publications and presentations** published in 2020 were shared via the website. SSHOC WP1 and WP2 decided that deliverables, reports and presentations should be made available via ZENODO to improve the sharing of the project's results. This was continued in 2020 and implemented for all documents.

In the year 2020, **50 news pieces** (see Appendices to this report) were published on the SSHOC website, **52 events** were promoted via the SSHOC website relevant for the project stakeholders, **of which 43 were SSHOC organised related activities**. In addition to these news-items **15 deliverables** were digested¹⁶ and published under project results. These updates were disseminated in a wider network via SSHOC and partner channels. In total **4 newsletters and direct messages**¹⁷ were sent, on the latest SSHOC achievements and activities to **330 subscribers**. A total of **17 publications** in external channels were made. In addition, **11 SSHOC scientific publications** are now highlighted on the website¹⁸.

On Twitter SSHOC has built a community of **1360 followers** and on LinkedIn, the community has grown to 325 connections by month 24 of the project. On Youtube SSHOC received **10.000+ views**, worth highlighting is the promotional video “SSH Open Marketplace - explained the easy way” with **7000+ views** since August 2020.

To ensure an aligned and strong project identity a **branding package** was delivered, for the consortium to use in communication activities.

¹² SSHOC Twitter: <https://twitter.com/SSHOpenCloud> [18.01.2021]

¹³ SSHOC LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/18997546/> [18.01.2021]

¹⁴ SSHOC Flickr: <https://www.flickr.com/photos/170844433@N02/> [18.01.2021]

¹⁵ SSHOC Youtube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCw-mY8v84yeHW2z4KG3ZLtA> [18.01.2021]

¹⁶ SSHOC Website publication of Deliverables produced: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/publications/deliverables> [20.01.2021]

¹⁷ SSHOC newsletter: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/newsletter/sshoc-newsletter> [20.01.2021]

¹⁸ SSHOC Scientific publications on the website: <https://sshopencloud.eu/scientific-publications> [20.01.2021]

Figure 2. “Empowered by SSHOC” branded stamp for services & tools enhanced under SSHOC

The package includes a Logo Pack¹⁹, Branding guidelines²⁰, and a template package for ppt presentation, deliverables, meeting agenda and milestones²¹ prepared in collaboration with WP1. Close alignment was established with WP7 on the branding of the SSH Open Marketplace, with WP6 on the training toolkit. WP2 set up a SSHOC branding services & tools document to describe the different levels of branding, identified for SSHOC services and tools, to be highlighted in the SSHOC tools & services catalogue on the project website and integrated in the SSH Open Marketplace. In addition, an “empowered by SSHOC” stamp was developed to be implemented in those services that are enhanced under SSHOC and to be maintained by SSHOC partners after the project’s lifetime. This stamp can exist in harmony with other branding. The dynamically evolving and stakeholder tailored SSHOC Communications Kit²² is SSHOC branded, and published on the project website for partners to use at events and dissemination activities.

Table 2: Communication collaterals delivered for the Communications Kit and SSHOC resources web pages in SSHOC M13-M24

Item	No	Description	Link
Dissemination videos	3	SSH Open Marketplace - explained the easy way Video Interviews at F2F consortium meeting at CNR, Florence with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • M. Wittenberg (KNAW) on SSHOC Dataverse • M. Ďurčo (DARIAH/OEAW) on SSH Open Marketplace 	https://youtu.be/4tyZ4vhrM9s <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ObfG1O78RSM • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-TmorX0WGWY
Video	11	Webinar videos	YouTube Playlist: https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLpuwwe1MpnmqKds5en7SyezeYESYDhy90M
Video	11	SSHOC Considerations for the Vocabulary Platforms	Youtube Playlist: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aEejUNlyjig&list=PLpuwwe1Mpnmq_P7bcam7qt

¹⁹ SSHOC logo pack: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/logo-pack> [20.01.2021]

²⁰ SSHOC brand guidelines: https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sites/default/files/SSHOC%20Guideline_booklet.pdf [20.01.2021]

²¹ Available at the SSHOC document repository and the project Wiki under visibility guidelines.

²² SSHOC communications kit: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/communications-kit> [20.01.2021]

			nSN5nGNxBHh
Video	7	SSHOC Online Information Sessions: Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms	Youtube Playlist: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZKaXhi6MOnw&list=PLpuwwe1MpnqleMC9cF341suBh5OIQI99J
Video	3	SSH Open Marketplace	YouTube Playlist: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4tyZ4vhrM9s&list=PLpuwwe1MpnqIbNSUjuDEOrp0bn19IjbQw
Video	32	Realising EOSC session videos	YouTube Playlist: https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLpuwwe1MpnqKKTezIRIHDaNx_zlo4yuRC
Infographics	3	Consortium infographic SSH Open Marketplace Infographic SSHOC Services & tools timeline SSHOC Stakeholder infographic, plus an interactive version with key messages.	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-infographics https://sshopencloud.eu/who-benefits
Empowered by SSHOC stamp	1	Branding for SSHOC tools & services	https://sshopencloud.eu/empowered-sshoc-stamp
Newsletters	4	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud Insights #3, 4, 5 and 6	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/newsletter/sshoc-newsletter

Posters created in SSHOC were tailored to the audience attending the specific conference. In M1-18, in total 6 posters were designed and presented.

Table 3. Posters created and presented in SSHOC in 2020

Event	Poster title	Date	ZENODO DOI
EOSC Hub week 2020	Three Pillars of the Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace	May 2020	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3813703
Open-Access-Tage 2020 (OAT2020), Bielefeld, Germany	Three Pillars of the Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace	September 2020	https://zenodo.org/record/4009121#.YD-92pNKhTY

In 2020, the SSHOC partners (co)-organised **2 consortium meetings**, **29 events** and **one joint conference**, where **2297 stakeholders** were engaged during the events and the event recordings were **viewed over 2500 times**. In addition, partners attended **30 public and smaller closed events**, engaging stakeholders from the scientific community, Research Infrastructures, Industry and Policy Makers. To raise awareness on the project and its activities and align with key players in the field (see Appendices to this report). SSHOC organised events and presence at external events has been promoted via the

website, SSHOC and partner social media channels and newsletters. For these events WP2 liaised with partners on collaterals, social media promotion and post event reporting and publication of presentations. WP2 has been working liaising with the **EOSC ecosystem** for communication and community engagement purposes via the following events:

- SSHOC at RDA global adoption week 2020²³
- ESFRI cluster projects - Position papers on expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC²⁴
- EOSC-hub week 2020²⁵.

In 2020, a total of 15 deliverables, 3 reports, 6 posters, and a selection of 25 presentations were uploaded²⁶ to ZENODO. Key results are now easily shared with the wider EOSC for reuse. WP2 has also been monitoring the impact of these publications. In december 2020, the **28 deliverables** had **5.054 total views** and **6.972 total downloads**, worth highlighting the visibility of deliverable **D7.1 SSH Open Marketplace System Specification** with **976 views and 4151 downloads**.

WP2 has set up an internal plan with the purpose of online community engagement, the requirements for the SSHOC online community engagement and in which format the website **sshopencloud.eu** is to provide this support. Specifically at December 2020 the plan covers online support for:

- the training community (**157 members**)
- the certification support service (**14 submissions, 14 repositories selected**)
- the SSH Open Marketplace tester community (**39 members**)

As part of this plan, in June 2020 WP2, 3, 6 and 7 organised an end-user focused session at the ICTeSSH 2020 session "*Agile development of the SSH Open Marketplace: User Workshop*". For this session a call for testers was issued to test the project internal alpha version of the SSH Open Marketplace and provide their feedback live at the, due to COVID-19, online session, **246 people** attended this workshop.

In April, WP7 and WP2 joined efforts to develop a Public Consultation Platform for the alpha release of the SSH Open Marketplace²⁷. The consultation platform aims to collect feedback from potential end-users on the alpha version of the SSH Open Marketplace to integrate in the work plan towards the beta release in December. The consultation platform went live in August 2020, and collected feedback on UX Design and Development, Content and Sources and Curation and Governance. Testers have to sign up to provide their input on the three topics, structured as surveys. The platform also has a direct messaging mechanism, to communicate directly with those signed up to the tester community. A group of **39 testers signed up** to the community and **22 answers** were received. In November, the

²³ SSHOC at RDA global adoption week 2020: <https://sshopencloud.eu/rda-global-adoption-week> [18.01.2021]

²⁴ Gotz, Andy, Petzold, Andreas, Asmi, Ari, Blomberg, Niklas, Lamanna, Giovanni, & Dekker, Ron. (2020, February 19). ESFRI cluster projects - Position papers on expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC. Zenodo. DOI [10.5281/zenodo.3675081](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3675081) [18.01.2021]

²⁵ EOSC Hub week 2020: <https://zenodo.org/record/3813703#.Xw2Kdy2w21s> [18.01.2021]

²⁶ SSHOC Zenodo Community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/sshoc/> [18.01.2021]

²⁷ SSH Open Marketplace Consultation Platform: <https://sshopencloud.eu/ssh-open-marketplace-consultation-platform> [20.01.2021]

consultation closed, so that the input provided by testers could be used for the development of the beta release of the SSH Open Marketplace, due at the end of the year.

Figure 3. SSH Open Marketplace Consultation Platform

WP2 and WP6 joined forces with EOSC-hub and FREYA in the organisation of the ***“REALISING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD - Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the Social Sciences and Humanities and beyond”*** conference. The joint online event was organised as a part of SSHOC stakeholder forum, or rather Stakeholders Series. The event was celebrated over 4 days and included a virtual EOSC expo. For the event joint branding and a dedicated # was created #RealisingEOSC. The event received **690+ participants**, from **45 countries**, including from **20 countries outside the EU**. The Virtual EOSC Expo²⁸ with 33 booths from EOSC projects was visited over 3780 times, with 880 video views and 1520 document views. Recordings were on SSHOC youtube playlist²⁹ and slides are uploaded on a dedicated ZENODO community³⁰.

²⁸ Video #EOSCprojectsEXPO: <https://twitter.com/SSHOpenCloud/status/1329089889581768709>

²⁹ #RealisingEOSC playlist: https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLpuwwe1MpnqKKTezIRIHdaNx_zlo4yuRC
[18.01.2021]

³⁰ #RealisingEOSC ZENODO community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/realisingtheeoscevent?page=1&size=20>
[18.01.2021]

Figure 4. #EOSCprojectsEXPO at the #RealisingEOSC conference and SSHOC virtual booth; Screen Capture

The team has created a number of synergies, to leverage on for project activities, fostering cross-disciplinary research and alignment with the EOSC ecosystem, continuing in 2020.

Table 4: Synergies created and continued in 2020 in SSHOC

Initiative	Synergy	Output
RDA and RDA Europe 4.0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of SSHOC Certification support and plan RDA Global adoption week 2020 & upcoming adoption story • SSHOC presentation RDA Slovenia event • Input RDA for EOSC survey (May 2020) • Session RDA P16 • <i>Community Building Examples Across EOSC-hub, FREYA, & SSHOC</i>, Joint session at “Realising the European Open Science Cloud. Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the SSH” conference. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.rd-alliance.org/research-data-alliance-contributing-european-open-science-cloud • RDA global adoption week session: https://sshopencloud.eu/rda-global-adoption-week • <i>Community Building Examples Across EOSC-hub, FREYA, & SSHOC</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Slides: https://zenodo.org/communities/realisingtheeoscevent/search?page=1&size=20 - Recordings: https://youtu.be/BELr6kG-bnk
ESCAPE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3-monthly communication & stakeholder meetings as of January 2020 • Proposal EOSC Cluster Collaboration IG 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Position papers: https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/esfri-cluster-position-papers-eosc-implementation • EOSC IG: https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-cluster

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint submission ICT2020 • ESFRI Cluster Position Papers on EOSC Implementation • Joint session at the “Realising EOSC” conference, titled “Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud 	<p>ter-collaboration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint proposal ICT2020 stand” The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures: A cross-disciplinary approach to EOSC - ICT 2020 has been cancelled • Joint session at the “Realising EOSC” event titled “Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presentation: https://zenodo.org/record/4277601#.YAWk2C2ZO1t - Recordings: https://youtu.be/jpWU9qVnY5o
PaNOSC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3-monthly communication & stakeholder meetings as of January 2020 • Proposal EOSC Cluster Collaboration IG • Joint submission ICT2020 • ESFRI Cluster Position Papers on EOSC Implementation • Joint session at the “Realising EOSC” conference titled “Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Position papers: https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/esfri-cluster-position-papers-eosc-implementation • EOSC IG: https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-cluster-collaboration • Joint proposal ICT2020 stand” The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures: A cross-disciplinary approach to EOSC - ICT 2020 has been cancelled.
ENVRI FAIR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3-monthly communication & stakeholder meetings as of January 2020 • Proposal EOSC Cluster Collaboration IG • Joint submission ICT2020 • ESFRI Cluster Position Papers on EOSC Implementation • Discussion panel SSHOC Kick-Off Meeting • Joint session at the “Realising EOSC” conference titled “Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud 	

EOSClife	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3-monthly communication & stakeholder meetings as of January 2020 • Proposal EOSC Cluster Collaboration IG • Joint submission ICT2020 • ESFRI Cluster Position Papers on EOSC Implementation • Discussion panel SSHOC Kick-Off Meeting • Joint session at the “Realising EOSC” conference titled “Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud” 	
EOSC Secretariat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESFRI Cluster Position Papers on EOSC Implementation • EOSC Cluster Collaboration IG • Article publication in LR4SSHOC proceedings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Position papers: https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/esfri-cluster-position-papers-eosc-implementation • EOSC IG: https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-cluster-collaboration • LR4SSHOC publication https://sshopencloud.eu/eosc-game-changer-social-sciences-and-humanities-research-activities
EOSC-hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SSHOC Task Force on EOSC alignment • Realising the European Open Science Cloud. Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the SSH. Joint 4-day conference with EOSC-hub, FREYA and SSHOC • EOSC-hub week 2020 poster presentation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realising the European Open Science Cloud: https://sshopencloud.eu/realising-european-open-science-cloud • Poster 23: https://www.eosc-hub.eu/eosc-hub-week-2020-poster-voting
FREYA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realising the European Open Science Cloud. Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the SSH. Joint 4-day conference with EOSC-hub, FREYA and SSHOC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realising the European Open Science Cloud: https://sshopencloud.eu/realising-european-open-science-cloud
OPERAS & TRIPLE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SSHOC participation Kick-Off meeting Triple Project • Article publication in LR4SSHOC proceedings • TRIPLE participation in SSHOC ICTeSSH workshop • Communication meetings • FAIR Research Data Management in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.eosc-hub.eu/news/eosc-hub-magazine-issue-3 • https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.lr4sshoc-1.2 • https://sshopencloud.eu/news/fair-principles-and-user-feedback-ssh-open-marketplace

	<p>SSH: a CO-OPERAS IN & SSHOC Workshop & Report</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Exploring the SSH data landscape: thematic discovery portals in the EOSC</i>, joint session at “Realising the European Open Science Cloud. Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the SSH” conference. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploring the SSH data landscape: thematic discovery portals in the EOSC: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Slides: https://zenodo.org/record/4290599#.YAWsEC2ZO1s - Recordings: https://youtu.be/hr94Yz8odPE
FAIRs FAIR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation SSHOC 2nd consortium meeting • SSHOC representation in FAIRsFAIR synchronisation workshops • Proposal SSHOC FAIR champion • EOSC Cluster Collaboration IG proposal • FAIRsFAIR video “How FAIR is research in Europe Today?” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2nd SSHOC Consortium Meeting: https://www.sshopencloud.eu/2nd-sshoc-consortium-meeting • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7lwO_tXXqKc
Europeana	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Citizen Science: What it means for SSH and how can multidisciplinary be achieved?</i> joint session at “Realising the European Open Science Cloud. Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the SSH” conference. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen Science: What it means for SSH and how can multidisciplinary be achieved? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Slides: https://zenodo.org/communities/realisingtheeoscevent/search?page=1&size=20 - Recordings: https://youtu.be/iqHwZNOaLsU
EOSCEnhance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SSHOC Task Force on EOSC alignment • 2 Joint sessions at “Realising the European Open Science Cloud. Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the SSH” conference. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How can I onboard my resource to EOSC? - Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud 	<p>Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Slides: https://zenodo.org/record/4277601#.YAWk2C2ZO1t - Recordings: https://youtu.be/jpWU9qVnY5o <p>How can I onboard my resource to EOSC?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recordings: https://youtu.be/32hgvCEhsrM

The communication and outreach strategy includes the regular monitoring of impact. For this aim, the team monitors **regular progress** and the status of compliance with the key performance indicators set. The **SSHOC Dashboard**³¹ allows easy access for all partners to monitor the SSHOC website and social media metrics and to shape our strategy accordingly.

³¹ SSHOC Dashboard: <https://datastudio.google.com/reporting/1JtWjrE7ee81DbpkWZc6596j22VNQncR> [18.01.2021]

Figure 5. SSHOC Website traffic in Reporting Period M13-M24; Screen Capture

2.2.1.3. TASK 2.3 SSHOC WEB PRESENCE

The task is led by TRUST-IT, and task partners involved were DARIAH ERIC, LIBER, and TRUST-IT LTPs. In 2020 the team was oriented to increase the SSHOC web presence. The achievement of **Milestone 5** -

SSHOC web platform continuous marketplace integration with SSHOC service offer 1/3³² was a result of a dedicated task force with representatives from WP1, 2, 3, 6 and 7 to align with the activities, work and needs of the ongoing work in SSHOC. From March 2020, WP7 and WP2 were collaborating on developing a SSHOC online public consultation platform to collect feedback on the alpha version of the SSH Open Marketplace from potential users, to build upon towards the release of the beta version in December 2020.

In June 2020, the work started on **Milestone 6: SSHOC web platform continuous marketplace integration with SSHOC service offer 2/3**. The task force prepared a plan and connected with the leads, in this case ESS Survey, to align on development. Also, special attention went out to updating the sections “Training”, “SSH Open Marketplace access”, the “SSHOC services & tools catalogue”, “About” and “Resources”. In alignment with T2.2 and WP6, the team worked on fostering the engagement with end-user communities. A dedicated sub-menu will be highlighting SSHOC activities with the SSH Open Marketplace Tester community, SSH Training Community and the SSH research communities from WP9.

Improvements on the SSHOC Website <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/> are the main result of this task, with a registration mechanism for the newsletter, training and SSH tester community on the SSHOC website, feeding into the GDPR compliant database of the project. The latest implementation of the Website is focused on an **improved navigation experience, greater functionality** and **easier access** to more information. As one of the major upgrades, the initial SSHOC Service Catalogue is now available on the SSHOC website: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/service-catalogue>. In the catalogue services can be found that will be produced within the frame of the SSHOC project as mapped and validated with WP leaders. The Catalogue is complete with delivery timeline and clearly formulated individual pages, that will be enriched with all the incoming content for each service. Services were also categorised in alignment with the EOSC Portal and can be filtered as such. In year 2 of the project the website has received **25.700+ visits from 12.900+ new users**.

2.2.2. Note on deviations from the plan and risk monitoring

Milestone 5 was postponed from December 2019 to March 2020 because project partners experienced delays in the identification of the categories, revised timelines and result types of the services and tools to be delivered during the project's lifetime, for the optimal cataloguing of the service offer on the SSHOC website. The identification is now used in the SSHOC EOSC Enhance alignment task force for the onboarding of services in the EOSC Portal.

Due to the COVID-19 global health crisis SSHOC WP2 worked on the following issues not foreseen in the workplan or adapted due to confinement rules in Europe:

1. Promotion of SSHOC organised and attended events turned virtual. The SSHOC organised virtual events were recorded by WP6, and promoted for reuse by WP2. A total of 2132 people attended the online events, the recordings were viewed over 5160 times in year 2.

³² Willems, Marieke & Leonardo Marino. (2020). M5 SSHOC web platform continuous marketplace integration with SSHOC service offer 1/3: M9, M10, M12 (Version v1.0). Zenodo. 10.5281/zenodo.4581200

- The SSHOC Stakeholder forum foreseen to take place in June 2020 had to be postponed and change format to online and hybrid complying with safety issues and SSHOC goals to engage with the full range of stakeholders. It started with the first event in what will be a SSHOC Stakeholder Series, the joint event with FREYA and EOSC-Hub projects.

Deliverable 2.2 Preliminary report on user communities engagement, due in December 2020, was delayed - due to the COVID-19 pandemic WP2 & WP6 were forced to adapt the planning around the stakeholder forum. *Milestone 6: SSHOC web platform continuous marketplace integration with SSHOC service offer 2/3* due in December was also delayed, as it is dependent on Milestone 31 from WP5.

Information on risk monitoring in WP2 for Year 2 is presented in the table below:

Table 5. Risk monitoring in WP2 - Year 2

Risks monitoring WP2				
<i>Risk (DoA)</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Mitigation measures applied?</i>	<i>Risk materialised so far?</i>	<i>Comments</i>
2	Lack of visibility through media channels	Yes	No	Targeted messages were sent directly via the multiplier channels, liaisons with other EOSC projects made.
3	Lack of engagement at outreach events	Yes	No	Targeted messaging is used for each event to attract the envisioned stakeholders for engagement. Each event is promoted via the SSHOC channels and multiplied via partner networks. Interactive elements are included in events to collect input and feedback from stakeholders. Recordings & outputs of events are made available for reuse via SSHOC channels.
5	Inefficient use of resources: survey creation, translation and storing	Yes	No	Apart from the regular calls, additional task force calls were set up, messages via the internal communication platform and personal emails were sent to collect input, and ensure participation and alignment.

2.3. WP3 - Lifting Technologies and Services into the SSH Cloud

In the second year the WP3 tasks built on the results of year one, the landscape inventories and surveys, and started with the implementation activities. Realising that the mentioned surveys and inventories are necessarily non-exhaustive and often in need of extension, such additions were provided where needed: in (Task 3.1) Vocabulary platform, (Task 3.4) Citation, (Task 3.5) interoperability needs, and (Task 3.6) use-cases and integration opportunities for SSHOC Switchboard and VCR. Implementation plans were achieved for Tasks 3.4, 3.5 and 3.6 (MS13 -Intermediate evaluation of developed TDM algorithms, MS14 -Inventory of existing (meta-)data format interoperability solutions). Also, discussions were continued about a more efficient collaboration and resource distribution over the different WP3 tasks.

WP3 lead was active together with the different task leaders promoting WP3 activities at conferences such as presenting contributions at the Bazaar poster session of the annual CLARIN conference (October 2020), to inform about the vocabulary initiative and to gather feedback from users in the discussion session and several sessions at the conference *REALISING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD*³³ (November 2020).

2.3.1. WP3 progress

2.3.1.1. TASK 3.1 MULTILINGUAL TERMINOLOGY

Task 3.1 (Leader CNR with partners CESSDA/ADP,FORS, FSD, GESIS, CentERdata, CLARIN ERIC, Athena, CUNI, UVT-EVS) aims to provide the background resources and tools to be used in the project to make data and services accessible and usable in SSH. One of the main aims is to provide multilingual metadata and taxonomies to maximize the accessibility and to improve discovery by non-native speakers.

In 2020, efforts mainly concentrated on **Multilingual Metadata and Taxonomies**, in order to provide (i) SSHOC recommendations for the vocabulary server and publication platform; (ii) to create multilingual metadata and taxonomies for discovery and to publish the translated vocabularies as a catalogue.

As concerns the vocabulary platform, the original plans to discuss the intermediate recommendations provided in *Milestone 8 report* at the LR4SSHOC Workshop³⁴ were cancelled in light of COVID pandemic. Instead it was decided to work with the CLARIN vocabulary initiative organising:

- **a series of three online info-sessions with experts** to further discuss the vocabulary hosting platforms (September 2020)³⁵ and

³³ Conference organised by EOSCHub-FREYA-SSHOC projects jointly - Realising the European Open Science Cloud <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/realising-european-open-science-cloud> [accessed 21.01.2021]

³⁴ LR4SSHOC Workshop, the Language Resources for the SSH Cloud: <https://www.clarin.eu/LR4SSHOC> [19.01.2021]

³⁵ SSHOC Online Information Sessions: Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms: <https://www.clarin.eu/event/2020/sshoc-online-information-sessions-open-source-vocabulary-hosting-and-management> [accessed 21.01.2021]

- a **SSHOC webinar** to present and discuss the intermediate recommendations, collect new insights and let new outcomes emerge (November 2020)³⁶.

These meetings have been organized in the framework of the WP-“transversal” **initiative towards harmonizing different vocabulary tasks in SSHOC** info sessions³⁷, under the CLARIN ERIC coordination.

As concerns **multilingual metadata**, starting from the first inventory of metadata schemas with candidate vocabularies provided in the Report on *Milestone 10 Inventory of SSHOC metadata sets and taxonomies* (together with CUNI, and collaboration by Athena and CESSDA) a first set of CLARIN CCR metadata and their descriptions was translated in French, German, Czech, Hindi, Russian, using the UFAL translation pipeline. A methodology for assessing the quality of the translation has been identified. Activities were also initiated on Multilingual document collections. The type of data to be collected was chosen; it has been agreed upon to first concentrate on ISO standardization documents which are easy to access thanks to the presence of various ISO experts at ILC-CNR and within CLARIN. A plan for multilingual terminology extraction was also drafted.

The work towards the provision of a **Multilingual Occupation Ontology**, with lead CLARIN-ERIC and partner CUNI, has also started with aims to create female and male occupational titles for the multi-country, multilingual ontology of occupational titles, which is among others, used for the survey question 'What is your occupation?'. For many languages the occupational titles for males and females are not identical. The challenge is to apply machine translation tools to generate the female version of job titles for German and a set of East-European Languages. A machine translation approach to generate the female version of the occupational titles has been explored, but, today, machine translation is not feasible for this purpose. German female titles were added manually, and for Czech, the possibility of generating female titles from male titles has been explored.

In addition to the intense activity of webinars, dissemination activities were carried out: participation in the publishing of the Proceedings of LR4SSHOC³⁸, a contribution at the Bazaar poster session of the annual CLARIN conference (October 2020), to inform about the vocabulary initiative. A contribution at AIUCD2021 - Italian Association for Digital Humanities in January 2021 was planned.

2.3.1.2. TASK 3.2 SELECTED SSH ONTOLOGIES AND VOCABULARIES

Task 3.2 is led by CLARIN/WageIndicator and partners are CentERdata, SHARE/Unive, and TiU-EVS. They aim to foster the use of selected global ontologies in the social sciences and humanities, regarding

³⁶SSHOC Workshop: Considerations for the Vocabulary Platforms:

<https://www.clarin.eu/event/2020/sshoc-considerations-vocabulary-platforms-virtual-workshop> [19.01.2021]

³⁷ Takeaways from the SSHOC Webinar Series on Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/takeaways-sshoc-webinar-series-open-source-vocabulary-hosting-and-management-platforms> [21.01.2021]

³⁸ The workshop about language resources for the SSH Cloud by organising the publication of workshop proceedings dedicated to different aspects of this topic, see:

<https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/events/lrec-2020/#2020-lr4sshoc-1> - LREC2020 (May 2020); [19.01.2021]

occupational titles, educational categories, sectors of industry, geographical regions, food items, and religions. These ontologies allow to classify elements into standard global classifications, for example the ISCO classification of occupations and its derived social status or the NACE/ISIC classification of industries.

During 2020 the partners were involved in a number of activities: CentERdata was updating the website **surveycodings.org**, to rethink new features that are in line with FAIR, and making technical improvements on front and backend. Due to a heavy workload in relation to COVID-19 surveys CentERdata decided to relocate some effort to partners TiU-EVS and ESS/GESIS. These partners will work on the task from 2021.

TiU-EVS proceeded working on the database of religious denominations. TiU-EVS added religious denominations, and consequently the database now counts around **2400 combinations of religious denominations-countries**. Following feedback provided by colleagues from OnBound, TiU-EVS is preparing summary files of each county for the translations to be checked. Where possible, these summaries will be sent to EVS/WVS³⁹ country teams or to other scholars for confirmation. By the end of 2020, around **40 countries** were fully ready for the check.

SHARE/Unive continued its work on recovering the codification of occupations for the non-coded job description text strings, collected in the SHARE survey. Such strings include the occupation of respondents' parents (wave 2-5, 118552 strings), the retrospective occupations collected (wave 3, 74529 strings), and all occupation strings collected in the survey from wave 6 onwards, in the situations when the Jobcoder instrument did not work properly. The coding effort aims to obtain a complete job-description-history for the entire SHARE sample. By the end of 2020, SHARE/Unive has **completed the codification** of the retrospective occupation coding for France and the French speaking respondents in Belgium and is on its way for Italian and Spanish respondents. The codification of the parents' occupations has been completed for France, Germany and Italy.

Task 3.2 team organised a session on the conference *REALISING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD, Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the social sciences, humanities and beyond*. The session, held 18 November, was called **SSHOC Surveycodings**. Several sets of classified key economic indicator variables were introduced, notably occupation, education, industry, religion. These can be used by survey holders in their questionnaires in several languages and in several survey modes. CentERdata and CESSDA/GESIS presented their work for surveycodings.org, a free service for survey projects, data archives and individual survey researchers measuring and coding socio-economic background variables, while CLARIN chaired the session.

2.3.1.3. TASK 3.3 TEXT & DATA MINING

Task 3.3. is led by CLARIN with partners from CLARIN/ATHENA, CLARIN/CUNI, DARIAH/UGOE. During the second half of the year, partners involved in this task have elaborated and **expanded previously**

³⁹ The European Value Study(EVS) and the World Value Survey (WVS) are two large-scale, cross-national and longitudinal survey research programs

defined use cases and datasets based on current results and due to the changes in the overall research landscape, e.g. COVID-19 pandemic. This additional line of research offered opportunities for further collaboration within SSHOC with other partners, such as SciencesPo, thus enriching developed TDM methods and ensuring cross-domains collaboration at the next stage of SSHOC.

Overall achieved progress and investigations directions are extensively described in Report on **Milestone 13 - Intermediate evaluation of the developed TDM algorithms**.

- The challenges of multilinguality, manual annotation, and potential for TDM usefulness, are addressed on the two use cases: processing of collective bargaining agreements and exploration of the intertextuality phenomena in European drama history;
- The challenges caused by the processing of Twitter data, and requiring the involvement of the social scientists at different TDM development stages are investigated in the context of Verbal Aggression detection in Social Media.

Despite cancellation of many important scientific events in 2020, the partners involved in the task have managed to lead an important discussion about language resources for the SSH cloud by organising the publication of LR4SSHOC workshop proceedings dedicated to different aspects of this topic.

2.3.1.4. TASK 3.4 MAKING DATA FINDABLE BY BEING CITABLE

Task 3.4 is led by CNRS (Huma-Num) with partners CLARIN ERIC, DARIAH/UGOE, LIBER, and CNR. The main objective is to foster Data Citation by providing a **common mechanism to cite SSH data and build stronger links between data and publications**. An expected side effect would be to enhance the reproducibility of SSH research, which is not yet very common nowadays. In this regard, also an important point is to be able to give high visibility to the research data used in Social Science and Humanities following FAIR data principles.

After the submission of *Deliverable 3.2 (Inventory of SSH citation practices, and choice for SSHOC citation formats and implementation planning)*, it became clear that the Task 3.4 work plan needed to be updated leading to the development of what was called the “FAIR SSH Citation”: the main idea is to take existing citations, normalize them, enriched them with other sources and annotations and to present them in a standardized way so it could be machine actionable. As part of this plan, the task has been working on a prototype to implement a FAIR SSH citation repository. Work on a set of recommendations for Data Citation, based on the information gathered from the *D3.2 “Inventory of SSH citation format and implementation planning”* has started. At the annual CLARIN conference (October 2020) Task 3.4 team joined with Task 3.6 at an exhibition booth to present the work done and to gather feedback from potential users in a discussion session. A presentation was made during the final FREYA project event (October 2020) and a round table was organized during the conference *REALISING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD* conference in cooperation with SSHOC WP9.

2.3.1.5. TASK 3.5 DATA AND METADATA INTEROPERABILITY HUB

Task 3.5 is led by CESSDA/FSD with partners CESSDA/SND, CESSDA/UKDA, CLARIN ERIC, CLARIN/EKUT, DARIAH/OEAW, CNR and FORTH. It aims to address interoperability challenges within SSHOC by analysing the SSHOC work plan, following activities, and recommending solutions.

Milestone 14 - Inventory of existing (meta-)data format interoperability solutions⁴⁰ was achieved in June 2020, building on *D3.1 Report on SSHOC (meta-) data interoperability problems*. The report on the milestone covers the inventorisation process and results collecting information on relevant conversion services, technology and practices that fall within the scope of the SSHOC Interoperability Hub.

The interoperability landscape is broad but here the scope is limited: metadata and data format conversions, focussing on conversions between SSHOC recommended formats (D3.1) since they are essential for making SSHOC services interoperable. Work on gap analysis regarding conversions continued. A data model for interoperability solutions was created and Interoperability Hub architecture agreed. It was decided to provide the **Interoperability Hub portal** using the same technological solution as used for the SSHOC training toolkit: Drupal 9 and Drupal 9’s ecosystem Search API, and the first draft version was ready in October 2020.

The screenshot shows the SSHOC Conversion Hub search interface. It includes a search bar, a 'Search' button, and a list of filters for 'Community' and 'Input format'. The main content is a table displaying search results for conversion solutions.

Title	Alternative name	Description	Input format	Output format
3M			text/xml	?
Audacity			audio/*	audio/*
Beautiful Soup			text/html, text/xml	?
CHAMD			text/x-chat	application/prs.paqu-metadata
CMDI2DC			application/x-cmdi+xml	application/dc+xml
CMDI2Marc21			application/x-cmdi+xml	application/marcxml+xml
CMDI2RDF			application/x-cmdi+xml	?
Colectica for Excel			application/x-sas-data, application/x-stata, application/x-spss-sav	application/vnd.ms-excel
DDI Converter			application/vnd.ddi+xml;version=2.5	application/vnd.ddi+xml;version=3.2
DDI to HTML Stylesheet			application/vnd.ddi+xml;version=2.0	text/html
EAF recipe			text/x-chat	text/x-eaf+xml
ELAN			text/csv, text/praat-textgrid, text/x-chat	text/csv, text/praat-textgrid, text/x-chat
epidoc-xslt			?	text/html, application/tei+xml
Handbrake			video/*	video/*
Haven package		Haven enables R to read and write various data formats	application/x-spss-sav, application/x-sas-data, application/x-stata	application/x-spss-sav, application/x-stata

Figure 6. SSHOC Interoperability Hub portal first draft version; Screen Capture

Task 3.5 collaborated with Task 3.6 on Switchboard (CNR), and collaborations with Task 4.7 and WP7 have been discussed. The Interoperability Hub will be one of the tools listed in the SSHOC Marketplace. In addition, the Marketplace will include separate entries of solutions within the Interoperability Hub.

⁴⁰ Mari Kleemola, Daan Broeder, Thorsten Trippel, Iris Alfredsson, Matej Ďurčo, Klaus Illmayer, ... Emiliano Degl'Innocenti. (2020). MS14 Inventory of existing (meta-)data format interoperability solutions (Version v1.0). Zenodo. 10.5281/zenodo.4581289

Task team members from CESSDA/FSD and DARIAH/OEAW presented SSHOC approach in FAIRsFAIR and RDA Workshop on Metadata catalogues integration for Interdisciplinary Research in September 2020 and participated in a follow-up workshop in October 2020. On November 17, the task chaired session “Metadata Interoperability: SSHOC and Beyond” in the *REALISING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD* conference. Team members from CLARIN ERIC also participated in RDA 16th plenary sessions on semantic interoperability and vocabularies.

2.3.1.6. TASK 3.6 MAKING DATA RE-USABLE AND ACTIONABLE

Task 3.6, led by CLARIN ERIC with partners DAI, CLARIN/EKUT, DARIAH/OEAW, DARIAH/UGOE, CNR is concerned with creating a **SSHOC Switchboard and SSHOC virtual collection registry (VCR)**. It was intended to generalise and adapt the CLARIN Switchboard and VCR and adapt it to the needs of the other SSHOC communities. Building on results of Year 1 *Milestone 9 Inventory of services tools and domain of actionable data-types* and *Milestone 12 Implementation plan Switchboard and VCR services*, these reports were further expanded and refined. The existing implementation plans for both Switchboard and VCR were adapted and put into motion. In the context of collaboration with WP7 on the SSH Open Marketplace created a report “**Collaborative Use Cases between SSH Open Marketplace and the Switchboard and VCR**”⁴¹. Several meetings took place with representatives from Task 5.2 directed at finding use cases for integrating SSHOC Switchboard and VCR in the SSHOC Dataverse, resulting in a first implementation plan.

Name	Type	Created
▶ Signpost Demo Collection – Bonner Gerontologische Längsschnittstudie (BOLSA), all recordings of subject 2608	extensional	2021-01-25
▶ CLARIN services in the European Open Science Cloud	extensional	2020-11-13
▼ SSHOC Webinar: CLARIN Hands-on Tutorial on Transcribing Interview Data A high-quality orthographic transcript is the basis for all types of analyses of spoken language data. However, transcribing speech is a time-consuming and tedious task. But automatic speech recognition as well as NLP and text annotation tools can make this task much quicker and save you a lot of time and frustration. In this first of a series of SSHOC webinars, organised by the consortium partner CLARIN ERIC, we will discuss the theoretical basis and the technology available for transcribing spoken language. In particular, we will focus on the role of automatic speech recognition – what are the opportunities, what are the pitfalls and to where can it be applied successfully. This virtual collection bundles the Webinar’s slides, video recording and event page.	extensional	2020-10-14
▶ Extremadura Buenas Noches	extensional	2020-10-02
▶ PubMed references to articles on "face mask" and "influenza" as of May 2020	extensional	2020-07-17
▶ Pirineos La Nuit	extensional	2020-07-16
▶ DuFLOR - Dubbed Films	extensional	2018-06-13
▶ VLO search results: BAS	extensional	2017-08-29
▶ Trebanks for the RDA Collaboration Project	extensional	2016-06-24

Figure 7. Virtual Collection Registry - SSHOC virtual collection; Screen Capture

⁴¹ Buddenbohm, Stefan, Broeder, Daan, Eisner, Marthe Irene, Illmayer, Klaus, & Durco, Matej. (2020, November 5). Collaborative Use Cases between SSH Open Marketplace and the Language Resource Switchboard and Virtual Collection Registry. Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4442320 [19.01.2021]

Main achievements of the task in the year 2020 are the steady continuation of refining use-cases and SSHOC Switchboard and VCR software development while continuing our collaboration with the other SSHOC tasks. At the annual CLARIN conference in October 2020 Task 3.6 team organised a stall presenting the combined 3.6 and 3.4 activities.

On 16 November, Task 3.6 leader co-chaired a session “SSH thematic services” in the *REALISING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD* conference, while the other team members presented the SSHOC Switchboard and VCR service plans.

2.3.2. Note on deviations from the plan and risk monitoring

Task 3.4 worked on a new version of its work plan which will be finalized in Year 3 of the project, and had no deviations in 2020. Information on risk monitoring in WP3 for Year 2 is presented in the table below:

Table 6. Risk monitoring in WP3 - Year 2

Risks monitoring WP3				
Risk (DoA)	Description	Mitigation measures applied?	Risk materialised so far?	Comments
4	Insufficient cooperation from or access to SSH tool development teams	Yes	Yes	Some partners had difficulties meeting agreed contributions, but attempts to re-plan and reschedule were implemented and the consortium is monitoring the cooperation.
6	Too few available software developers	Yes	Yes	Some partners had difficulties in allocating work to software developers, but attempts to re-plan and reschedule were implemented and the consortium is monitoring the cooperation.

2.4. WP4 - Innovations in Data Production

SSHOC Work Package 4 tasks are concerned with the data creation phase of the data lifecycle and aim to develop, test and share innovative ways of producing data of interest to analysts and policy makers within the Social Sciences and Humanities with which to populate the Open Science Cloud.

In Year 2 of the SSHOC project Task 4.1 (A sample management system for cross-national web surveys) mainly aimed to test the sample management system, developed in Year 1. Task 4.2. ('Preparing tools for the use of Computer Assisted Translation) team centred on the publication of the first version of the Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires [MCSQ] and initial testing of the prototype interface. Task 4.3 (Applying Computer Assisted Translation in Social Surveys) had two main objectives in Year 2: to test and improve a bilingual word embedding model (English-German), and to conduct fieldwork of the Machine Translation experiments and preprocess and document the raw data obtained from the experiments. Task 4.4 (Voice recorded interviews and audio analysis) work centered on voice recorded interviews, while Task 4.5 work in 2020 centred around the development and testing of a Social Policy API's for Social Surveys. In Task 4.6 ('Semantic annotation of Heritage Science Data), the first beta-testing programme which involved selected actors of cultural heritage scientific and professional community, was completed. Finally, the activities of Task 4.7 (Modeling the SSHOC data life cycle) aimed at elaborating the definition of a common meta-level schema to model the full data life cycle of the Social Sciences and the Humanities.

2.4.1. WP4 progress

2.4.1.1. TASK 4.1. A SAMPLE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FOR CROSS-NATIONAL WEB SURVEYS

The first working version of the sample management system, named "Web Panel Sample Service" (WPSS) was released at the end of December 2019. A complete set of user guides were also made public at the same time. In January 2020, **internal testing** started at ESS headquarters to test the main functionalities implemented and identify additional functionalities to be added to the system. In particular 1) Headquarter role, 2) National coordinator role and 3) Panellist role, were tested.

Milestone 15 - Test of Sample Management System complete was achieved in July 2020 and concerned the test of the sample service to be performed in a cross-national setting. To this purpose a live test of the system was programmed in May 2020, for which a web survey pilot study was set up. The first wave of the WPSS cross-national live test was launched in mid-June 2020. Respondents were recruited off the back of the ESS Round 10 pilot and adults aged 18+ in the United Kingdom and Austria were invited to join the test study. The test was completed on the 9 July 2020. After the pilot test, the team at ESS headquarters and at SciencesPo worked together to deliver an updated version of the WPSS which included several additional functionalities. A new version of the sample service was released in October 2020. A complete specification of the WPSS panellist user was established at the end of October 2020.

2.4.1.2. TASK 4.2. PREPARING TOOLS FOR THE USE OF COMPUTER ASSISTED TRANSLATION

The first version of the **MCSQ (Ada Lovelace)** was officially released in June 2020. In this release, the MCSQ was composed of datasets from ESS (rounds 1 to 6) and EVS (waves 3 and 4) in the English source

versions and their translations into Catalan, Czech, French (France, Switzerland, Belgium and Luxembourg), German (Austria, Germany, Switzerland and Luxembourg), Norwegian, Portuguese, Spanish and Russian (Israel, Latvia, Lithuania, Russian Confederation, Ukraine, Estonia). This release corresponded to deliverables **D4.3 Survey specific parallel corpora'** which is the data itself, and **D4.4: Guidelines for building survey-specific corpora**, which is a report about the design and compilation of the corpus, both submitted in June 2020. The **MCSQ version 1.1 (Beatrice Worsley)** was then released in October 2020. In this version, in addition to improvements in the preprocessing and alignments scripts that led to an overall increase of data quality, model adjustments and bug fixes, SHARE COVID questionnaires were included for the following languages: Czech (Czech Republic), English (Malta and source questionnaire), French (Belgium, Switzerland, Luxembourg, France), German (Austria, Switzerland, Luxembourg, Germany), Portuguese (Portugal), Spanish (Spain) and Russian (Estonia, Israel, Latvia). Currently, MCSQ holds **404.041 text sentences** from **169 distinct datasets**.

The screenshot shows the website for the Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires (MCSQ) at upf.edu/web/mcsq. The page features a navigation menu with links for [MCSQ], Project, How to cite, News, and Members. A large banner image displays a collage of diverse human faces, with a globe graphic overlaid. The main heading reads "[MCSQ]: The Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires" with a button labeled "Access Database >".

[MCSQ]: The Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires is an entity-relationship (ER) database of survey questions in English language and their translations into Catalan, Czech, French, German, Norwegian, Portuguese, Spanish and Russian. It is part of the [Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud \(SSHOC\)](#) project.

Version 1 (Ada Lovelace) includes questionnaires from the [European Social Survey](#) and the [European Values Study](#).

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Figure 8. [MCSQ] interface; Screen Capture

Furthermore, the UPF team developed a **dedicated web interface**⁴² that runs on top of the MCSQ SQL-database. The interface achieved prototype phase by December 2020. Dissemination started after the second release (version 1.1), the [MCSQ] was presented at the 20th ESS Core Scientific Team meeting and the 15th ESS National Coordinators Forum, both in November 2020. The [MCSQ] was presented at the EOSC-HUB, FREYA, SSHOC Conference in November 2020. The UPF team's second year was of preparation for the release of the (last) version 2.0 of the [MCSQ], which in addition to the inclusion of new datasets, will include part-of-speech data annotation. The fruitful collaboration between the EVS and UPF teams continues, as the EVS team collaborates with manual work in data that will feature in the version 2.0 release.

2.4.1.3. TASK 4.3. APPLYING COMPUTER ASSISTED TRANSLATION TOOLS IN SOCIAL SURVEYS

During the first six months of 2020, the team members continued developing a bilingual word embedding model (English-German), namely the Automated Verification Tool (AVT). It took several iterations of different versions, e.g. supervised vs. unsupervised models, to select the best modelling approach. Once the model was trained, the team tested it to flag translated questions that did not satisfy the chosen quality criteria. The translation of the German questionnaires (DE, AT, CH, LU) for the SHARE wave 8 COVID CATI were verified using the AVT and the team sent flagged items to the translators for revision. During the second part of the year, the team analysed the data to evaluate the performance of the tool and to compute false positive rates. The team presented preliminary results at international conferences collecting useful feedback, namely the EOSC-HUB-FREYA-SSHOC Conference in November 2020 and the BigSurv20 which ran during November and December 2020. In order to improve the performance of the model the team started to collect a new set of training data, from the MCSQ version 1.1 developed by ESS/UPF in Task 4.2. "Preparing tools for the use of Computer Assisted Translation.

Machine Translation (MT) experiment: The MT team (ESS/UPF and ESS/GESIS) achieved their **Milestone 17 Open source CAT TM software selected**⁴³. Up till September, they finalised all decisions for the experiment (e.g., selection of test persons or of items). Between mid-September and end of October 2020, they successfully completed data collection in the experiment: After training all test persons, those assigned with translation and post-editing, respectively, completed their tasks (T in the TRAPD model). Subsequently, ESS/GESIS coordinated and managed six 8-hour long review team discussions (R in the TRAPD model; 3 review discussions for English-German; 3 review discussions for English-Russian). It needs to be noted that all steps, including team translation discussions, eventually took place online due to Covid restrictions. The remaining time till the end of the year was dedicated to data curation, management and preparation for qualitative and quantitative analyses, as well as developing and fine-tuning the analysis methods (e.g., error schemes for quality assessment).

2.4.1.4. TASK 4.4. VOICE RECORDED INTERVIEWS AND AUDIO ANALYSIS

Both qualitative and quantitative research are the building blocks for the social sciences and humanities domain. While qualitative research is mostly used to advance theory, understand mechanisms and

⁴² [MCSQ] interface: <http://easy.mcsq.upf.edu/> [accessed 18.01.2021]

⁴³ Zavala-Rojas, Diana, Veronika Keck, Danielly Sorato, Dorothee Behr, & Brita Dorer. (2020). MS17 Open source CAT TM software selected (Version v1.0). Zenodo. 10.5281/zenodo.4581805

develop hypotheses, quantitative research is used to understand when certain phenomena occur and how often they occur. Qualitative data is often generated through the gathering of texts, audio and video recordings and interview transcripts. Instead, quantitative information is mostly generated through experiments and surveys. Traditionally, quantitative and qualitative information from respondents is collected through separate processes. At the end of 2019 *D4.12: "Audio Survey Modules"* was submitted. This deliverable provided the guidelines for the integration of Audio Capture data in Survey Interviews. In the year 2020, the Task team focused on taking these guidelines forward by **preparing the technical implementations for data collection**. The COVID-19 situation forced the team to adapt the Technical Specifications outlined in D4.12. The plan was to collect the Audio Module during fieldwork of the Dutch Generations and Gender Survey at the start of 2021.

2.4.1.5. TASK 4.5. SOCIAL POLICY APIS FOR SOCIAL SURVEYS

In 2020, an API was built by the Task team, which is based on the OECD Family Database. This database is accessible via the web and provides for different countries and individual scenarios information on child benefits through benefits and wages, birth related leave benefits, and income and tax reductions. The API allows users to extract responses from the OECD Calculator through an internet connection, making the data much more findable, accessible and interoperable than previously. **Deliverable 4.14 Policy API tool⁴⁴** was submitted to the EC portal in March 2020.

In 2020, the Task team has further discussed the possible strategies of integrating this API in a survey. It has been decided to integrate⁴⁵ the API into the WageIndicator Survey⁴⁵. The mission of the WageIndicator platform is to provide transparency about labour market information to promote fair pay. In addition, the platform invites its visitors to take part in the WageIndicator Survey. The data that is generated via this survey is used for research. The WageIndicator Survey already collects information about the number of children, age of the youngest child, income of the respondent and partner status. This information will be fed into the API to calculate the family related benefits of that person. The result of this calculation will be shown to the respondent and they will be asked if they think this information is correct, and if not, which benefits their household actually receives. Because the WageIndicator Survey already collects much of the necessary information, the additional burden for the respondent that is caused by the inclusion of the Social Policy API module, will be limited.

2.4.1.6. TASK 4.6. SEMANTIC ANNOTATION OF HERITAGE SCIENCE DATA

In the Task 4.6 the main activities of the Year 2020 of the reporting period focused on the development of the features defined in *D4.16 Specification of the new features of the Aioli⁴⁶* platform, which concern the technical robustness of the platform, the collaboration framework, the management of controlled vocabularies and the compatibility with the CIDOC-CRM (in collaboration with FORTH). The results of these first works are reported in the first deliverable (D4.16) submitted in 2019. The beta testing of Aioli platform has demonstrated a great interest from the users of the Cultural Heritage community. In order

⁴⁴ Emery, Tom. (2020). SSHOC D4.14 Policy API Tool (Version v1.0). Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3725925.

⁴⁵ WageIndicator Survey:

<https://wageindicator.org/Wageindicatorfoundation/researchlab/wageindicator-survey-and-data> [17.01.2021]

⁴⁶ Aioli platform: <http://www.aioli.cloud/> [17.01.2021]

to increase the use scenarios, it is necessary to face technical issues related to the management of large volumes of data.

In 2020, the team focused on **mapping the Aioli dataset** with CIDOC CRM high level classes but also classes of specific domain ontologies such as CRMdig (digital provenance). A first mapping has been defined for the description of the Heritage asset and the Annotation process within the Aioli platform. This mapping has been submitted to FORTH for comments, corrections and suggestions. This exchange allowed the sharing of elements (the schema of the Aioli database and an archive of an Aioli project) and the improvement of the mapping definition. The collaboration continues with FORTH to further elaborate and enrich the mapping concerning the annotation process and to define a mapping for the photogrammetric process. As a further work in the framework of SSHOC, Tasks 4.6 and 4.7 would be to use Aioli Project datasets (from photogrammetric acquisition to annotation process) as a use case to test, assess and validate SSHOCro ontology model. To this end, the team will further collaborate with FORTH to organize the data sets.

2.4.1.7. TASK 4.7. MODELING THE SSHOC DATA LIFE CYCLE

In the framework of the Task 4.7 **Deliverable 4.18 SSHOCro (beta version) v1.0**⁴⁷ was produced and made available to the SSHOC community for testing purposes. D4.18 was the outcome of a stepwise process that involved analysing research workflows from the domains of the social sciences and the humanities, like cultural heritage, historical research, NLP, [socio]linguistic analysis, economics and psychology –to name but a few. Emphasis was placed on experimental data collection, analysis and management, which includes methods and tools for collection, and processing, statistical methods and tools for analysis, storing and reusing, as well as documenting each of these stages. Work on D4.18 continued until 24 January 2020, when the SSHOCro (beta) meta-level schema and supporting documentation were submitted for reviewing. The updated definition of the SSHOCro (beta) was submitted to the EC portal and appeared on Zenodo, in March 2020.⁴⁸

Once SSHOCro (beta) v1.0 was produced, the effort concentrated on validating the proposed schema by mapping metadata from selected metadata standards to it (**Deliverable 4.19 Mapping of two indicative selected standards to the SSHOCro**⁴⁹). This action, concluded in December 2020 was informed by the decisions reached in the context of **Milestone 20 - SSH metadata standards for mapping to SSHOCro selected**⁵⁰, a report on the process of selecting said metadata standards. The metadata standards

⁴⁷ Bekiari ,Chrysoula, Kritsotaki, Athina, & Tsouloucha, Eleni. (2020). SSHOC D4.18 SSHOC Reference Ontology (beta version) (Version v1.0). Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3744860

⁴⁸ Building trustworthy repositories: Introduction to CoreTrustSeal certification (Virtual workshop during the DARIAH Virtual Annual Event 2020):
<https://sshopencloud.eu/building-trustworthy-repositories-introduction-coretrustseal-certification> [21.01.2021]

⁴⁹ Tsouloucha, Eleni, Athina Kritsotaki, Chrysoula Bekiari, & Maria Theodoridou. (2021). D4.19 Mapping of two indicative selected standards to the SSHOCro (Version v1.0). Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4457495

⁵⁰ Bekiari, Chrysoula, Eleni Tsouloucha, Athina Kritsotaki, Maurizio Sanesi, Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, & Ariane Neroulidis. (2020). MS 20 Selection of SSH metadata standards for mapping to SSHOCro (Version v1.0). Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4582017

chosen to be mapped to SSHOCro were DDI Codebook⁵¹ and CMDI⁵² – the former in view of being used in documenting research activities/tools/services relevant for CESSDA and CLARIN, i.e. two major stakeholders of SSHOC. The decision was motivated by (i) an extensive literature review on metadata standards used by the SSHOC communities, (ii) a careful consideration of SSHOC deliverables upon publication, and (iii) a thorough search on online resources/repositories for metadata records adhering to their respective metadata schema.

To be able to follow the workflows, tools and services used by social scientists and humanities scholars, the team of T4.7 attended a series of online events and webinars organized by SSHOC partners:

- CLARIN Hands-on Tutorial on Transcribing Interview Data,⁵³
- Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms.⁵⁴
- Introducing the newly launched Ethnic and Migrant Minorities (EMM) Survey Registry⁵⁵
- SSHOC Considerations for the Vocabulary Platforms⁵⁶
- DARIAH Annual Event 2020⁵⁷

Figure 9. Example of WP4 Events at SSHOC website

⁵¹ DDI Codebook 2.5, available through the DDI alliance website:

<https://ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-Codebook/2.5/>; [10.02.2021]

⁵² CMDI: <http://www.clarin.eu/cmdi> [06.01.2021]

⁵³ see Appendix - Tables of events, and Section 2.6 of this report - WP6

⁵⁴ see Appendix - Tables of events, and Section 2.3 of this report - WP3

⁵⁵ see Appendix - Tables of events, and Section 2.6 of this report - WP6

⁵⁶ see Appendix - Tables of events, and Section 2.6 of this report - WP6

⁵⁷ DARIAH Annual Event 2020: <https://dariah-ae-2020.sciencesconf.org/> [21.01.2021]

2.4.2. Note on deviations from the plan and risk monitoring

In WP4 the Task 4.2. (Preparing tools for the use of Computer Assisted Translation) *MS16 focussed on Survey questions extracted from TMT and delivered in machine readable format* was due in September 2020 but data pre-processing has proved to be more difficult than expected especially due to COVID-19 situation the team needed more time. However, the Milestone is to be achieved soon, from the three survey projects (SHARE, EVS and ESS) only ESS is outstanding.

In task 4.3 (“Applying Computer Assisted Translation in Social Surveys”) *MS18 on Beta version of automatic verification software available for testing*, was due in December 2020 and has not been achieved.

In Task 4.4 (Voice recorded interviews and audio analysis), due to the pandemic the plan to collect the Audio Module during fieldwork of the Dutch Generations and Gender Survey has been postponed. For this reason, the Task team is exploring alternative strategies to collect the data. Collecting data through the LISS-panel has been identified as a viable alternative strategy.

The Task 4.8 *Report on possibilities for incorporating open source CAT tool functionality into the TMT* that was due in December 2020 could not be finished because of the issue of staff availability. The implementation of the activity is postponed till June 2021.

Information on risk monitoring in WP4 for Year 2 is presented in the table below:

Table 7. Risk monitoring in WP4 - Year 2

Risks monitoring WP4				
<i>Risk (DoA)</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Mitigation measures applied?</i>	<i>Risk materialised so far?</i>	<i>Comments</i>
6	Too few available software developers	Yes	Yes	The risk has materialised because developers/programmers have faced difficulties to work from home efficiently and that has led to the delay of MS16 and D4.7.

2.5. WP5 - Innovations in Data Access

WP5 facilitates innovations in data access and will provide tools and services for intelligently open data for the SSH domain to be incorporated into the EOSC cloud. Year 2 focused on implementing the specifications outlined in Year 1.

More precisely, the respective tasks **focused on tool development and refinement** (T5.2, T5.5), **writing guidelines and frameworks** (T5.1, T5.3, T5.4), connecting and transferring knowledge on **FAIR data** across communities (T5.6), and intensifying collaboration and **developing applicable workflows** (T5.7). As a result, WP5 achieved two milestones, and submitted two deliverables planned for Year 2. The development of three further deliverables has been completed, but revisions and submission reached into 2021.

2.5.1. WP5 progress

2.5.1.1. TASK 5.1 LEGAL, ETHICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL ISSUES OF ACCESS TO BIOMEDICAL DATA

This task is led by SHARE ERIC, and the partner contributing in Year 2 was CentERdata. Major progress has been made in all work areas of Task 5.1. The main achievements of Task 5.1 in Year 2 was the submission of D5.2, the draft completion of D5.1 and the achievement of M22.

- **Primary analyses of the DBSS** in specialised laboratories are underway and progressing well. Laboratory processing had to be interrupted due to Covid-19 for two months in Spring 2020 and resumed in June 2020. Completion of all analyses is expected in Summer 2021.

Deliverable 5.2 “Data access protocol for DBSS data, linked to survey data, conforming FAIR principles (Access to biomedical data)”⁵⁸ has been submitted in November 2020. The document describes the preparation of the SHARE DBSS data for release, the measures taken to make the data FAIR and the conditions of data access for the SHARE data in general as well as for the DBSS data. There will be no additional conditions for the use of the biomarker data as compared to the regular SHARE survey data.

- The target of the **accelerometer project** was to collect 2000 net complete datasets overall, 200 per country. End of March 2020, the accelerometer data collection had to be suspended, like the regular SHARE Wave 8 data collection, as a result of the Covid-19 outbreak in all European countries⁵⁹. At the time of the interruption, about **850 complete accelerometer datasets** had been collected. Due to the ongoing global pandemic, the accelerometer data collection will not be resumed. The available data will be released as planned. The smaller number of observations

⁵⁸ Luzia M. Weiss. (2020). D5.2 Data access protocol for DBSS data, linked to survey data, conforming FAIR principles (Access to biomedical data) (Version v1.0). Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4405216

⁵⁹ More on the history of events and the SHARE response in data collection can be found in: Scherpenzeel, A., et al (2020). Collecting survey data among the 50+ population during the COVID-19 outbreak: The Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE). Survey Research Methods, 14(2), 217-221.

might lead to less statistical power than initially envisioned. However, FAIR principles or the aim of SSHOC will not be affected.

Milestone 22 - Inventory of computing space needed for processing and analysing accelerometer data was achieved in August 2020. It reports the evaluation of the feasibility and technical requirements to handle and perform analysis on accelerometer data in large studies. The two main challenges on data transfer and data preparation were identified and successfully addressed. Though the processing takes very long and the first set-up of the implementation is cumbersome, the conclusion is positive: The data transfer can be arranged in an easy and secure way and it is feasible to do the data processing with standard office computers.

- **Deliverable 5.1 “Guidelines for ethics considerations in making biomedical survey data FAIR (Access to biomedical data)”** has been written in 2020 and will be under review and submitted in 2021. The comprehensive documentation provides useful information and support for preparing the implementation of biomedical data collections. The focus of the deliverable addresses the ethical requirements as well as on solutions to make such data FAIR.

2.5.1.2. TASK 5.2 HOSTING AND SHARING DATA REPOSITORIES

Task 5.2 is led by KNAW(DANS), and the partners contributing to this task are CESSDA/AUSSDA, DARIAH/PSNC, DARIAH/UGOE, CLARIN/UIT and CNR. Task 5.2 makes use of the Dataverse open source software⁶⁰ and adapt it to the needs of the European SSH research community. To make implementation on cloud platforms feasible, a continuous integration pipeline running on Jenkins in the CESSDA cloud was developed. Extra functionalities based on common needs of CESSDA, DARIAH, CLARIN and E-RIHS will be developed during the project.

The work in the second project year was mainly focused on continuation, **improvement and refinement** of the implementation of the Dataverse installation and the required functionalities. To obtain feedback from data managers and researchers **two webinars** were organised, one for CESSDA Service Providers in M15 (March 2020)⁶¹, a second one for the DARIAH community (September 2020)⁶². The consultation with the designated communities will be continued in 2021. Additional to the webinars, a presentation was given about translation of the User Interface (UI) of Dataverse⁶³. To translate the UI in all the European languages, a workflow was developed by which translators of the various national

⁶⁰ Dataverse is an open source web application to share, preserve, cite, explore, and analyze research data (<https://dataverse.org/>).

⁶¹ Slides of the Dataverse Webinar for the CESSDA community are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3714988>. The recording can be viewed here: <https://youtu.be/f7-r-80M-Fk>. [19.07.2020]

⁶² Slides of the Dataverse Webinar for the DARIAH community are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4054847>. The recording can be viewed here: <https://youtu.be/wiPg6yal8Rk>

⁶³ Presentation at Event Realising the Open Science Cloud: *Dataverse, Adaptation to the European Research Environment, Translation of the User Interface*. Slides are available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4279182> Recordings can be viewed at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jyNZ5gDcaDg> [21.01.2021]

languages can work together and make these translations to be a crowd effort. Task 5.2 has also consulted with SSHOC task 3.6 about collaboration to integrate the task 3.6 switchboard with Dataverse.

2.5.1.3. TASK 5.3 LEGAL ISSUES OF INNOVATIVE DATA ACCESS

This task is led by NSD, and the partners contributing in Year 2 were CESSDA/DDA and CNR. The main result in the second year has been the work on an extensive report on the **impact of the GDPR on research** and possible implications for EOSC (D5.7). The full draft was completed until October 2020, followed by a thorough review period, and revisions stretching into 2021. The report is likely to be submitted in early 2021. D5.7 assesses the impact of the GDPR on research and its implications for EOSC by re-evaluating and extending **Milestone 27 - Draft report on the impact of the GDPR on research and the EOSC**, which has been achieved in February 2020, and conducting qualitative interviews with researchers from Denmark, Norway and Italy on their experiences and challenges with the implementation of the GDPR. The report describes and compares national implementations of the GDPR, with focus on some specific countries: Norway, Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Germany and Italy. This report has compared national data protection legislation and analysed whether or not they are beneficial for research and archival purposes. It also shows how the research environment in some countries has experienced GDPR's impact on research and identifies some possible implications GDPR might have for EOSC. The findings in the report show that some of the countries have implemented provisions in their national legislation that are beneficial for research, but not all. The report also shows that such different interpretations, among other factors, might have implications for EOSC.

Furthermore, the task partners have continued preparing the (D5.19) Stakeholder workshop about the SSH Code of Conduct, to be held in early 2021. The workshop will be held virtual and the task collaborates with Task 6.2 for assistance in organising the event.

Task 5.3 has been in further contact with different organisations in Europe working on the GDPR and research, such as the BBMRI-ERIC's work on a Health and Life Science Code of Conduct about potential collaborations. This is in preparation of the tasks final deliverable *D5.8 Draft SSH Code of Conduct*. The overall aim of this task is to **initiate the work on a SSH GDPR Code of Conduct** to be handed over to and finalized in Task 8.3 Legal and Ethical Issues. The GDPR encourages the use of approved codes of conduct as a tool to ensure correct legal application and demonstrate compliance with the GDPR. This gives the scientific community a new opportunity to create a formal common framework to demonstrate compliance and facilitate harmonization of data-sharing rules and practices e.g. in relation to research, making it easier to access and share research data that also contains personal data.

2.5.1.4. TASK 5.4 REMOTE ACCESS TO SENSITIVE DATA

This task is led by CESSDA/GESIS, and the partners contributing in Year 2 were CESSDA/UKDA, CESSDA/FORS, CLARIN/RUN, and CLARIN ERIC. During 2020, the main focus and the main achievement for this task has been the work on the deliverable **D5.9 Framework for Data Use Agreements⁶⁴**. In order to increase the usability of the template, it was agreed to do additional edits, which have successfully

⁶⁴ Woollard, Matthew, Beate Lichtwardt, Elizabeth Lea Bishop, & Dana Müller. (2021). D5.9 Framework and contract for international data use agreements on remote access to confidential data (Version v1.0). Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4534285

been implemented until the end of 2020 (final Deliverable submitted in January 2021). D5.9 provides a **Template Contract on the Provision of Safe Room Remote Desktop Access** and, more generally, a Conceptual Framework for Access to Confidential/Sensitive Data. It will aid and enable future international collaborations on confidential/sensitive data use. It serves as advice through necessary considerations and can be adapted to other institutions planning to facilitate access to their confidential/sensitive microdata via Safe Room Remote Desktop Access.

Work has started on **D5.10 Requirements and Recommendations for Remote Secure Access in the Social Sciences and Humanities**. It consists of two parts:

(1) Landscape and definitions of varieties of Remote Secure Access (RSA): Minimal requirements for RSA - Within 2020, a draft document **defining access conditions for sensitive data** has been completed. This was produced for GESIS (social science data) and is compared to UKDA (also social sciences) and being integrated with linguistics data (CLARIN).

(2) Platform Assessment and Recommendations - these two sections will be written based on Milestones 28 and 30, namely, Assessments of Existing Platforms, and Recommendations for a Platform for Further Expansion. An inventory (spreadsheet) of technical and platform solutions for sharing sensitive data has been drafted. This includes refining the correct, relevant characteristics that need to be compared.

Further progress has been made for Deliverables due at the end of the project: For D5.11 ERAN Pilot, a bilateral pilot to connect Safe Rooms is being negotiated with GESIS and UKDA. Installation at UKDA should be possible in early 2021. Finally, the D5.12 Secure Data Facility Professionals Network has been refined to be a “network of networks”, based on country-specific networks (rather than a pan-European group) reflecting differing national legal regimes.

In addition, the work of task 5.4 has been presented at the SSHOC-DELAD webinar Sharing Datasets of Pathological Speech in October 2020⁶⁵.

2.5.1.5. TASK 5.5 ESS AS A SERVICE: A PILOT MAKING CROSS-NATIONAL SURVEY DATA FAIR

Task 5.5 is led and realized by ESS/NSD. In April 2020, the **programming phase** started with building the infrastructure elements data, the metadata repository and APIs. , The main progress made includes:

(1) **Tool development:** ESS/NSD is working in parallel on various components such as mapping of metadata components (towards standards and between tools), database structure and other infrastructure elements. The close collaboration with the above mentioned national NORDi project, which is also building a new data repository, ensures that we will bring ESS to the EOSC in a robust manner whilst FAIRifying it. The chosen solutions will be tailored to ESS needs while remaining as generic as possible. Progress has also been made in ensuring a DDI-CDI and DDI Lifecycle compliant (and sustainable) database.

⁶⁵ see Appendix - Tables of events, and Section 2.6 of this report on WP6 work

(2) **User testing for user interface and web:** Liaison started with the new ESS website team involving mainly ESS/NSD and ESS headquarters staff. Plans for testing of tools and platforms are being developed. External testers will be recruited from the broad base of ESS users.

The second half of 2020 was dedicated to building the cloud-based metadata (documentation) repository alongside the data repository. The metadata repository is being developed with Colectica in NSD’s cloud at MS Azure. The need for further development of Colectica’s system to ensure that the system will work for ESS and NSD has been defined, and it is standard based to enable predefined and searchable data extraction from the repository.

The next step will be to move the ESS metadata from ESS ERIC’s also Colectica-based Question and Variable database to the new metadata repository, and testing, as well as work with a user panel. When the system is in place (expected by April 2021), the data will be imported from the previous ESS rounds. The next development steps will be the APIs and the new landing pages, building on the metadata storage format, and setting up the data repository for ESS rounds 1-9.

In parallel, and in cooperation with GESIS, the development of a new data deposit tool has started. The new tool is built inside ESS’ new project management tool, **MyESS**, developed by GESIS. At the end of 2020, the work has arrived in its **final testing phase**. From this new channel, ESS round 10 data and metadata will land in the ESS archive’s **cloud-based ESS SSHOC data repository** as from summer 2021.

Figure 10. Screen Capture from MyESS, the ESS archive’s section

2.5.1.6. TASK 5.6 ISSUES IN PROVIDING OPEN DATA IN HERITAGE SCIENCE AND ARCHAEOLOGY

The first part of Task 5.6 was led and realized by the UK's Archaeology Data Service (UoY-ADS) addressed the heritage science and archaeology domain. The UoY-ADS has worked with E-RIHS and the broader heritage science and archaeological communities to **collect information** on the current information landscape, including the types of data and the challenges in making data FAIR across different European countries. This collaboration resulted in a **report on policy recommendations for heritage science**. The outcomes were presented in the SSHOC workshop Use and Re-use of Scientific Data in Archaeology and Heritage on 2 April 2020⁶⁶, which was jointly organised with WP6. This report and the SSHOC workshop focussed on heritage science more broadly, but future work in Task 5.6 will also prioritise archaeology.

Work has also begun on D5.15 Report on opening access to research data in the Heritage Science and Archaeology domain, which is an examination of the issues and challenges faced in **providing FAIR access to archaeological and archaeological science data**, and review of the solutions adopted across Europe. UoY have undertaken a full audit of FAIR compliance for their archaeological data as a baseline for further work. The team also ran a session on the ARIADNEplus portal for the EOSC/SSHOC/FREYA conference and the CLARIN/SSHOC vocabulary workshop, both held in November 2020.

The second part of this Task is led by the NG, and in 2020 work has been contributed by the NG and the CNR. NG has worked to ensure that the two data sources and the initial semantic mapping models, that will be the main focus of the task, are accessible and usable. The first data source used is the **Raphael Research Resource**⁶⁷. Progress has involved updating the administration systems, the graphical user interface of the original 2007 system, along with the SPARQL end-point for the data held within the resource⁶⁸, to ensure accessibility and respond to security concerns. The updating of the SPARQL end-point was carried out in collaboration with an AHRC funded project examining Linked Conservation Data⁶⁹. The second data source, a database of preparation layers⁷⁰, has not needed as much preparation, as it is actively being exploited as the output of the IPERION-CH⁷¹ (H2020) project and still being developed. The initial semantic mapping models, again outputs of the IPERION-CH (H2020) project, were initially only available as a prototype description⁷². Work has been carried out to convert and format them as re-usable and editable tab separated text files. Additional effort has been carried out to start creating an open web resource to visualise these initial semantic models, with the intention of encouraging discussions, within SSHOC, around their further development⁷³. The automatic modelling

⁶⁶ see Appendix - Tables of events and Section 2.6 of this report on WP6 work

⁶⁷ Website of Raphael Research Resource: <https://cima.ng-london.org.uk/documentation> [29.12.2020]

⁶⁸ Website of Linked Conservation Data Example: <https://rdf.ng-london.org.uk/workshops/lcd/>, with the source code available at: <https://github.com/jpadfield/bg-lcd-example> [29.12.2020]

⁶⁹ Website of Linked Conservation Data funded by AHRC: <https://www.ligatus.org.uk/lcd/> [29.12.2020]

⁷⁰ Portal of collaborative research resource of Iperion: <https://research.ng-london.org.uk/iperion/> [29.12.2020]

⁷¹ <http://www.iperionch.eu/> [19.07.2020]

⁷² IPERION-CH Deliverable D8.5: Completed example of prototype designs for integration of various types of documentation and analytical data generated for a single object: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5c8d1c525&appId=P_PGMS [29.12.2020]

⁷³ Website of Semantic mapping models: <https://rdf.ng-london.org.uk/modelling/>, with all of the source code available at <https://github.com/jpadfield/cidoc-crm.examples>. [29.12.2020]

process is being further simplified and a further dynamic version has been developed⁷⁴, to increase the accessibility of the work and to ensure that the methods used within the task can be as FAIR as the final datasets that will be created. All **development work is documented on GitHub**⁷⁵.

Work has also been continuing in relation to the development of the MOVIDA⁷⁶ software (CNR), including the further development of collaborations with other projects, such as IPERION-HS⁷⁷ (H2020). This work has concentrated on developing the FAIR nature of the Heritage Science data gathered during the examination of Heritage Objects. A key goal of this work is to increase interoperability and ensure that the data stored can be interoperable between different examination campaigns and between specialists working in different institutions. This work has focussed on the mapping of data stored within the MOVIDA software to the CIDOC CRM ontology⁷⁸. These existing activities will be directly integrated with and supported by the activities of the dedicated research fellow in 2021.

2.5.1.7. TASK 5.7 OPEN LINKED DATA. ARCHAEOLOGICAL CASE STUDY

Task 5.7 is led by DAI (Berlin) and conducted with the partner CNR (two Institutions of CNR: ITABC (Rome) and IBAM (Lecce), both now part of the CNR-ISPC Institute for Heritage Science).

The main result of Year 2 is the delivery of **D5.17 Implementation plan for the archaeological case study**⁷⁹ in June 2020. In the preparation for this deliverable, the task partners agreed to create a unified, cloud-based workflow for archaeological data from excavation and survey data to the 3D reconstruction of an archaeological site. A concept was designed for a workflow that will use tools being developed by the task partners, such as idai.field for excavation documentation (DAI) and the Extended Matrix for 3D reconstruction (CNR). The task partners also agreed to focus on documentation, norm data, data re-usability and reproducibility. For this, the case study will rely on systems for normative data such as gazetteers for place and time information, in particular the norm data systems of the idai.world.

As a **case study** the partners have chosen the virtual reconstruction of the Roman theatre in Catania. Its level of preservation will help testing early versions of the workflow and its different construction phases correspond to the focus on temporal data. In Addition, it will allow a comparison between an existing 3D reconstruction and a new reconstructive hypothesis using the Extended Matrix approach. D5.17 in addition already contains thoughts on the role of Linked Open Data and a sketch of a collaboration with task 5.2 (Hosting and sharing data repositories) and other tasks.

The task partners have also worked on **Milestone 36** (*Identification of a suitable archaeological case study and implementation of prototypes of the software module and the corresponding web service for that case study*) by investigating how FAIR principles can be applied to the planned workflow and how to include

⁷⁴ <https://github.com/jpadfield/dynamic-modelling> - developed in collaboration with <https://linked.art> [29.12.2020]

⁷⁵ <https://github.com/jpadfield/simple-modelling> [29.12.2020]

⁷⁶ MOVIDA is a tool for the data management and analysis of non-invasive investigations in the Cultural Heritage

⁷⁷ IPERION HS website: <http://www.iperionhs.eu/> [29.12.2020]

⁷⁸ CIDOC-CRM: CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/> [accessed 21.01.2021]

⁷⁹ Schmidle, Wolfgang and Sofia Pescarin, Emanuel Demetrescu, Bruno Fanini, Francesco Gabellone, Alberto Bucciero, ...Francesco Giuri. (2020). D5.17 Implementation plan for the archeological case study. Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3931705 [19.01.2021]

existing data management strategies in their respective institutions. The team has started to create a minimal version of the unified workflow that will be the output of task 5.7. The creation of the example workflow requires careful consideration on the topic of copyright, the preparation of the existing data for the Extended Matrix and the incorporation of the FAIR principles. One of the goals is an easy solution to add model licences to photographs and data in general, especially for heritage data.

Figure 11. 3D Model from laser scanner of the Roman theatre in Catania, virtual reconstruction chosen as the case study (IBAM Lecce)

2.5.2. Note on deviations from the plan and risk monitoring

Some of the WP5 deliverables were delayed in submission. D5.1 because of a delay in the processing of the SHARE biomarker data, caused by the necessity of additional validation tests as well as by practical obstacles in the application of the GDPR to these types of data. An additional delay in accelerometer data collection as a result of the COVID-19 outbreak prolonged the process. D5.9 Framework for Data Use Agreements was scheduled for June 2020 but its submission was postponed due to adjusted work schedules during Covid-19 for the most experienced partner on the topic.

D5.7 Report on the impact of the GDPR and its implications for EOSC has been drafted on time, but thorough revisions stretched into 2021. D5.19 Stakeholder workshop on SSH GDPR Code of Conduct has been postponed to February 2021 as the workshop intends to bring together researchers and findings from three projects that are all finalised until Dec 2020 only. These are the findings of D5.7, the BBMRI Code of conduct for health research and a report from the EU about the implementation of GDPR in specific countries. D5.8 Draft SSH GDPR Code of Conduct has been postponed due to the change of personnel, COVID-19 and postponement of Task 5.3 and the following workshop. All the postponed deliverables are expected to be submitted in 2021.

Some Milestones were also postponed due to the COVID-19 related issues, namely: Milestone 28 *Assessment of Existing Platforms* due in December 2020. In January 2021, a procedure for moving forward will be determined, with an interim deadline of March 2021 for the criteria. Milestone 31 *Setting up and populating a new ESS repository*, Milestone 32 *Developing API's* and Milestone 33 *Integrate data publishing with DataCite/DOI and bespoke advanced landing pages with rich functionalities* are highly interconnected and have been postponed to April 2021, May 2021 and September 2021 respectively. Milestone 36 *Identification of a suitable archaeological case study and implementation of prototypes of the software module and the corresponding web service for that case study* was due in October 2020 and is now postponed. While the first part (identification of the topic of the case study) is already completed, the second part (creating a minimal version of the unified workflow) needs more time for preparing the existing data for the Extended Matrix and incorporating the FAIR principles and clarifying copyright issues. No negative consequences are perceived.

Information on risk monitoring in WP5 for Year 2 is presented in the table below:

Table 8. Risk monitoring in WP5 - Year 2

Risks monitoring WP5				
<i>Risk (DoA)</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Mitigation measures applied?</i>	<i>Risk materialised so far?</i>	<i>Comments</i>
11	Understaffing of research infrastructures	Yes	Yes	Re-allocation of work in Task 5.1 in order to mitigate the risk
7	Technical difficulties of complex software development	Yes	No	Mitigation measure applied: hiring scientific developers, users involved in process via feedback webinars, adapting development plans (Task 5.5)

2.6. WP6 - Fostering Communities, Empowering Users, & Building Expertise

WP6 aims to broaden the SSHOC network of user communities and empower them to a greater level of expertise in utilizing the SSHOC services, tools, data throughout the research lifecycle and according to the FAIR Principles. WP6 is led by LIBER and participating organisations are CESSDA ERIC, CLARIN, DARIAH ERIC, KNAW, TRUST-IT (and its LTPs), CNRS, CNR, UCL.

During the second year of the project, WP6 moved from planning and setting strategic goals to the implementation of engagement and training activities, according to the two strategic documents in place, the KPIs set already in the Grant Agreement and taking into account the COVID-19 pandemic. It did so by maintaining collaboration with all WPs, aiming to address all stakeholders the project is targeting.

Greatly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, especially when it comes to delivery of face-to-face events, WP6 decided to put more effort in rescheduling and providing alternatives for fostering the SSHOC community engagement and training goals and needs in virtual environments during the pandemic. A level of flexibility was applied in formatting, taking as many elements as possible online. Virtual opportunities were created/identified. To support online events, effort and resources have been invested in identifying the appropriate tools that would provide a satisfying level of engagement and would be appropriate for training activities. At the same time, WP6 partners closely collaborated with WP2 in updating the website pages pertaining to training⁸⁰.

2.6.1. WP6 progress

2.6.1.1. TASK 6.1 MAPPING THE LANDSCAPE AND DEVELOPING STRATEGIES TO FOSTER COMMUNITIES & BUILD EXPERTISE

Task 6.1 is led by LIBER, and partners participating in it were TRUST-IT (and its LTPs), DARIAH/OEAW, CESSDA/ADP, CLARIN/UL-FF. Although T6.1 formally ended in M12, WP6 continues to monitor changes and developments in the landscape, while regularly checking the progress on the KPIs identified in **D6.1 Community Engagement Strategy⁸¹** and **D6.2 Building Expertise Strategy⁸²** through the monitoring of activities of the other WP6 tasks.

2.6.1.2. TASK 6.2 FOSTERING COMMUNITIES: ENGAGING NEW & EXISTING USERS

Task 6.2 is led by CESSDA/UL-ADP, with LIBER, TRUST-IT, CESSDA/GESIS, and CLARIN/UL-FF as participating partners. In the second year of the project, T6.2 kept regular communication with other WP and task leads to monitor the progress of SSHOC services development, to respond to the needs of the

⁸⁰ SSHOC Training page: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/training> [21.01.2021]

⁸¹ Torma, Martina and Kalaitzi, Vasso, Vipavc Brvar, Irena, Fišer, Darja, Pahor de Maiti, Kristina, Petitfils, Clara, ... Willems, Marieke. (2019). SSHOC D6.1 Community Engagement Strategy (Version v1.0). Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3592243

⁸² Torma, Martina and Vasso Kalaitzi, Elly Dijk, Marion Wittenberg, Marieke Willems, Darja Fiser, ... Irena Vipavc Brvar. (2019). SSHOC D6.2 Building Expertise Strategy (Version v1.0). Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3595995

stakeholders and to explore ways of community engagement, but also with WP2 on maximizing the impact of awareness raising activities. To leverage connections, communication and participation of relevant stakeholders, regularly identify third-party events, where SSHOC workshops could potentially take place.

In March 2020, **Milestone 39** was achieved - **Launch of the Expertise Strategy**, thus initiating planning for the midterm Stakeholder Forum, originally planned to take place during the ESOF event in July 2020 in Trieste, Italy. Due to the implications of the COVID-19 pandemic, T6.2 and WP2 instead organised a joint online event in collaboration with projects FREYA⁸³ and EOSC-hub⁸⁴, which is meant to be one of the Stakeholder Series events of the project. The conference, titled **REALISING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD**, took place in November 2020. The event brought together almost **700 visitors to 30 sessions** and **30 virtual exhibition booths**, with the goal to address all SSHOC stakeholders. Reaching all SSHOC stakeholders until the end of the project is the task's priority.

Figure 12. The virtual entrance to the joint event **REALISING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD**

Further to this event, planning of awareness raising events and stakeholder series events has started in the requested period, by collecting relevant input from other WPs.

⁸³ FREYA project: <https://www.project-freya.eu/en/about/mission> [21.02.2021]

⁸⁴ EOSC hub project: <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/> [21.02.2021]

Several awareness raising activities took place in 2020, resulting from a collaboration between WP6/T6.2 and SSHOC WPs and partners, as well as Stakeholder Series events:

- SSHOC Webinar: Discussion meeting about requirements of CESSDA Service Providers for a Dataverse repository⁸⁵
- SSHOC Webinar: How to improve the quality of your repository? SSHOC and certification of repositories⁸⁶
- SSHOC Workshop: Agile development of the SSH Open Marketplace: User Workshop⁸⁷
- SSHOC Webinar: SSH Open Marketplace: Public Consultation for the DARIAH Community⁸⁸
- SSHOC webinar series: Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms:
 - SSHOC Online Information Sessions: Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms - First session: Wikibase⁸⁹
 - SSHOC Online Information Sessions: Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms - Second session – SKOSMOS⁹⁰
 - SSHOC Online Information Sessions: Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms - Third session - CESSDA Vocabulary Service⁹¹
- SSHOC webinar: DARIAH Community Requirements for a Dataverse Repository⁹²

⁸⁵ SSHOC Webinar: Discussion meeting about requirements of CESSDA Service Providers for a Dataverse repository: <https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-cessda-service-providers-dataverse> [accessed 21.01.2021]

⁸⁶ SSHOC Webinar: How to improve the quality of your repository? SSHOC and certification of repositories: <https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-repositories-quality-certification> [accessed 21.01.2021]

⁸⁷ SSHOC Workshop: Agile development of the SSH Open Marketplace: <https://sshopencloud.eu/agile-development-ssh-open-marketplace-user-workshop> (Virtual workshop during the ICTeSSH 2020 conference) [accessed 21.01.2021]

⁸⁸ Barbot, Laure, Fischer, Frank, Larrousse, Nicolas, Petitfils, Clara, Illmayer, Klaus, & Buddenbohm, Stefan. (2020, July). SSH Open Marketplace: Public Consultation for the DARIAH Community (Version v1.0). Zenodo. DOI [10.5281/zenodo.3935345](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3935345) [21.02.2021]; SSH Open Marketplace: Notes from our Public Consultation with DARIAH: <https://sshopencloud.eu/news/ssh-open-marketplace-notes-our-public-consultation-dariah> [accessed 21.01.2021]

⁸⁹ SSHOC Online Information Sessions: Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms - 1st session: Wikibase: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-online-information-sessions-open-source-vocabulary-hosting-and-management-platforms-first> [accessed 21.01.2021]

⁹⁰ SSHOC Online Information Sessions: Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms - 2nd session – SKOSMOS: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-online-information-sessions-open-source-vocabulary-hosting-and-management-platforms-second> [accessed 21.01.2021]

⁹¹ SSHOC Online Information Sessions: Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms - 3rd session - CESSDA Vocabulary Service: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-online-information-sessions-open-source-vocabulary-hosting-and-management-platforms-third> [accessed 21.01.2021]

⁹² SSHOC Webinar - DARIAH Community Requirements for a Dataverse Repository: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-dariah-community-requirements-dataverse-repository> [28.09.2020]; Marion Wittenberg, & Péter Király. (2020, September). Requirements of DARIAH community for a Dataverse repository (Version v1.0). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4054847> [accessed 21.01.2021]

- Building trustworthy repositories: Introduction to CoreTrustSeal certification⁹³
- SSHOC Workshop: Considerations for the Vocabulary Platforms⁹⁴
- REALISING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD Conference.

2.6.1.3. TASK 6.3 EMPOWERING USERS: TRAINING MATERIALS AND ONLINE LEARNING PATHS

The development of the training inventory was used as the basis for the Training Discovery Toolkit. During the second year of the project, further customisation of the data model and the used controlled vocabularies took place, as well as changes to the layout and structure of the application.

Exchange and planning took place in collaboration with WP7 on the relation between Training Inventory and in fact all training-related resources in SSHOC and the SSH Open Marketplace. Task 6.3 planned the alignment of data models, especially under consideration of the many international initiatives developing metadata schemas for training materials.

The **Training Resource Catalogue Interoperability Workshop**⁹⁵ brought together representatives from more than 10 international initiatives proved as an extraordinarily useful platform to learn about related activities and exchange about plans and strategies.

Given that in the long-term the SSH Open Marketplace should become the main catalogue of SSH related resources, especially for training materials, strategies are being developed to ensure the flow of information about these resources into the Marketplace. While the information about training events and materials in SSHOC is presented on the SSHOC website under the respective page, the resources themselves are being deposited in the Zenodo SSHOC community, and on the dedicated YouTube channel. Further work is taking place on metadata requirements, which will have to be provided either from the SSHOC Website, or in the post-harvesting curation process on the side of the SSH Open Marketplace. First harmonisation iteration is already being performed in the training-toolkit application mapping the heterogeneous keywords to a list of curated topics.

⁹³ Tomasz Parkoła, René van Horik, Birger Jerlehag, & Daan Broeder. (2020, November 3). Building Trustworthy Repositories: Introduction to CoreTrustSeal Certification. Presented at the Scholarly Primitives - DARIAH Annual Event 2020, Zagreb, Croatia: Zenodo. DOI [10.5281/zenodo.4233299](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4233299) [21.01.2021]

⁹⁴ SSHOC Considerations for the Vocabulary Platforms: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-considerations-vocabulary-platforms> [21.01.2021]; Takeaways from the SSHOC Webinar Series on Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms: <https://sshopencloud.eu/news/takeaways-sshoc-webinar-series-open-source-vocabulary-hosting-and-management-platforms> [21.01.2021]

⁹⁵ Training Resource Catalogue Interoperability Workshop, <https://www.fairsfair.eu/events/training-resource-catalogue-interoperability-workshop> [21.01.2021]

2.6.1.4. TASK 6.4 BUILDING EXPERTISE: THE SSHOC TRAINING NETWORK

Task 6.4 is led by KNAW(DANS) and partners participating were LIBER, CESSDA/GESIS, CESSDA/UKDA, UCL and CLARIN/UL-FF. In the second year of SSHOC **Milestone 40 - SSHOC Training Toolkit (preliminary version)** was achieved and **Deliverable 6.9 - SSHOC Trainer Toolkit (draft)** was submitted⁹⁶, branded as **SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit**⁹⁷.

Partners also further developed and fostered the **SSHOC training community** as a network for collaboration and exchange and **Deliverable 6.10 Report on the SSHOC Training Community** was submitted⁹⁸. Further work in the second year of the project included the planning and organisation of train-the-trainer bootcamps and brainstorm sessions with the SSHOC Training Community towards setting the requirements and developing the **SSHOC trainer directory**, a registry for finding trainers in the social sciences and humanities

The **Training Discovery Toolkit** was released in April 2020 and is meant as a discovery tool for learning and training materials that trainers in the Social Sciences and Humanities can use to develop and improve their own training activities. It contains more than **70 items** from **41 different sources** on a range of topics including Research Data Management, Open Science and didactics. Since the release of the initial version of the Toolkit, T6.4 has been working on the second iteration.

The Toolkit has been presented to the SSHOC Training Community and during bootcamps to collect feedback for the next iteration, re: additional materials and changes to increase the usability, sustainability and relevance of the toolkit. Importantly, the team closely monitors related activities on training catalogues, standardization of metadata, sustainability and interoperability aspects, and aims to integrate the next iteration of the SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit as much as possible. For this reason, T6.4 partners have been participating in the RDA focus groups on minimal and extended metadata for FAIR learning resources (e.g. RDA IG Education and Training on Handling Research Data⁹⁹) and the Training Resource Catalogue Interoperability workshop organised by the EOSC-5B Projects Training and Skills Task Force and FAIRSFAR. Furthermore, discussion with other work packages within the SSHOC project have been initiated about the integration of the Toolkit into the SSHOC marketplace and what harmonisation would be required.

⁹⁶ Braukmann Ricarda, and Leenarts Ellen. (2020). SSHOC D6.9 SSHOC Trainer Toolkit (draft) (Version v1.0). Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3824754

⁹⁷ Training Discovery Toolkit: <https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/> [10.02.2021]

⁹⁸ Ricarda Braukmann, and Ellen Leenarts. (2020). SSHOC D6.10 Report on the SSHOC Training Community (Version v1.0). Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3875985

⁹⁹ Education and Training on Handling Research Data, <https://rd-alliance.org/groups/education-and-training-handling-research-data.html> [10.02.2021]

SSHOC SSH Training Discovery Toolkit

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Search for sources and items

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Source

ID	Title	Description	Curated topics
232	Alison	Alison is one of the world's largest free learning platforms for education and skills training.	Didactics
43	CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide	The Data Management Expert Guide is designed by European experts from the CESSDA Training Working Group to help social science researchers m	Didactics , Research data management/FAIR data
230	CLARIN Depositing Services	One of the fundamental services of the CLARIN infrastructure is making sure that language resources can be archived and made available to the community in a reliable manner.	Open Science , Research data management/FAIR data , Text encoding and TEI
46	CLARIN Knowledge Sharing	The aim of the CLARIN Knowledge Sharing Initiative is to ensure ensure that the available knowledge and expertise provided by CLARIN consortia does not exist as a fragmented collection of unconnect	Data visualization , Open Science , Quantitative analysis , Research data management/FAIR data , Text encoding and TEI

Entity type

Item (73)

Source (39)

Collections

Training Discovery Toolkit (5)

Training Toolkit (112)

Intended audience

Data steward (74)

Trainer (60)

Researcher (57)

Data creator (52)

Data provider (50)

Service provider (31)

Student (27)

Figure 13. SSH Training Discovery Toolkit main page; Screen Capture

The trainer community has grown a lot since its launch in 2019 and as of November 2020 includes **157 members**. From March onwards, T6.4 has organized 9 monthly online meetings for the Training Community which covered various topics, such as Toolkit sneak-peak, Improving Online Meetings, Presentations and Workshops, Online and offline games and Open Science. The Community members were invited to share their experiences with each other. A dedicated space has been provided by the project to serve the Training Community. T6.4 was also involved in co-organising a community building session at the Realising the EOSC event on 18 June 2020, where the SSHOC Training Community was presented as an example of community building activities across EOSC projects.

One bootcamp¹⁰⁰ took place during the LIBER online conference on 23 June 2020. It was organized by SSHOC partners CLARIN, LIBER and DANS and focused on librarians as a target audience. To showcase the SSHOC training toolkit to the Training Community, T6.4 organized an online mini bootcamp¹⁰¹ on 2 June 2020. The goal of the bootcamp was to present the community with the Toolkit and its functionality to find training materials as well as to gather feedback on the Toolkit for a next iteration. The team started planning an RDM train-the-trainer bootcamp together with DARIAH to be held in the Love Data Week in February 2021.

¹⁰⁰ LIBER bootcamp blog post:

<https://sshopencloud.eu/news/boost-research-librarians-sshoc-train-trainer-bootcamp> [21.01.2021]

¹⁰¹ Mini bootcamp blog post: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/first-sshoc-training-community-mini-bootcamp> [21.01.2021]

Do you wish to join the **SSH Training Community**?

“Engage with other SSH trainers, get a sneak preview of new training materials, such as our train-the-trainer toolkit, and volunteer to host one of our workshops.”

Do you wish to join the SSH Training Community?

Yes, count me in!

Gmail Address

Please fill this field to allow us to give you access to the Training Community Shared Google Drive

Please indicate your areas of interest/preferred resources

- Joining a Workshop
- Hosting a Workshop
- Factsheets
- Case Studies
- Videos

Figure 14. Training Community registration page at SSHOC website; Screen Capture

2.6.1.5. TASK 6.5 COORDINATING TARGETED TRAINING IN THE SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES

Task 6.5 is led by CLARIN/UL-FF, while partners participating in this period were LIBER, CESSDA/ADP, CLARIN ERIC, DARIAH ERIC, CNRS(Huma-Num), and UCL. It is responsible for the organization of 12 training events equally divided between content-related workshops and webinars on targeted training topics: Data Protection and the GDPR, Data Stewardship and RDM in theory and practice, Data Citation principles and practice, Data Science for the Social Science and Humanities, Data Science for Heritage Science, and Text Mining for the Social Sciences and Digital Humanities. The input from T6.5 partners – having an excellent overview of their field, the needs of the specific research community and access to professional individuals – ensures that SSHOC activities fill the gap in knowledge and skills transfer and thus help researchers pursue their scientific objectives in line with Open Science principles.

In order to find the balance between providing relevant and attractive events for the scientific community on one side, and promoting the output of SSHOC WPs on the other, T6.5 team has put special emphasis on informal discussions with SSHOC task leaders, while encouraging the formation of mixed groups of presenters that bring together SSHOC members and outside experts. The rationale behind this approach was to also use the professional network of presenters outside SSHOC in order to bring SSHOC to the doorstep of researchers not necessarily acquainted with the project. In doing so, the T6.5 events helped raise awareness about SSHOC's objectives among the audience and served to transfer high-quality content to targeted communities. In the preparation of the events, close collaboration also took place with external initiatives and networks such as the DARIAH-ELDAH group¹⁰²,

¹⁰² DARIAH-ELDAH group:

<https://www.dariah.eu/activities/working-groups/ethics-and-legality-in-the-digital-arts-and-humanities-eldah/>
[21.01.2021]

DELAD initiative¹⁰³, the ETHMIGSURVEYDATA Cost Action¹⁰⁴, the Oral History & Technology research group and the SEADDA Cost Action¹⁰⁵.

In sum, in 2020, the T6.5 team has organized 8 events:

1. Data Science for the Social Science and Humanities targeted training webinar **“CLARIN Hands-on Tutorial on Transcribing Interview Data”**¹⁰⁶
2. Data Stewardship and RDM in theory and practice targeted training workshop **“Caring for Sharing - Data Management and FAIRness of Migration Data”**¹⁰⁷
3. Data Science for Heritage Science targeted training webinar **“Use and Re-use of Scientific Data in Archaeology and Heritage”**¹⁰⁸
4. Text Mining for the Social Sciences and Digital Humanities additional targeted training webinar **“Quanlify with Ease: Combining quantitative and qualitative corpus analysis”**¹⁰⁹
5. Data Stewardship and RDM in theory and practice targeted training webinar **“Tools and resources for FAIR data”**¹¹⁰
6. Data Protection and the GDPR: Targeted training webinar **“Putting Data Protection into Practice: GDPR and the DARIAH ELDAH Consent Form Wizard”**¹¹¹

¹⁰³ DELAD Initiative: <https://delad.ruhosting.nl/wordpress/> [accessed 21.01.2021]

¹⁰⁴ ETHMIGSURVEYDATA Cost Action: <https://ethmigsurveydatahub.eu/> [accessed 21.01.2021]

¹⁰⁵ SEADDA cost Action: <https://www.seadda.eu/> [accessed 10.01.2021]

¹⁰⁶ Data Science for the Social Science and Humanities targeted training webinar “CLARIN Hands-on Tutorial on Transcribing Interview Data” <https://sshopencloud.eu/hands-on-tutorial-transcribing-interview-data> [03.03.2020]; SSHOC Webinar: CLARIN Hands-on Tutorial on Transcribing Interview Data, <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-webinar-clarin-hands-tutorial-transcribing-interview-data> [14.04.2020]

¹⁰⁷ Data Stewardship and RDM in theory and practice targeted training workshop “Caring for Sharing - Data Management and FAIRness of Migration Data” <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-workshop-caring-sharing-%E2%80%93-data-management-and-fairness-migration-data> [03.03.2020]; Caring for Sharing: SSHOC Workshop on Data Management and FAIRness of Migration Data, <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/caring-sharing-workshop-data-mgmt-and-fairness-migration-data> [06.05.2020]

¹⁰⁸ Data Science for Heritage Science targeted training webinar “Use and Re-use of Scientific Data in Archaeology and Heritage” <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/use-and-re-use-scientific-data-archaeology-and-heritage> [02.04.2020]; Use and Re-use of Scientific Data in Archaeology and Heritage, <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-webinar-use-and-re-use-scientific-data-archaeology-and-heritage> [03.06.2020]

¹⁰⁹ Text Mining for the Social Sciences and Digital Humanities additional targeted training webinar “Quanlify with Ease: Combining quantitative and qualitative corpus analysis” <https://sshopencloud.eu/3rd-sshoc-webinar-quanlify-combining-quantitative-qualitative-corpus-analysis> [16.04.2020]; Quanlify with Ease: Combining Quantitative and Qualitative Corpus Analysis SSHOC Webinar Notes, <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/quanlify-ease-combining-quantitative-and-qualitative-corpus-analysis-sshoc-webinar-notes> [01.07.2020]

¹¹⁰ Data Stewardship and RDM in theory and practice targeted training webinar “Tools and resources for FAIR data” <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-emmm-survey-data-fair> [18.05.2020]; Tools and Resources for FAIR Data, <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/tools-and-resources-fair-data-sshoc-webinar-notes> [01.07.2020]

¹¹¹ Data Protection and the GDPR: Targeted training webinar “Putting Data Protection into Practice: GDPR and the DARIAH ELDAH Consent Form Wizard” <https://sshopencloud.eu/putting-data-protection-practice-gdpr-and-dariah-eldah-consent-form-wizard-0> [13.10.2020]; Putting Data Protection into Practice: GDPR and the DARIAH ELDAH Consent Form Wizard, <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/webinar-notes-gdpr-and-dariah-eldah-consent-form-wizard> [20.11.2020]

7. Data Science for the Social Science and Humanities additional targeted training webinar “**Sharing Datasets of Pathological Speech**”¹¹²
8. Data Stewardship and RDM in theory and practice additional targeted training webinar “**Introducing the newly launched EMM Survey Registry**”¹¹³

After each event, the T6.5 team prepares a blogpost with the main highlights from the event, and a report to be included in the respective deliverable. Presentation slides are uploaded to the SSHOC Zenodo channel, and the webinar recordings to the SSHOC YouTube channel.

The positive feedback from the participants as well as high attendance show that the events are addressing timely topics and that speakers and venues were chosen appropriately. Despite a proliferation of online events due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the team observes that the webinars were very well attended by **live viewers (100+)** and that the webinar recordings at SSHOC YouTube channel exhibit a constantly growing number of views. Ad hoc Q&A sessions which had a fixed one-hour time slot allocated for four consecutive weeks, were provided as an informal, tailor-made online help room dedicated to users seeking help and additional information about the tools showcased in the webinar.

2.6.2. Note on deviations from the plan and risk monitoring

The main deviations of WP6 are related to face-to-face events. A number of planned face-to-face activities had to be cancelled, postponed or moved online due to the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak. WP6, in agreement with the project coordination and the rest of the consortium, made the decision to put more effort in still fostering the SSHOC community, and engaging and training the SSHOC stakeholders, instead of cancelling all planned face-to-face activities indefinitely.

WP6 aspires also to deliver face-to-face activities, even with some deviation in terms of number of events, format and length overall than initially planned, as soon as the global health situation allows it. WP6 partners are closely monitoring the situation and adapting accordingly. Significant effort was spent in mitigation planning, testing of online tools and working on online formats, to support the engagement and training needs of the SSHOC community.

T6.2 had to repurpose its stakeholder forum activities and awareness raising workshops and webinars due to the pandemic, by also initiating its Stakeholder Series events, which resulted in postponing *Deliverable 6.5 - Report on Stakeholder Forum*. T6.4 worked more intensely on Training community calls and online Bootcamps, while T6.5 focused more on the webinars, planning most of the undelivered workshops in the coming period.

¹¹² Data Science for the Social Science and Humanities additional targeted training webinar “Sharing Datasets of Pathological Speech” <https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-sharing-datasets-pathological-speech> [14.10.2020]; Webinar notes: Sharing Datasets of Pathological Speech, <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/webinar-notes-sharing-datasets-pathological-speech> [20.11.2020]

¹¹³ Data Stewardship and RDM in theory and practice additional targeted training webinar “Introducing the newly launched EMM Survey Registry” <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-introducing-newly-launched-ethnic-and-migrant-minorities-emm-survey-registry> [26.10.2020]; Webinar notes: Introducing the newly launched EMM Survey Registry, <https://sshopencloud.eu/news/webinar-notes-introducing-newly-launched-emm-survey-registry> [09.11.2020]

Information on risk monitoring in WP6 for Year 2 is presented in the table below:

Table 9. Risk monitoring in WP6 - Year 2

Risks monitoring WP6				
<i>Risk (DoA)</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Mitigation measures applied?</i>	<i>Risk materialised so far?</i>	<i>Comments</i>
3	Lack of engagement at outreach events	Yes	No	All tasks that perform events (T6.2, T6.4 and T6.5) prevented this risk by early and intensive promotion. Especially for T6.5, by respecting at least a month-long promotion period, T6.5 managed to secure 100+ participants at most of the online events and fully booked face-to-face events. In the case of T6.2, an extra action taken for the Stakeholder event "Realising the EOSC" was collaborating with two other projects and taking advantage of shared communication.
10	Low acceptance or understanding of the new data access tools, guidelines and services by users and public	Yes	No	T6.5 organizes training events that showcase useful tools, especially those developed in the SSHOC framework, in order to facilitate the adoption of these tools by researchers. Furthermore, T6.5 organized Q&A sessions dedicated to specific tools, but despite heavy promotion, this opportunity has not been heavily exploited by researchers.
14	Delay in development of SSHOC services might affect training schedule	Yes	Yes	Continuous communication is held by T6.5 with all WPs in order to promote as many SSHOC resources as possible. If additional resources are developed even after a targeted training has been delivered, T6.5 makes efforts to organize additional events in order to support the dissemination and active use of the services developed in SSHOC.
U7	No delivery or reformatting/adjusting of face-to-face activities due to COVID-19	Yes	Yes	Monitoring the global health situation closely, in agreement with WP1 and overall the project scheduling activities online, reformatting them or postponing where feasible, in order to achieve the goals set in DoA.

2.7. WP7 - Creating the SSH Open Marketplace

WP7 goal is to create the SSH Open Marketplace, a discovery portal which pools and contextualises resources for Social Sciences and Humanities research communities: tools, services, training materials, datasets and workflows.

After a first year dedicated to the identification of user requirements, design of the system specification, prioritisation of data sources and first implementations, in 2020, WP7 partners focused on two important milestones: MS42 “Marketplace - alpha release” in June 2020 and MS43 “Marketplace - beta release” in December 2020. The alpha release showcased a manually curated set of data and was accessible to testers only. The beta version of the SSH Open Marketplace, improved based on testers’ feedback and publicly available, aggregates ~5,000 individual items, of which a subset has been enriched.

Over the course of 2020, all WP7 tasks delivered necessary activities to ensure the success of these two milestones, and the result of this work is accessible via: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/>. Following an agile methodology and based on users’ consultation and feedback loops (T7.1), several iterations of the website were developed and implemented (T7.2) in 2020. In the meantime, T7.3 investigated the best sources and ingestion pipelines for data population and T7.4 prepared two deliverables and started to design the curation workflows.

Figure 15. Timeline for the SSH Open Marketplace as implemented by WP7

2.7.1. WP7 progress

2.7.1.1. TASK 7.1 USER REQUIREMENTS, CONCEPTUAL MODEL AND SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF THE SSH OPEN MARKETPLACE

The task is led by DARIAH/UGOE while the partnering institutions were CESSDA ERIC, DARIAH ERIC, CNRS (Huma-Num), DARIAH/PSNC, DARIAH/OEAW, SWC, CNR, and FORTH. It formally terminated with achievement of MS42 in June 2020, however, as all partners are involved in other tasks as well, a community involvement task force, in collaboration with WP2 and WP6, has continued the work on dissemination and participatory design up to the Beta and to the Final Release of the SSH Open Marketplace.

Following the initial *D7.1 System Specification for the SSH Open Marketplace* (submitted in 2019) Task 7.1 worked, in 2020, to regularly **refine the system specifications**, taking specific topics into account, such

as governance, curation or user management. Moreover, task 7.1 focused on two main lines of activity to support the development process and the uptake of the service:

- Community and stakeholder feedback loop as part of the participatory design: support the other tasks, e.g. by filtering back comments from testers and reviewers into the development process.
- Facilitate the uptake and awareness of the service within its potential user and stakeholder community: in contrast to the feedback for the development of the service, the uptake and awareness activities take a more strategic perspective and look at the future use of the service and the embedment of it within the general EOSC context.

The main instruments and methods used by T7.1 to contribute to MS42 and MS43 have been the participation or creation of events and, in collaboration with WP2, the publication of news items and the creation of the **Public Consultation Platform (PCP)** as an instrument to collect feedback in a structured way apart from events.

Visibility within selected communities was achieved thanks to the coordination or **contributions to events**:

- FAIR research data management in SSH workshop¹¹⁴ (DARIAH/UGOE: the 30th of January 2020, together with CO-OPERAS in Göttingen);
- Agile development of the SSH Open Marketplace: Alignment with user requirements¹¹⁵ (ICTeSSH, the 30th of June 2020, coordinated by WP2);
- SSH Open Marketplace: Public Consultation for the DARIAH Community¹¹⁶ (the 3d of July 2020);
- Who needs tool directories? A forum on sustaining discovery portals large and small¹¹⁷ (forum opened during the DH2020 Conference, 20-25 July 2020);
- poster at the German Open Access Tage 2020¹¹⁸ (15-17 September 2020);
- The SSH Open Marketplace: it's relevance for the CLARIN communities and CLARIN services¹¹⁹ (stall at the CLARIN Conference Bazaar, the 7th of October 2020);
- EOSC Co-Creation: Anticipating the future of research in the social sciences and humanities¹²⁰ (contribution in a workshop, OPERAS Conference, the 2nd of November 2020);
- DARIAH Public Demonstration of the SSH Open Marketplace¹²¹ (the 13th of November 2020, DARIAH Annual Event);

¹¹⁴ FAIR research data management in SSH workshop:

<https://www.sshopencloud.eu/fair-research-data-management-ssh-co-operas-sshoc-workshop> [21.01.2021]

¹¹⁵ See Appendix - Tables of events, and Section 2.6 of this report on WP6 work

¹¹⁶ See Appendix - Tables of events, and Section 2.6 of this report on WP6 work

¹¹⁷ DH2020 Conference Forum: <https://dh2020directoriesforum.hcommons.org/> [21.01.2021]

¹¹⁸ Poster at German Open Access Tage 2020: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4009120> [21.01.2021]

¹¹⁹ Bazaar CLARIN Conference: <https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-bazaar-2020> [21.01.2021]

¹²⁰ Workshop OPERAS Conference: <https://www.operas2020.com/speakers-workshops> [21.01.2021]

¹²¹ Demo DARIAH Annual Event: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4290536> [21.01.2021]

- Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud¹²² (16th of November 2020, Realising the EOSC event);
- Exploring the SSH data landscape: thematic discovery portals in the EOSC¹²³ (17th of November 2020, Realising the EOSC event);
- Cracking digital archival research and metadata: Archives Portal Europe¹²⁴ (18th of November 2020, DARIAH Annual Event);
- Challenges in Sustainability of FAIR Research Data and Services for SSH and Beyond¹²⁵ (19th of November 2020, Realising the EOSC event).

The community involvement task force worked, in collaboration with WP2, to open a Public Consultation Platform on the SSHOC website, in order to collect users' feedback on the alpha version of the Marketplace, between July and December 2020. Results of the consultation were channeled back into the development process.

Task 7.1, collaborating with WP2, achieved considerable success with regard to the general visibility of the SSH Open Marketplace. For instance, DARIAH/UGOE led the creation of an **explainity clip published at YouTube**¹²⁶ gained more than **7k views within a few weeks**.

2.7.1.2. TASK 7.2 DEVELOPMENT OF THE MARKETPLACE APPLICATION

Task 7.2 is led by DARIAH/OEAW. Partners contributing were DARIAH ERIC, DARIAH/PSNC, CNRS (Huma-Num), DARIAH/UGOE, TRUST-IT (and its LTPs), and SWC. Based on the system specification and the MVP - minimum viable product -, deployed in December 2019, the team continued to work in multiple short iteration cycles on the implementation of the main application, with clear separation into the backend or the server-side application and frontend or client component with the REST-API¹²⁷ serving as a contract and sole mode of interaction between these. The development was accompanied by two further iterations of the UI-design informed by input from first test users. Agreeing on a traditional development path with well-established technologies, the server component is a Java-Spring application, the client application is being implemented in JavaScript using the React framework¹²⁸. The code base is maintained collaboratively in git repositories¹²⁹ hosted by one of the partners, DARIAH/UGOE.

¹²² Realising the European Open Science Cloud - Thematic Discovery Marketplaces panel: <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/realising-european-open-science-cloud/thematic-discovery-marketplaces-european-open-science-cloud> [21.01.2021]

¹²³ Realising the European Open Science Cloud - Exploring the SSH data landscape: <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/realising-european-open-science-cloud/thematic-discovery-portals-eosc-exploring-ssh-data-landscape> [21.01.2021]

¹²⁴ Cracking the archives: <https://dariah-ae-2020.sciencesconf.org/308507> [21.01.2021]

¹²⁵ Realising the European Open Science Cloud - Challenges in Sustainability: <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/realising-european-open-science-cloud/challenges-sustainability-fair-research-data-and-services-ssh-and-beyond> [21.01.2021]

¹²⁶ SSHOpen Marketplace explainity clip: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4tyZ4vhrM9s> [20.01.2021]

¹²⁷ Web service API (application programming interface) that adheres to the REST (representational state transfer) architectural constraints.

¹²⁸ React is a JavaScript library for building user interfaces.

¹²⁹ Gitlab instance of the SSH Open Marketplace: <https://gitlab.gwdg.de/sshoc> [20.07.2020]

In parallel to the development of the application, a number of data sources has been ingested based on the prioritised list of potential data sources. Though this was mainly a T7.3 task, a close collaboration between T7.2 and T7.3 was required to ensure multilateral alignment between the data model, its implementation in the database and in the API, its usage in the manually devised mappings for individual sources as well as in the ingestion pipelines implementing those mappings. All this, while each of these involved parties/components was a potential source of need for change in the data model, yielding its continuous evolution in numerous iterations.

Figure 16. Screen Capture of the SSH Open Marketplace homepage - beta release

Mappings have been defined from the data model for each of the sources to the data model of the SSH Open Marketplace, based on which a transformation pipeline was implemented using the ETL-framework Unified Views¹³⁰, part of the semantic suite PoolParty¹³¹ provided by one of the partners, SWC. The pipeline reads the data from the sources, extracts the data, potentially normalizes, converts or

¹³⁰ Unified Views (<https://unifiedviews.eu/>) is an open source Extract-Transform-Load (ETL) framework that allows users to define, execute, monitor, debug, schedule, and share Resource Description Framework (RDF) data processing tasks.

¹³¹ Semantic technology platform: <https://www.poolparty.biz/> [20.07.2020]

enriches them, generates the MP-compatible data structure and pushes the converted data against the API of the Marketplace. The pipelines can be run regularly, allowing continuous updates from the source. Indeed they were run a number of times in the process of fine-tuning the mappings. All ingest of data is only possible via the API, ensuring consistency with respect to the data model. Both milestones - alpha and beta releases - brought a richer set of functionality, more mature API, adaptations to layout based on users input and growing set of data. Implemented features were full-text search, faceted search, detail view, relations between items, workflows.

2.7.1.3. TASK 7.3 MARKETPLACE INTEROPERABILITY

Task 7.3 is led by CLARIN ERIC, with partners DARIAH/PSNC, CNRS (Huma-Num), DARIAH/OEAW, DARIAH/UGOE, SWC, CLARIN/Athena, and CNR. After creating a structured overview of relevant sources of information which could be imported into the SSH Open Marketplace, in this phase work has become more concretely tied to the Marketplace. First, the list was prioritized to create an order of sources in which they will be successfully integrated into the Marketplace import workflow, then over the course of the year a number of sources have been integrated and are now available in the beta release of the marketplace that was launched at the end of 2020. For each of the sources, the following steps were taken:

1. T7.3 team looked at the metadata that could be harvested, e.g. the output from an API call, and created a mapping for each harvested metadata field to the marketplace data model, creating new properties and extending controlled vocabularies where necessary. Certain sources, like the EOSC portal marketplace, have also been analysed further in direct communication with the people responsible in the EOSC-hub project.
2. A test import was done, which was then checked and the mapping adapted where it didn't work out yet.
3. The mapping was finalized and the source was added to the list of harvestable sources.

Besides that, experiments for direct extraction of tools from publications started.

The actions described above lead to the following results: A **long list of information sources**, a short list of **prioritized information sources**, including relevant technical details and findings on what constitutes a reasonable granularity and quality level; a number of mapping descriptions for all the sources that are currently available in the marketplace and for some of the ones that will be integrated next; and an **issue board with an up-to-date overview of the inclusion of the shortlisted sources**. The current beta release of the marketplace contains information from the following sources: TAPoR¹³², the Programming Historian¹³³, the EOSC Portal¹³⁴, SSK Workflows¹³⁵ and Resources¹³⁶, the Language Resource

¹³² TAPoR website: <http://tapor.ca/home> [22.01.2021]

¹³³ The Programming Historian website: <https://programminghistorian.org/> [22.01.2021]

¹³⁴ EOSC catalogue and marketplace: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/> [22.01.2021]

¹³⁵ Standardization Survival Kit: <http://ssk.huma-num.fr/#/> [22.01.2021]

¹³⁶ Standardization Survival Kit Zotero library: <https://www.zotero.org/groups/427927/ssk-parthenos/collections/ZIVPVK66> [22.01.2021]

Switchboard¹³⁷ and publications from DH Conferences¹³⁸ and journals¹³⁹ retrieved from DBLP. All of these outcomes will eventually be used as a starting point to draft a report on Marketplace Interoperability, which in turn will serve as a base for the final deliverable of this task, D7.3.

2.7.1.4. TASK 7.4 GOVERNANCE: POPULATION, CURATION & SUSTAINABILITY OF THE SSH OPEN MARKETPLACE

Task is led by CNRS (Huma-Num), and DARIAH/PSNC, DARIAH/OEAW, TRUST-IT (and its LTPs) are the partners participating. Considering the links with other tasks, other partners, such as CNR or DARIAH/UGOE for example, were also regularly involved in T7.4 activities. Three main activities structured T7.4 work over the course of 2020:

(1) The SSH Open Marketplace Governance will be presented in D7.5 “Marketplace - Governance” (initially planned for M24, but submitted in 2021). To prepare this deliverable Huma-Num/CNRS is coordinating discussions between representatives of SSHOC project’s ERICs and partners: CNRS, CESSDA, CLARIN, DARIAH and TRUST-IT have met in January 2020 to get a first idea of the potential future contribution of ERICs to the Marketplace Governance. Then, a draft of the main governing bodies - a Governing Board, an Editorial Board and a Contributors Community - and governance hypotheses envisioned was presented during a 1st Tier Meeting in March 2020, and the five SSHOC ERICs (CESSDA, CLARIN, ESS, SHARE and DARIAH) have agreed to take part in the Governance of the SSH Open Marketplace at least for the first year after the project’s end. These different discussions contributed to the content of D7.5.

(2) The SSH Open Marketplace Curation will be presented in D7.4 “Data population and curation” for M36. To prepare this deliverable Huma-Num/CNRS has contributed to the efforts carried out for the manual curation of the content populating the Marketplace (alpha and beta releases). In order to clarify curation workflows (curation steps, actors involved and activities to perform) an extensive analysis of the first data ingestion was conducted by CNRS, CNR, DARIAH/OEAW and DARIAH, which led to substantial modifications of the data model of the Marketplace and the creation of editorial policy and guidelines for future curators. The different roles within the Editorial Board and also for contributors from the different communities has been established in relationship with the Contributors Community.

(3) The survey on the use of SSH vocabularies - D7.6 Resources for Marketplace content description - was initially planned for M24, but will be submitted in 2021. To prepare this deliverable Huma-Num/CNRS has designed the questionnaire, targeted channels for dissemination and defined the tool to be used (LimeSurvey provided by DARIAH/OEAW). Thanks to TRUST-IT and WP2 support, the survey was circulated between February and May 2020, gathering 330 participations (however not all complete) throughout the European SSH research community. Results and analysis are included in D7.6. This activity around SSH vocabularies was also an opportunity for collaboration with CLARIN who undertakes an harmonisation exercise regarding all the SSHOC survey/questionnaires/interviews conducted on SSH vocabularies and ontologies, and with other H2020 projects or international initiatives with regards to the analysis of the data collected: TRIPLE project or CO-OPERAS.

¹³⁷ CLARIN Switchboard: <https://switchboard.clarin.eu/tools> [22.01.2021]

¹³⁸ Digital Humanities Conference proceedings on DBLP: <https://dblp.org/db/conf/dihu/index.html> [22.01.2021]

¹³⁹ Digital Scholarship in the Humanities journal on DBLP: <https://dblp.org/db/journals/lalc/index.html> [22.01.2021]

2.7.2. Note on deviations from the plan and risk monitoring

No major deviations happened in 2020. Despite the COVID situation which has prevented all the face-to-face meetings planned for 2020, all the partners involved in WP7 work showed availability and reactivity. MS42 and MS43 were delivered thanks to the virtual and collaborative efforts of WP7 partners. Two deliverables - D7.5 “Marketplace - Governance” and D7.6 “Resources for Marketplace content description” - were expected at M24 (December 2020). They will be submitted in 2021, but were in the process of being finalised in 2020. Information on risk monitoring in WP7 for Year 2 is presented in the table below:

Table 10. Risk monitoring in WP7 - Year 2

Risks monitoring WP7				
<i>Risk (DoA)</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Mitigation measures applied?</i>	<i>Risk materialised so far?</i>	<i>Comments</i>
6	Too few available software developers	Yes	Yes	Two front-end developers were planned. After one of them left, the work was reorganised and prioritised to ensure a manageable workload for the remaining developer.
7	Technical difficulties of complex software development	Yes	No	Hired scientific developers highly experienced in SSH.

2.8. WP8 - Governance / Sustainability / Quality Assurance

WP8 goal is to elaborate efficient strategies to realize the successful integration of the SSH and CH research communities into the EOSC, addressing several layers of complexity including, but not limited to: governance, sustainability, quality and ethical requirements for research data, cross-disciplinary coordination and cooperation. WP 8 activities are articulated in 4 tasks, focussed on implementing a robust model for shared governance (T8.1); developing a framework to promote research data quality and support providers with repositories certification process (T8.2); elaborating shared legal and ethical guidelines for public research data sharing and reuse (T8.3); promoting cross-disciplinary and cross-clusters collaborations towards the development of shared resources at the European (T8.4).

During the second year of the project WP8 activities (T8.1; T8.4) have been focussed on **developing new synergies** with other relevant actors within and outside the ESFRI boundaries (e.g. RDA, EGI, FAIRsFAIR, Nordic-EOSC etc.) and **consolidating the ones already established** (e.g.: EU-LAC ResInfra cooperation) such as the connection with PaNOSC (Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud) on **aligning data policy frameworks**. This activity led to the finalisation of *Milestone 45 - First series of consultations with relevant parties*, that will constitute the basis for the final Report on inter-cluster cooperation activities.

Another relevant achievement for WP8 in 2020 has been the finalization of D8.2 Certification plan for SSHOC repositories, based on the first version of the first version of the SSHOC Certification framework for repositories (T8.2).

2.8.1. WP8 progress

2.8.1.1. TASK 8.1 GOVERNANCE & SUSTAINABILITY

Task 8.1 is led by CLARIN ERIC, while partners participating are DARIAH ERIC, CESSDA ERIC, LIBER, CNR, TRUST-IT. In 2020 the work for this task focused on the monitoring and **analysis of the ongoing discussions in the context of the establishment of EOSC** that are likely to have implication for the development of **models for the sustainability** of:

- Individual project results and platform components for which the ownership is with individual project partners,
- Components that are based on the integration of results for which the ownership is with multiple project partners, and
- Individual project results and components that by the end of the project will be ready for integration in the emerging EOSC framework.

Representatives of CLARIN, CESSDA and TRUST-IT active in T8.1 participate regularly in several of the ongoing discussions in the EOSC landscape. They have developed an information position that has enabled them to adequately plan the work towards the goals foreseen for the upcoming period and to provide the other partners with relevant information regarding the governance of EOSC and the consequences for the individual RIs and their contributions to SSHOC.

The task team participated regularly in several of the ongoing discussions in the EOSC landscape. **Liaisons with the EOSC WG Sustainability and EOSC WG Landscape** were created and used for strengthening the information position.

Discussions about the pros and cons of establishing a common legal entity that would facilitate the collaboration among the SSH partners represented in the steering group have taken place, both in Tier-1 Strategic Board meetings and with individual members.

A planning of T8.1 activities for Q1&Q2 2021 has been prepared, including external consultations (who, where, when) and the collection of the information and elements for a policy vision that will offer the basis for the sustainability models that will be included in the governance and sustainability roadmap. For this process a T8.1 ‘team’ session has been scheduled to collect topics for the question list guiding the external consultations.

The work of T8.1 was reflected in the co-organisation of the SSHOC workshop at the 2019 RDA plenary meeting in Helsinki about the role and position of RI clusters in the EOSC landscape and preparations for a follow up of this event at the RDA plenary meeting in 2021 have started in 2020.

2.8.1.2. TASK 8.2 TRUST & QUALITY ASSURANCE

Task 8.2 is led by CESSDA/FSD, while partners participating in this period were DARIAH-PSNC, CLARIN ERIC, KNAW(DANS), CESSDA/SND, CESSDA/UKDA, CNR. Task 8.2 carried out the support activities for the certification process of selected repositories. One of the main results in 2020 was submission of the ***Deliverable 8.2 Certification plan for SSHOC repositories***¹⁴⁰. The deliverable contains the certification plan for the SSHOC repositories, including an overview of the certification T8.2 status as well as the **certification goal for each repository**.

Repositories within SSHOC domains are very diverse. Trust work will include organisations at different levels of maturity, and the different levels of feasibility for the various goals within the project timeframe are quite diverse. The benefits of self-assessment and peer review against an agreed standard do not depend on formal certification. Undertaking the process improves internal communications and understanding as well as facilitates comparison to peer organisations and cooperation with partner organisations.

In this scenario Task 8.2 had created and followed certification plan for the SSHOC repositories, including an overview of the certification T8.2 status as well as the certification goal for each repository. To proceed coherently and effectively, **14 repositories were selected**, each of which was entrusted with 2 internal reviewers (internal to the project task).

These are the repositories that have been selected (after the collection of applications by 31 August 2020) to proceed with certification:

1. DARIAH-DE Repository

¹⁴⁰ Kleemola, Mari, Alaterä, Tuomas J., Koski, Niko, Ala-Lahti, Henri, Jerlehag, Birger, L'Hours, Hervé, ... Van Horik, René. (2020). SSHOC D8.2 Certification plan for SSHOC repositories (Version v1.0). Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3725867

2. Digital Repository of Scientific Institutes
3. Center for Socio-Political Data (CDSP) / Sciences Po
4. Croatian Social Science Data Archive (CROSSDA)
5. Lithuanian Data Archive for Social Sciences and Humanities (LiDA)
6. Publications of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts
7. CLARIN-LV
8. Historic Graves
9. mdwRepository
10. NAKALA
11. Slovak Archive of Social Data
12. SBX/CLARIN Repository (Språkbanken Text CLARIN Repository)
13. Corpus OVI dell'italiano antico
14. Digital library of University of Maribor.

A liaison has also been created with other relevant projects (e.g. FAIRsFAIR, Nordic-EOSC, ...) that provide CTS certification support. In this context, the hypothesis was raised of producing a paper as co-authors in which difficulties and features are taken into consideration that have been expressed, examined and possibly resolved during the support process.

The activities are related to:

- Supporting of CTS process for the repositories, including training and review of CTS self-assessments;
- Monitoring the progress of repositories with respect to certification;
- Establishing a virtual place for sharing experiences, problems and solutions about CTS
- Exploring the best ways to support standardisation, alignment and certification across the increasingly extended and complex partnerships which provide SSH infrastructure elements.
- Summary analysis of SSH repositories' weaknesses and strengths and recommendations for future.
- Evaluation of Repository services (in OAIS Reference Model/Trustworthy Digital Repository terms) vs other data services offered by partners with a view to broadening certification coverage
- Defining the criteria by which trusted services might be outsourced within the TDR model to support complex partnership models
- Review of the evaluation levels of the CTS alongside other traditional scoring mechanisms including quality, risk and maturity.
- Defining the relationship between CTS criteria and the co-dependant areas of trust^[4] ^[5] in software products and evaluation of the in-scope data collections (collection profiling) to align with FAIR.

The Task team also focused on the organization of webinars relating to the topics as a good way to reach the community. *SSHOC webinar: How to improve the quality of your repository?* was held on 23rd April 2020¹⁴¹.

¹⁴¹see Appendix - Tables of events, and Section 2.6 of this report on WP6 work

2.8.1.3. TASK 8.3 LEGAL AND ETHICAL ISSUES

Task 8.3 is led by CESSDA/NSD, while partners participating are CLARIN ERIC, DARIAH ERIC, SHARE ERIC, ESS ERIC, and CNR. The team collected information and data for the creation of a draft code of conduct regarding the GDPR, this set of rules outlines the norms/responsibilities and addresses legal issues related to open access, reusability of research data, and legal implementation of the FAIR principles. The aim is to contribute to a legal and ethical framework for SSH research that handle uncertainties and contribute to consistent and sustainable data-sharing rules across countries, legal systems and cultures to support the realisation of the EOSC.

A strong liaison has been created between Task 8.3 and WP5 Innovations in Data Access (notably T5.3 Legal Issues of innovative data access). From **Milestone 27 Draft report on the impact of the GDPR on research and the EOSC** (achieved in Feb 2020) in which the national data protection legislations in several European countries have been compared and an analysis has been done on whether or not they are beneficial for research and archival purposes. Task 5.3 is organizing a workshop in March 2021, where a SSH Code of Conduct will be discussed. Members of WP8, in particular task 8.3 will be invited and expected to participate sharing the resources previously collected. Focus will be on the implementation of the GDPR and its implications for cross-border research in Europe.

2.8.1.4. TASK 8.4 OVERARCHING CLUSTERS

Task 8.4 is led by CNR, while the partner participating in this period was CLARIN ERIC. The main activities of the Task 8.4 were related to inter-cluster cooperation as follows:

1) contribution to the conference co-organized by EOSC-hub, FREYA, SSHOC “Realising the European Open Science Cloud - Towards a FAIR Research Data Landscape for the Social Sciences, Humanities and Beyond” (Nov. 16-19, 2020). Virtual brainstorming and alignment meetings took place, in coordination with WP2, planning the structure and content of a special session **Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud: The EOSC ecosystem of open science marketplaces - from EOSC hub to EOSC Future**¹⁴² on Day 1 under the topic: Policy and Governance. (Nov. 16, 2020).

¹⁴² WP8 session at the event:

<https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/realising-european-open-science-cloud/thematic-discovery-marketplaces-european-open-science-cloud> and Zenodo recording: (doi:10.5281/zenodo.4277601): <https://zenodo.org/record/4277601#.YBFBYXdKjOR> [29.01.2021]

Figure 17. Contribution to the conference “Realising the European Open Science Cloud” by WP8 team

Several preparatory meetings narrowed down the topics to be addressed by the five thematic marketplace representatives:

- the needs of the research communities (complexity is the reality),
- highlighting one learning point for the clusters towards the future collaboration. How does the state-of-art translate to future collaboration in EOSC,
- singling out one top need for aggregation to EOSC future.

Three key activities were also identified on which cluster projects need to align with the EOSC portal:

- the design and development of the UX
- a target number of content and sources
- management and governance: Mechanisms envision

The session concluded with 3 joint recommendations for the future and collaborative work.

2) Collaboration with EOSC ESFRI Clusters Collaboration Interest Group (IG) ¹⁴³

Several operative sessions took place together with WP2, EOSC secretariat and cluster members, starting from July 2020. The purpose and scope of the Interest Group is to promote and facilitate ESFRI cluster collaboration in a bottom-up approach from the high-level governance discussions to engage the researchers in ESFRI involved in services operation and development. Among possible outcomes is the

¹⁴³ EOSC ESFRI Cluster Collaboration Group: <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-cluster-collaboration> [29.01.2021]

support, for organising and promotional work, at least until April 2021 when the EOSCsecretariat project officially ends. The brainstorming session focused on singling out some technical topics common to all the clusters so as to prevent re-invention – among those: data interoperability, policy, catalogue and services, EOSC integration, training, innovation – the usefulness of common repository at the level of deliverables.

Some common areas for collaborative actions were identified as follows:

- Interoperability of use cases,
- Sharing information on interoperability challenges,
- Streamlining collaborations between all the projects,
- Linking the outputs of ESFRI to the actions in the (INFRA EOSC) projects,
- Technical aspects e.g. best practices, use cases, success stories,
- Organisation a workshop to showcase the use-cases (focus on cross cluster use-cases if any).

The liaison platform (November 2020) managed by EOSC secretariat has been updated through the website and setting up the web forum/message board and mailing list. The next step could be an organization of thematic workshop kicking off the above-mentioned activities.

This work contributed to achieving the **Milestone 45 - First series of consultations with relevant parties**, closing one important phase in order to prepare for Deliverable 8.6. The Milestone was achieved in November, with the first set of consultations being crowned with the WP8 team contribution to the conference co-organized by EOSC-hub, FREYA, SSHOC.

2.8.2. Note on deviations from the plan and contingencies

Due to the COVID-19 crisis, a number of activities - including face-to-face meetings and other direct collaboration occasions - were rescheduled or canceled, causing delays in specific activities (i.e. T8.4) and resulting in a few minor deviations. However WP8 teams developed alternative approaches to improve the workflow and promote effective collaboration using digital tools and platforms for remote communication and community engagement.

Though no major deviations have to be reported for 2020, two slight delays should be reported:

- D8.2 has been postponed from M12 to M14, to allow a better alignment with FAIRsFAIR project's certification support work, CESSDA Trust work, and the E-RIHS work on quality assurance. The delay did not cause any negative consequences on other milestones or deliverables.
- MS45 First series of consultations with relevant parties has been delayed 3 months, to enable for efficient exchanges between the relevant clusters despite the difficulties caused by the COVID crisis (i.e.: meetings, workshops and conferences rescheduled and/or canceled). The delay did not cause any negative consequences on other milestones or deliverables.

Information on risk monitoring in WP8 for Year 2 is presented in the table below:

Table 11. Risk monitoring in WP8 - Year 2

Risks monitoring WP8				
Risk (DoA)	Description	Mitigation measures applied?	Risk materialised so far?	Comments
12	Imbalance between research communities in the governance: disciplines poorly/over represented	Yes	No	Mitigation measures implemented: Ensuring participation of different domains (Humanities, Social Sciences and Heritage Science), ongoing consultations with other EOSC actors
13	Overlapping of work with other clusters	Yes	Yes	Possible common actions involving other clusters have been investigated in various contexts; T8.4 established specific communication tools and procedures as part of the activities of the E-RIHS CO

2.9. WP9 - Data Communities

In 2020, WP9 built on preparation and investigation work done in the first year of the project, finalising four of its major Deliverables. A novelty impacting the whole SSHOC project are the links identified between SSHOC WP9 Data Communities, and the EURHISFIRM, an EC funded project aiming to “design a world-class research infrastructure to connect, collect, collate, align, and share detailed, reliable, and standardized long-term company-level data for Europe”¹⁴⁴, adding up to the existing European Value Studies and Migration Studies pilots already in the project. The 3 core institutions forming the EURHISFIRM Executive Board joined the SSHOC Consortium. They joined WP9 Data Communities, specifically and will be contributing to the deliverables with the input and perspective from their community.

2.9.1.1. TASK 9.1 IDENTIFYING SHARED AND UNIQUE CHALLENGES FOR SSH DATA COMMUNITIES; EVALUATION AND USABILITY REPORT

Task 9.1 is led by UNOTT and partners contributing are Sciences Po, SWC, EEP PSE, SAFE, UAntwerp. The task focuses on challenges that the user communities represented in WP9 experience when contributing to the SSHOC and on availability of procedures, tools and services to address these challenges, and whether these require tailoring for the user communities involved.

After producing a report identifying shared and unique challenges to user communities attempting to contribute to SSHOC (*D9.1 Report on challenges user communities face when attempting to contribute to SSHOC*), the team continued the work on investigating the same topic. A continuation of the analyses of these challenges is planned to result in preparation and submission of deliverable *D9.2 Mid-term evaluation report*, and *D9.3 Usability evaluation report* to be delivered in 2021, with additional focus of evaluating the usability of existing and developed procedures, tools and services from the perspectives of the user communities involved in this WP. The group involved in T9.3 has been extended in 2020 by the joining of the EURHISFIRM Consortium (EEP PSE, SAFE, UAntwerp) that was concluded in May 2020. The EURHISFIRM project representatives, after entering the SSHOC in 2020, have been participating in the consortium-related activities and meetings, and are preparing to contribute further in WP9 activities in 2021. In 2020, discussions have started to include another community in the project before summer 2021.

As a part of T9.1, the team contributed to the EOSC-hub, FREYA and SSHOC four-day conference *REALISING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD*. WP Leader (UNOTT) and Sciences Po (representing the Ethnic and Migration community in SSHOC) joined the session “*EOSC in Practice: From a Research Communities’ Perspective*” (19 November 2020) aiming to discuss the added value of EOSC for research practices. Sciences Po also contributed the conference organising a session “*Implementing FAIR data principles - The Ethnic and Migrant Minorities’ Survey registry*” (16 November 2020), illustrating how the FAIR principles informed the design, development, and delivery of the EMM Survey Registry, developed by Task 9.2 alongside COST Action 16111 - ETHMIGSURVEYDATA and FAIRETHMIGQAUNT. Sciences Po, together with EEP PSE joined the “*FAIR Data-Citation for Social Sciences and Humanities*” session (16 November 2020), on data citation in SSH from a historical point of view and current practices in different

¹⁴⁴ EURhisFIRM project website: <https://eurhisfirm.eu/index.php/the-project-2/> [20.07.2020]

domains. SWC contributed to the event by participation in a panel discussion “*Engaging the Private Sector: Roadblocks and success stories in the uptake of EOSC services*” (18 November 2020) representing the private sector perspective, demonstrating how the marketplace and environment of EOSC can be used by industry, as well as representing the private sector in the discussion, how EOSC data and data related services could also be used by European industry, and which conditions would be important to foster such collaborations.

Figure 18. Contribution to the conference “Realising the European Open Science Cloud” by WP9 team members

The work on the T9.1 will intensify in 2021 and towards the end of the project, including collaboration with WP6.

2.9.1.2. TASK 9.2 ETHNIC AND MIGRATION STUDIES

Task 9.2 is led by Sciences Po (CEE team) who works routinely with two closely related projects, COST Action 16111 – ETHMIGSURVEYDATA (a research network with 200 plus members who are primarily based in Europe, and are part of the ethnic and migration studies field)¹⁴⁵ and FAIRETHMIGQUANT (a project funded via the French Agence Nationale de la Recherche Open Science call)¹⁴⁶. As Task 9.2’s overarching objective is to help make quantitative survey data on ethnic and migrant minorities’ (EMMs) integration FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), it is working to: (1) produce a consolidated FAIR-compliant registry (i.e. the EMM Survey Registry¹⁴⁷) that displays survey-level metadata

¹⁴⁵ ETHMIGSURVEYDATA COST’s webpage: <https://www.cost.eu/actions/CA16111> [09.03.2021]

¹⁴⁶ Sciences Po’s webpage for FAIRETHMIGQUANT, with brief description about the project: <https://www.sciencespo.fr/centre-etudes-europeennes/en/node/30931.html> [09.03.2021]

¹⁴⁷ EMM Survey Registry landing/welcome page: <https://ethmigsurveydatahub.eu/emmregistry/> [09.03.2021]

for existing quantitative surveys on EMMs' integration in Europe and (2) test the feasibility of setting up, within the CESSDA-led EuroQuestionBank (EQB), a full stream component that is dedicated to a selection of the surveys identified and subsequently included in the aforementioned EMM Survey Registry.

The beta version of the EMM Survey Registry was finalised in June 2020 and the deliverable **D9.4 Database with the metadata of surveys to EMMs across Europe (Version v1.0)**¹⁴⁸ was submitted in October 2020. The Registry, which continues to be offered in beta version, displays metadata for over **750 surveys** from **18 different countries**. It is also fully functional, allowing a wide-range of users to easily filter (simple and advanced), sort and search for surveys that are of interest to them. In 2021, Task 9.2 will continue to enhance the beta version of the Registry by: (a) expanding its metadata collection, such as including COVID-19 surveys undertaken with EMM respondents; (b) further improving the Registry's existing functionalities so it can more easily be sustained and updated in the short and long-term; (c) making it accessible to and interoperable with relevant databases/data catalogues by attempting to set up an OAI-PMH compliant API; and (d) collaborating with WP7 to ensure that the Registry can be successfully integrated and included in the SSH Marketplace and subsequently the EOSC.

Moreover, in parallel with developing and enhancing the Registry, the Task 9.2 team, in close collaboration with the two above mentioned communities, has been working on a pilot to test and vet the workflow needed to successfully integrate the questionnaires of surveys on EMMs' integration into the EQB. Specifically, through this pilot, which uses surveys covering the topic of civic life and political integration, initial processes for how to collect questionnaires and how to document the questionnaire/question items and the metadata have been developed.

2.9.1.3. TASK 9.3 DATA COMMUNITY PROJECT: ELECTORAL STUDIES & EURHISFIRM

Task 9.3 is led by UNOTT and contains contributions from SWC, AUSSDA, UNOTT and EEP PSE, SAFE, UAntwerp. The main task of T9.3 is the development of a **Knowledge Graph (KG)** in Electoral Studies as a pilot to assess the potential, as well as the challenges, for the development of such research-infrastructure tools in other subdisciplines of the social sciences, such as the field of historical financial data (EURHISFIRM).

Much of the work at the beginning of 2020 involved laying the foundation for the development of the KG, including the demarcation of the field and the research community involved, planning engagement of the user community, and detailing the specifications of the pilot KG. The demarcation of the field of electoral studies outlined in **D9.6 Demarcation Report of Electoral Studies User Community** (submitted in February 2020)¹⁴⁹ served as the basis for planning the pilot KG. Here the scholars from UNOTT and the AUSSDA contributed the necessary subject-specific knowledge. SWC provided the technical know-how for implementing the pilot KG. A two-day workshop involving the group members was held in February. The resulting planning for a pilot KG on electoral participation, a prominent subfield of electoral studies, was

¹⁴⁸ Saji, Ami and Laura Morales. (2020). D9.4 Database with the metadata of surveys to EMMs across Europe (Version v1.0). Zenodo. 10.5281/zenodo.4088377

¹⁴⁹ Van der Eijk, Cees. (2020). SSHOC D 9.6 Demarcation Report of Electoral Studies User Community. Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3725822.

documented in ***D9.7 Design and Planning of Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies***¹⁵⁰. Developing the pilot KG should also involve the user-community; a plan was delivered in June 2020 by UNOTT - ***D9.8 User-community involvement plan in the development of a Knowledge Graph for Electoral Studies***¹⁵¹.

The actual development of the KG has also started in late Spring 2020. Scholars from AUSSDA provided the expertise on which publications and datasets relevant to the field of electoral turnout research should be ingested into the KG and from which resources information about publications and datasets might be gathered. Towards the end of the year, much work by AUSSDA went into developing a proto ontology. This proto ontology was refined in collaboration with the involved scholars from the AUSSDA and UNOTT. SWC assisted the group in providing the necessary technological foundations and, at the same time, started implementing the KG in the PoolParty Semantic Suite (the software tool used for this work). This work should result in the planned pilot KG that will be a part of D9.9 in 2021. In addition to the substantive work, the group involved in T9.3 has been extended by the joining of the EURHISFIRM Consortium (EEP PSE, SAFE, UAntwerp) that was concluded in May 2020.

2.9.1.4. TASK 9.4 HERITAGE SCIENCE AND HUMANITIES

Task 9.4 is led by CNR with contributions from CNRS (MAP). The goal for T9.4 is to foster the integration of the Heritage Science digital ecosystem within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) by aligning the development of the E-RIHS digital platform (DIGILAB) with the EOSC requirements and landscape. To better represent the needs and requirements of the Heritage Science community and capitalize on existing digital assets, a number of activities have been undertaken in close collaboration with both internal (i.e.: SSHOC tasks) and external actors (i.e.: IPERION-CH¹⁵² and IPERION-HS¹⁵³ projects, RDA, EU-CELAC ResInfra collaboration¹⁵⁴ and EGI). The activities related to the SSHOC Market Place development are also of key relevance for the development of the HS pilot in T9.4, since they define the architectural and technical design of the SSHOC digital platform.

Up until the end of 2020, the task team (OVI-CNR) has developed a data community pilot project, working on the **alpha version of the digital infrastructure of RESTORE** - smaRt accESs TO digital heRitage and mEmory - platform (pilot), which will be released in 2021.

RESTORE is a digital platform made of tools for the mapping and the integration of dataset coming from different GLAM institutions; the task team has worked with partners settled in Tuscany but representative of the cultural *bureaux* at a national level, responsible for research within the HS fields. Crossing each disciplinary border, the team lab worked at the integration of the contents provided by each different partner, such as the documents of State Archives (office of Prato), the works of art entries of the Municipal Museum of the city of Prato, the lemmatised *corpora* of letters from the OVI (Institute

¹⁵⁰ Van der Eijk Cees, Kritzinger Sylvia, Partheymüller Julia, Kaltenböck Martin, Ahmeti Albin, & Karampatakis Sotirios. (2020). SSHOC D9.7 Design and Planning of Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies (Version v1.0). Zenod. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3824265.

¹⁵¹ Van der Eijk, Cees (2020). D9.8 User-community involvement plan. Zenodo. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3931722.

¹⁵² Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure ON Cultural Heritage (H2020-INFRAIA-2014-2015, Grant n. 654028)

¹⁵³ Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science (H2020-INFRAIA-2018-2020, Grant n. 871034)

¹⁵⁴ Towards a new EU-CELAC partnership in Research Infrastructures (INFRA SUPP-01-2018-2019)

for the Italian Vocabulary - *Crusca* Academy). So far, the workflow planned and followed by the task team has been focused on the semantization of the datasets, realised by use of free and open access tools: the data are stored in CKAN, and the KARMA¹⁵⁵ data integration tool was used to map the different types of data. A transformation from different file format has been a key in order to foster data integration, going from the acquisition of materials organised by each discipline standards (such as EAD - EAC, ICCD entries, and so on) to their transformation in CIDOC-crm ontology (also, a SSHOCro). Such a system will allow each user - and especially those coming from research institutes - to get open access to a unique data lake, where both the original resources and their triples (RDF), could be visualized and, if needed, downloaded.

In 2020, the task team has also participated in two relevant meetings: the EU-CELAC ResInfra collaboration on Digital Infrastructures Kick Off Meeting (30-31 January 2020, Madrid, Spain, Ministry of Science) and DIGILAB Working Group Kick Off Meeting (Virtual) on 1 April 2020. The two meetings gathered researchers and professionals working in the field of Heritage Science from the European and Pan American communities and focussing on the establishment of interoperable research infrastructures. A direct follow-up of this activity has been the elaboration of a BoF proposal, held at the 16th RDA Plenary in August 2020, discussing Linguistic and Disciplinary Barriers to Heritage Science Data Interoperability¹⁵⁶.

2.9.1.5. NOTE ON DEVIATIONS FROM THE PLAN AND RISK MONITORING

WP9 has experienced delays with regards to deliverables and milestones due to COVID-19 situation and a limited personnel in the WP leading institution. The D9.2 Midterm evaluation report has been delayed, but should be submitted in the Q1-2 of 2021. The *D9.6 Demarcation Report* and *D9.7 Design of Knowledge graph* were both scheduled in 2019 but were finalised and submitted in 2020. Finally, *D9.8 User-community involvement plan*, had a three months delay in order to allow for quality peer-review and inclusion of all relevant partners. Information on risk monitoring in WP9 for Year 2 is presented in the table below:

Table 12. Risk monitoring in WP9 - Year 2

Risks monitoring WP9				
Risk (DoA)	Description	Mitigation measures applied?	Risk materialised so far?	Comments
U7	Vulnerability to obstructing personal circumstances in small teams where work to be done cannot be transferred to another team member	Yes	Yes	The Coordinator and WP9 working on other solutions, engaging more partners in WP9 work that can take over part of the work obligations to relieve partner with a small number of team members.

¹⁵⁵ Karma is an information integration tool that enables users to quickly and easily integrate data from a variety of data sources including databases, spreadsheets, delimited text files, XML, JSON, KML and Web APIs (cfr. <https://usc-isi-i2.github.io/karma/>)

¹⁵⁶ RDA plenary August 2020 :

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/linguistic-and-disciplinary-barriers-heritage-science-data-interoperability> [20.07.2020]

3. Summary of progress and delivery

As explained in the previous chapters, SSHOC project managed to achieve **13 Milestones**, and submit **16 Deliverables** in Year 2. This is another year of successful work, and in spite of the COVID pandemic. Most of the delays were due to several being scheduled for the same date, or overlapping with the holiday season. The postponed deliverables (see Table 14 below) are expected in the first half of 2021 and do not cause any concern. Review processes have been prolonged, and the main focus put on quality. No negative consequence for the rest of the work is perceived. The following tables show a summary of the Milestones achieved and Deliverables submitted in Year 2.:

Table 13. Milestones planned and achieved in Year 2 of SSHOC Project

Year 2 - 2020						
MILESTONES						
WP No.	Task	No.	Title	Lead beneficiary	Due Date (month)	Actual delivery (month)
WP 2	2.3	MS 5	SSHOC web platform continuous marketplace integration with SSHOC service offer 1/3	TRUST-IT	12	15
WP 2	2.3	MS 6	SSHOC web platform continuous marketplace integration with SSHOC service offer 2/3	TRUST-IT	24	<i>pending</i>
WP 3	3.3	MS 13	Intermediate evaluation of developed TDM algorithms	CLARIN ERIC	20	20
WP 3	3.5	MS 14	Inventory of existing (meta-)data format interoperability solutions	CESSDA ERIC	18	18
WP 4	4.1	MS 15	Test of Sample Management System complete	ESS ERIC	21	19
WP 4	4.2	MS 16	Survey questions extracted from TMT and delivered in machine readable format, to be used as input for T4.3 and T3.1	CentERdata	21	<i>pending</i>
WP 4	4.3	MS 17	Open source CAT TM software selected	ESS ERIC	22	19
WP 4	4.3	MS 18	Beta version of automatic verification software available for testing	SHARE ERIC	24	<i>pending</i>
WP 4	4.7	MS 20	SSH metadata standards for mapping to SSHOCro selected	FORTH	18	18
WP 5	5.1	MS 22	Inventory of computing space needed for processing and analyzing accelerometer data	SHARE	20	20
WP 5	5.3	MS 27	Draft report on the impact of the GDPR on research and the EOSC	CESSDA ERIC	14	14
WP 5	5.4	MS 28	Assessment of existing platforms	CESSDA ERIC	24	<i>pending</i>
WP 5	5.5	MS 31	Setting up and populating a new ESS repository	ESS ERIC	20	<i>pending</i>
WP 5	5.5	MS 32	Developing APIs	ESS ERIC	21	<i>pending</i>
WP 5	5.5	MS 33	Integrate data publishing with DataCite/DOI and bespoke advanced landing pages with rich functionalities	ESS ERIC	23	<i>pending</i>
WP 5	5.7	MS 36	Identification of a suitable archaeological case study and implementation of prototypes of the software module and the corresponding web service for that case study	DAI	22	<i>pending</i>
WP 6	6.2	MS 39	Launch expertise strategy	CESSDA ERIC	13	15
WP 6	6.4	MS 40	SSHOC train-the trainer toolkit (preliminary version)	KNAW	16	16
WP 7	7.4	MS 42	Marketplace – alpha release	DARIAH ERIC & CRNS	18	18
WP 7	7.4	MS 43	Marketplace – beta release	DARIAH ERIC & CRNS	24	24
WP 8	8.4	MS 45	First series of consultations with relevant parties	CNR	20	23
WP 9	9.4	MS 49	Heritage Science and Humanities Pilot alpha release	UNOTT, CNR	18	<i>pending</i>

Table 14. Deliverables scheduled and delivered in Year 2 of SSHOC Project

Year 2 - 2020						
DELIVERABLES						
WP No.	Relative number in WP	Del. No.	Title	Lead beneficiary	Expected submission date	Actual delivery date
WP1	D1.3	D3	First Annual Progress & Activity Report	CESSDA ERIC	31 Jan 2020	31 Jan 2020
WP1	D1.6	D6	Data Management Plan - DMP	CESSDA ERIC	30 Jun 2020	30 Jun 2020
WP2	D2.2	D8	Preliminary report on user communities engagement	TRUST-IT	31 Dec 2020	<i>postponed</i>
WP4	D4.3	D22	Survey specific parallel corpora	ESS ERIC	30 Jun 2020	30 Jun 2020
WP4	D4.4	D23	Guidelines for building survey-specific corpora	ESS ERIC	30 Jun 2020	26 Jun 2020
WP4	D4.7	D26	Code for data exchange between TMT and open source CAT software	CentERdata	30 Sep 2020	<i>postponed</i>
WP4	D4.8	D27	Report on possibilities for incorporating open source CAT tool functionality into the TMT	CentERdata	31 Dec 2020	<i>postponed</i>
WP4	D4.14	D33	Policy API tool	KNAW	31 Dec 2019	11 Mar 2020
WP4	D4.18	D37	SSHOCro beta version	FORTH	31 Dec 2019	26 Mar 2020
WP4	D4.19	D38	Mapping of two indicative selected standards to the SSHOCro	FORTH	31 Dec 2020	15 Dec 2020
WP5	D5.1	D40	Guidelines for ethics considerations in making biomedical survey data FAIR (Access to biomedical data)	SHARE ERIC	30 Jun 2020	<i>postponed</i>
WP5	D5.2	D41	Data access protocol for DBSS data, linked to survey data, conforming FAIR principles (Access to biomedical data)	SHARE ERIC	31 Oct 2020	18 Dec 2020
WP5	D5.7	D46	Report on the impact of the GDPR and its implications for EOSC (Legal issues of innovative data access)	SHARE ERIC	31 Oct 2020	<i>postponed</i>
WP5	D5.8	D47	Draft SSH GDPR Code of Conduct (Legal issues of innovative data access)	CESSDA ERIC	31 Oct 2020	<i>postponed</i>
WP5	D5.9	D48	Framework for Data Use Agreements (Remote access to sensitive data)	CESSDA ERIC	30 Jun 2020	<i>postponed</i>
WP5	D5.17	D56	Implementation plan for the archaeological case study	DAI	30 Jun 2020	29 Jun 2020
WP5	D5.19	D58	Report on stakeholder workshop about a SSH Code of Conduct (Coop. with 8.3)	CESSDA ERIC	31 Dec 2020	<i>postponed</i>
WP6	D6.5	D64	Report on Stakeholder Forum	CESSDA ERIC	31 Dec 2020	<i>postponed</i>
WP6	D6.9	D68	SSHOC train-the-trainer toolkit (draft)	KNAW	30 Apr 2020	29 Apr 2020
WP6	D6.10	D69	Report on the SSHOC Training network (first iteration)	KNAW	30 Apr 2020	06 May 2020
WP7	D7.5	D79	Marketplace – Governance	CNRS	31 Dec 2020	<i>postponed</i>
WP7	D7.6	D80	Resources for Marketplace content description	CNRS	31 Dec 2020	<i>postponed</i>
WP8	D8.2	D82	Certification plan for SSHOC repositories	CESSDA ERIC	31 Dec 2019	28 Feb 2020
WP9	D9.2	D88	Midterm evaluation report	UNOTT	31 Aug 2020	<i>postponed</i>
WP9	D9.4	D90	Database with the metadata of surveys to EMMs across Europe	Sciences Po	31 Oct 2020	13 Oct 2020
WP9	D9.6	D92	Demarcation Report	UNOTT	30 Jun 2019	28 Feb 2020
WP9	D9.7	D93	Design of Knowledge Graph	SWC	31 Dec 2019	24 Apr 2020
WP9	D9.8	D94	User-community involvement plan	UNOTT	31 Mar 2020	30 Jun 2020

4. Use of resources and budget expenditure

With the second year ending, the project reached 60% of its duration (24/40 months). Out of the 42 tasks in the project, 2 ended in year 1, and one ended during 2020, while the other 39 tasks teams were active all 12 months of 2020. The work intensified, after the starting year, and looking at the work and achievements planned inform Milestones and Deliverables, it can be concluded that 21 out of 49 Milestones (42 %) were scheduled and 28 out of 101 Deliverables were planned (27 %) for 2020, including the postponed ones from the previous year. Not all were finalised or achieved, but work has started on most. That is in line with the Use of resources reported by the partners by the end of 2020, where in total about 882 person-months were used (50%) of the total person-months allocated to the project, expecting most of the important final deliverables to follow in Year 3. Translated to budget expenditure, about 6,2 million € was spent (43%) out of the total budget of 14,5 million €. The slight discrepancy is certainly due to unused travel budget and unused budget for organising face-to-face events, as well as some missing numbers at the time of this reporting. The Use of resources summary tables present an estimation reported by partners by the end 2020. The expectation is that Year 3 of the project (2021) will be more demanding, as all the tasks are active, and most of the delivery is planned in that period.

Table 15. Use of resources: Person-months reported per partner per work package in first 2 years of SSHOC

Status after Y2 (2020)												
TOTAL SPENT PM												
No.	Partner	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	Total	% spent
1	CESSDA ERIC	19.8	-	-	-	-	-	0.4	0.3	-	20.5	49%
1.1	NSD	-	-	-	-	4.9	-	-	-	-	4.9	29%
1.2	UKDS	0.2	-	4.4	-	2.7	2.0	-	2.1	-	11.4	46%
1.3	UL-ADP	0.3	1.0	0.5	-	-	4.5	-	-	-	6.3	34%
1.4	GESIS	0.1	-	3.8	-	4.7	0.6	-	-	-	9.1	30%
1.5	SND	0.4	-	2.0	-	-	-	-	1.5	-	3.9	27%
1.6	UTA-FSD	0.3	-	7.3	-	-	-	-	5.7	-	13.3	54%
1.7	FORS	0.5	-	0.0	-	0.3	-	-	-	-	0.9	11%
1.8	DNA	0.2	-	-	-	1.5	-	-	-	-	1.7	27%
1.9	AUSSDA	0.3	4.7	-	-	5.2	-	-	-	2.3	12.5	59%
2	ESS ERIC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	-
2.1	City	1.8	-	-	14.2	-	-	-	-	-	16.0	65%
2.2	GESIS	0.3	-	-	12.5	-	-	-	-	-	12.9	112%
2.3	UPF	2.8	-	-	31.2	-	-	-	-	-	34.0	65%
2.4	NSD	-	-	-	-	13.4	-	-	-	-	13.4	25%
3	SHARE ERIC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	-
3.1	MPISOC	-	-	-	2.2	21.7	-	-	0.8	-	24.7	22%
3.2	UniVe	-	-	24.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	24.2	67%
4	CLARIN ERIC	3.0	2.1	45.6	-	1.8	1.8	6.8	4.0	-	65.1	55%
4.1	Athena	0.2	-	8.2	-	-	-	0.5	-	-	8.9	43%
4.2	EKUT	-	-	5.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	5.3	21%
4.3	CUNI	0.6	-	8.3	12.5	-	-	-	-	-	21.4	75%
4.4	UL-FF	0.8	-	-	-	-	13.1	-	-	-	14.0	46%
4.5	RUN	-	-	-	2.8	3.8	-	-	-	-	6.6	35%
5	DARIAH ERIC	0.8	2.1	-	-	-	0.5	16.9	-	-	20.2	60%
5.1	PSNC	0.1	-	-	-	7.3	-	17.4	3.6	-	28.4	45%
5.2	OEAW	-	-	1.9	-	-	3.3	33.3	-	-	38.5	54%
5.3	UGOE	-	-	10.5	-	-	-	18.5	-	-	29.0	45%
6	LIBER	1.5	4.3	2.9	-	-	16.2	-	-	-	24.8	60%
7	KNAW - GGP	0.4	-	2.9	24.4	12.5	5.0	-	3.1	-	48.4	60%
8	UoY - ADS	-	-	-	-	6.7	-	-	-	-	6.7	67%
9	TIU	0.5	-	8.4	1.7	-	-	-	-	-	10.5	43%
10	TRUST-IT	1.0	11.2	-	-	-	2.5	1.1	0.6	-	16.4	66%
10.1	Trust-SRL	0.2	9.0	-	-	-	1.6	0.3	0.3	-	11.3	45%
10.2	COMMpla	0.2	7.0	-	-	-	3.5	1.4	0.2	-	12.2	98%
11	SWC	0.3	-	-	-	-	-	11.0	-	9.3	20.6	67%
12	SCIENCES PO	-	-	-	47.0	-	-	-	-	24.8	71.7	67%
13	UNOTT	1.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.4	3.4	32%
14	DAI	0.1	-	2.0	1.0	7.0	-	-	-	-	10.1	53%
15	CNRS	0.3	1.7	4.8	14.2	-	1.8	20.7	-	-	43.4	52%
16	CNR	0.3	0.6	18.0	7.6	16.4	3.6	4.0	18.2	1.1	69.7	45%
17	UCL	0.3	-	-	-	-	10.0	-	-	-	10.3	108%
18	FORTH	-	-	2.5	31.3	-	-	1.5	-	-	35.3	153%
19	CentERdata	0.4	-	11.6	13.8	12.1	-	-	-	-	37.9	37%
20	NG	0.4	-	-	-	2.2	-	-	-	-	2.5	21%
21	EEP PSE	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0%
22	SAFE	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0%
23	Uantwerp	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	0%
Total		39.3	43.6	175.1	216.3	124.1	69.7	133.7	40.5	39.8	882.1	50%

Table 16. Use of budget reported per partner in the first 2 years of the project

Status after Y2 (2020)							
TOTAL SPENT BUDGET							
No.	Partner	Personnel €	Sub-contracting €	Other costs €	Indirect costs €	Total Spent €	% spent
1	CESSDA ERIC	166,946.77	-	42,573.92	52,380.17	261,900.86	62.45%
1.1	NSD	28,979.33	-	2,818.93	7,949.57	39,747.83	21.99%
1.2	UKDS	66,299.77	-	1,993.87	17,073.41	85,367.05	30.90%
1.3	UL-ADP	23,342.84	-	1,835.19	6,294.51	31,472.54	37.00%
1.4	GESIS	58,465.25	-	1,016.58	14,870.46	74,352.29	25.81%
1.5	SND	22,123.18	-	2,919.32	6,260.63	31,303.13	20.20%
1.6	UTA-FSD	86,161.45	-	1,755.61	21,979.27	109,896.33	48.06%
1.7	FORS	11,275.00	-	2,557.24	3,458.06	17,290.30	15.20%
1.8	DNA	10,520.56	-	1,557.41	3,019.49	15,097.46	20.37%
1.9	AUSSDA	60,788.14	-	1,232.08	15,505.06	77,525.28	45.34%
2	ESS ERIC	-	-	-	-	0.00	0.00%
2.1	City	98,823.77	-	4,312.84	25,784.15	128,920.76	58.47%
2.2	GESIS	71,764.35	-	8,485.72	20,062.52	100,312.59	71.56%
2.3	UPF	133,653.52	-	8,804.63	35,614.54	178,072.69	48.29%
2.4	NSD	85,252.22	-	3,025.35	22,069.39	110,346.96	19.13%
3	SHARE ERIC	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.1	MPISOC	201,754.09	-	1,082.49	50,709.15	253,545.73	33.00%
3.2	UniVe	102,420.00	-	-	25,605.00	128,025.00	60.15%
4	CLARIN ERIC	483,834.71	-	34,347.52	119,475.97	637,658.20	55.98%
4.1	Athena	38,755.38	-	3,914.66	10,667.51	53,337.55	38.27%
4.2	EKUT	34,078.94	-	1,923.03	9,000.49	45,002.46	18.03%
4.3	CUNI	57,272.38	-	2,597.12	14,967.38	74,836.88	40.74%
4.4	UL-FF	30,511.59	-	3,617.54	8,532.28	42,661.41	29.77%
4.5	RUN	55,962.42	-	2,477.90	14,610.08	73,050.40	42.20%
5	DARIAH ERIC	98,099.90	-	6,199.76	26,074.92	130,374.58	52.61%
5.1	PSNC	149,134.40	-	4,556.09	38,422.62	192,113.11	46.71%
5.2	OEAW	181,229.09	-	4,948.01	46,544.28	232,721.38	48.76%
5.3	UGOE	160,851.65	-	2,939.38	40,947.76	204,738.79	38.16%
6	LIBER	146,391.88	-	9,725.70	39,029.40	195,146.98	43.28%
7	KNAW - GGP	356,109.44	-	2,623.83	89,683.32	448,416.59	51.67%
8	UoY - ADS	35,953.62	-	1,406.17	9,339.95	46,699.74	49.69%
9	TIU	54,524.54	-	993.07	13,879.40	69,397.01	24.85%
10	TRUST-IT	82,913.03	-	6,864.24	22,444.32	112,221.59	43.32%
10.1	Trust-SRL	31,283.97	-	728.44	8,003.10	40,015.51	25.97%
10.2	COMMpla	36,811.71	-	-	9,202.93	46,014.64	62.00%
11	SWC	125,304.17	-	3,771.48	32,268.91	161,344.56	66.72%
12	SCIENCES PO	323,985.49	-	20,184.29	86,042.45	430,212.23	56.96%
13	UNOTT	41,523.14	-	496.60	10,504.94	52,524.68	23.14%
14	DAI	87,176.32	-	455.28	21,907.90	109,539.50	74.62%
15	CNRS	184,961.74	-	7,009.55	47,992.82	239,964.11	40.87%
16	CNR	326,487.88	-	4,183.12	82,667.75	413,338.75	46.94%
17	UCL	49,761.27	-	1,172.14	12,733.35	63,666.76	63.90%
18	FORTH	73,662.58	-	3,705.19	19,341.94	96,709.71	66.13%
19	CentERdata	274,999.26	-	2,360.72	69,340.00	346,699.98	33.02%
20	NG	15,238.15	-	984.05	4,055.55	20,277.75	18.22%
21	EEP PSE	-	-	-	-	0.00	0.00%
22	SAFE	-	-	-	-	0.00	0.00%
23	Uantwerp	-	-	-	-	0.00	0.00%
Total		4,765,388.89	-	220,156.06	1,236,316.70	6,221,861.65	43.00 %

5. Conclusions

In the first 2 years, SSHOC Consortium has achieved most of its planned milestones and objectives and the impact is already visible. Regardless of the COVID-19 situation, the work has continued, measures for mitigating the risks have been applied, and, where necessary, the activities have been adapted to the new environments and conditions. The focus remained on quality, results, and community building with an impact.

An important milestone highlighted the end of 2020 - submission of the 1st SSHOC Periodic report to the EC, and it being approved as a part of the 1st EC review of the project. It resulted in all 27 deliverables submitted by June 2020 being approved by the EC as well, providing additional motivation for the partners and a confirmation of the quality of the work done within the project. The management package team (WP1) focused on maintaining this quality and handling successfully a Consortium of this size, at the same time going beyond SSHOC, and maintaining close connections with other cluster projects and considering the strategically important issues.

The project teams working in WP2 and WP6 on branding, dissemination and community building have been mostly affected by the COVID-19 restrictions, which prevented delivery of numerous face-to-face activities, thus making work on visibility of the project even more challenging. However, closely monitoring the situation and in collaboration with all partners, fostering communities, empowering users and building expertise have been achieved by adopting a creative and flexible approach, tailor-made to the needs of the project, its partners, and its stakeholders. The project review by the EC has found that the dissemination and activities carried out have produced good results *"...as the brand of SSHOC is recognizable, relying on the strategy to network with different established communities of stakeholders..."*.

EC review also confirmed the originally ambitious plan being realised: *"...to build an umbrella cloud and create a hub gathering all social sciences and humanities networks and to provide conditions for them to collaborate, the project is confidently on the way of accomplishing this objective both on the technological and on the organizational side"*.

The WPs and teams gathered around technological work e.g. WP3 (on Lifting technologies and services to SSH Cloud) and WP7 (on Creating the SSH Open Marketplace) confirm progress with their work in 2020, as they have further deepened the contacts with the SSHOC communities, were active in promoting the activities at conferences, while working intensely together to align the ongoing work. All efforts resulted in the first two versions of the SSH Marketplace.

Teams involved in Innovations in data production (WP4) have also been successful in avoiding the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic and executing most of planned activities. Prototype and Beta versions of the main research outputs were launched with success. Teams focused on Innovations in data access (WP5) had success in tool development, preparing guidelines and frameworks, transferring knowledge on FAIR data across communities and developing applicable workflows. Last, but not least, the Governance and Sustainability work (WP8), as well as engaging and including new Data Communities (WP9) in SSHOC is well on its way, intensifying, as planned, in Year 3 of the project. Thus, the Consortium considers the project to be on track and has successfully started the third year of its implementation.

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SSHOC Brand guidelines:

https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sites/default/files/SSHOC%20Guideline_booklet.pdf [accessed 20.01.2021]

SSHOC Communications kit: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/communications-kit> [accessed 20.01.2021]

SSHOC Dashboard: <https://datastudio.google.com/reporting/1JtTWjrE7ee81DbpkWZc6596J22VNQncR> [accessed 18.01.2021]

SSHOC Flickr: <https://www.flickr.com/photos/170844433@N02/> [accessed 18.01.2021]

SSHOC LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/18997546/> [accessed 18.01.2021]

SSHOC Logo pack: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/logo-pack> [accessed 20.01.2021]

SSHOC Newsletter: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/newsletter/sshoc-newsletter> [accessed 20.01.2021]

SSHOC Online Information Sessions: Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms - First session: Wikibase:

<https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-online-information-sessions-open-source-vocabulary-hosting-and-management-platforms-first> [accessed 21.01.2021]

SSHOC Online Information Sessions: Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms - Second session – SKOSMOS:

<https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-online-information-sessions-open-source-vocabulary-hosting-and-management-platforms-second> [accessed 21.01.2021]

SSHOC Online Information Sessions: Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms - Third session - CESSDA Vocabulary Service:

<https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-online-information-sessions-open-source-vocabulary-hosting-and-management-platforms-third> [accessed 21.01.2021]

SSHOC Scientific publications on the website: <https://sshopencloud.eu/scientific-publications> [20.01.2021]

SSHOC Training page: <https://sshopencloud.eu/training> [accessed 21.01.2021]

SSHOC Twitter: <https://twitter.com/SSHOpenCloud> [18.01.2021]

SSHOC Webinar: CLARIN Hands-on Tutorial on Transcribing Interview Data,

<https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-webinar-clarin-hands-tutorial-transcribing-interview-data>

SSHOC Webinar: DARIAH Community Requirements for a Dataverse Repository:

<https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-dariah-community-requirements-dataverse-repository> [accessed 21.01.2021]

SSHOC Webinar: Discussion meeting about requirements of CESSDA Service Providers for a Dataverse repository: <https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-cessda-service-providers-dataverse> [accessed 21.01.2021]

SSHOC Webinar: How to improve the quality of your repository? SSHOC and certification of repositories:

<https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-repositories-quality-certification> [accessed 21.01.2021]

- SSHOC Webinar: Use and Re-use of Scientific Data in Archaeology and Heritage,
<https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-webinar-use-and-re-use-scientific-data-archaeology-and-heritage> [accessed 21.01.2021]
- SSHOC Webinar: Introducing the newly launched Ethnic and Migrant Minorities (EMM) Survey Registry
<https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-introducing-newly-launched-ethnic-and-migrant-minorities-emm-survey-registry> [17.01.2021]
- SSHOC Workshop on Data Management and FAIRness of Migration Data, Caring for Sharing:
<https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/caring-sharing-workshop-data-mgmt-and-fairness-migration-data> [accessed 21.01.2021]
- SSHOC Workshop: Agile development of the SSH Open Marketplace:
<https://sshopencloud.eu/agile-development-ssh-open-marketplace-user-workshop> [accessed 21.01.2021]
- SSHOC Workshop: Considerations for the Vocabulary Platforms:
<https://www.sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-considerations-vocabulary-platforms>
<https://www.clarin.eu/event/2020/sshoc-considerations-vocabulary-platforms-virtual-workshop>
[accessed 21.01.2021]
- SSHOC YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCw-mY8v84yeHW2z4KG3ZLtA> [accessed 21.01.2021]
- SSHOC Zenodo Community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/sshoc/> [accessed 21.01.2021]
- Takeaways from the SSHOC Webinar Series on Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms:
<https://sshopencloud.eu/news/takeaways-sshoc-webinar-series-open-source-vocabulary-hosting-and-management-platforms> [accessed 21.01.2021]
- TAPoR website: <http://tapor.ca/home> [22.01.2021]
- Text Mining for the Social Sciences and Digital Humanities additional targeted training webinar “Quantify with Ease: Combining quantitative and qualitative corpus analysis”
<https://sshopencloud.eu/3rd-sshoc-webinar-quantify-combining-quantitative-qualitative-corpus-analysis> [accessed 21.01.2021]
- The Programming Historian website: <https://programminghistorian.org/> [22.01.2021]
- Tools and Resources for FAIR Data:
<https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/tools-and-resources-fair-data-sshoc-webinar-notes>
[accessed 21.01.2021]
- Training Discovery Toolkit: <https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/> [accessed 21.01.2021]
- Training Resource Catalogue Interoperability workshop, 29 October 2020:
<https://www.fairsfair.eu/events/training-resource-catalogue-interoperability-workshop> [accessed 21.01.2021]
- Video #EOSCprojectsEXPO: <https://twitter.com/SSHOpenCloud/status/1329089889581768709> [accessed 21.01.2021]
- WageIndicator Survey:
<https://wageindicator.org/Wageindicatorfoundation/researchlab/wageindicator-survey-and-data>
[17.01.2021]

WEBINAR NOTES: Introducing the newly launched EMM Survey Registry,

<https://sshopencloud.eu/news/webinar-notes-introducing-newly-launched-emm-survey-registry>

[accessed 21.01.2021]

Website of Linked Conservation Data Example: <https://rdf.ng-london.org.uk/workshops/lcd>, with the source code available at: <https://github.com/jpadfield/bg-lcd-example> [29.12.2020]

Website of Linked Conservation Data funded by AHRC: <https://www.ligatus.org.uk/lcd/> [29.12.2020]

Website of Raphael Research Resource: <https://cima.ng-london.org.uk/documentation> [29.12.2020]

Website of Semantic mapping models: <https://rdf.ng-london.org.uk/modelling/>

Workshop OPERAS Conference: <https://www.operas2020.com/speakers-workshops> [21.01.2021]

#RealisingEOSC playlist:

https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLpuwwe1MpnqKKTezlRIHDaNx_zlo4yuRC [accessed

18.01.2021]

#RealisingEOSC ZENODO community:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/realisingtheeoscevent?page=1&size=20> [accessed 18.01.2021]

[MCSQ] interface: <http://easy.mcsq.upf.edu/> [accessed 18.01.2021]

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7. Appendix – Tables of events & Scientific Publications

M13 - M24 (Year 2020)						
SSHOC organised & co-organised events						
Conference	Type event	Title	Date	No. Attendees	Target Stakeholder	Link
FAIR Research Data Management in SSH: a CO-OPERAS IN & SSHOC Workshop	Workshop	FAIR Research Data Management in SSH: a CO-OPERAS IN & SSHOC Workshop	30/01/20	28	Ph.D Students, early career and senior scholars in the SSH,	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/fair-research-data-management-ssh-co-operas-sshoc-workshop
TEI training tutorial	Workshop	TEI and Context: the TEITOK environment	20/02/20	40	Scientific Community	https://lindat.cz/sites/default/files/lindat-tut-feb.pdf
SSHOC Webinar: CLARIN Hands-on Tutorial on Transcribing Interview Data (online)	Tutorial	CLARIN Hands-on Tutorial on Transcribing Interview Data	03/03/20	Attendees: 101 Recordings 213 views	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/hands-on-tutorial-transcribing-interview-data#overlay-context=
SSHOC at HERItage conference 2020: The role of cultural heritage in socio-economic development and preservation of democratic values	Parallel session	The Role of Cultural Heritage in Socio-Economic Development and Preservation of Democratic Values - HERItage	11-13/03/20	cancelled due to COVID-19	SSH Researchers, EC and Croatian Policy Makers, EC and Croatian funders	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-heritage-conference-2020-role-cultural-heritage-socio-economic-development-and-preservation#overlay-context=
SSHOC training session during the COST Action meeting and 2nd Annual Policy Dialogue Conference, Brussels, Belgium	Training session	Caring for Sharing: Data Management and FAIRness of Migration Data	9-10/03/20	33	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-training-session-cost-action-meeting#overlay-context=

SSHOC Webinar - Discussion meeting about requirements of CESSDA Service Providers for a Dataverse repository (online)	Webinar	Discussion meeting about requirements of CESSDA Service Providers for a Dataverse repository	18/03/20	attendees 50, recordings seen 146 times	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-cessda-service-providers-dataverse#overlay-context=
SSHOC Training Community Kick-Off Call (online)	Kick-Off Call	SSHOC Training Community kick-off call	19/03/20	26	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-training-community-kick-call#overlay-context=
SSHOC Workshop - Linking Social Survey and Linguistic Infrastructures through EOSC	Workshop	Linking Social Survey and Linguistic Infrastructures through EOSC	24/03/20	Postponed due to COVID-19	SSH research community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-workshop-linking-social-survey-linguistic-infrastructures-eosc#overlay-context=
3rd SSHOC Consortium meeting (online due to Covid-19)	Consortium meeting	3rd Consortium meeting	24-25/03/20	80 attendees	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/3rd-sshoc-consortium-meeting#overlay-context=
Use and Re-use of Scientific Data in Archaeology and Heritage	Webinar	Use and Re-use of Scientific Data in Archaeology and Heritage	02/04/20	attendees 65, recordings seen 100 times	Scientific Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/use-and-re-use-scientific-data-archaeology-and-heritage
3rd SSHOC WEBINAR “Quanlify with ease: Combining quantitative and qualitative corpus analysis” (online)	Webinar	Quanlify with Ease: Combining quantitative and qualitative corpus analysis	16/04/20	attendees 75, recordings seen 88 times	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/3rd-sshoc-webinar-quantify-combining-quantitative-qualitative-corpus-analysis#overlay-context=
SSHOC WEBINAR: How to improve the quality of your repository? SSHOC and certification of repositories	Webinar	How to improve the quality of your repository? SSHOC and certification of repositories	23/04/20	attendees 50, recordings seen 98 times	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-repositories-quality-certification#overlay-context=

(online)						
SSHOC OH-Portal Questions & Answers Session 1, 2, 3 and 4	Q&A sessions	OH-Portal: Questions & Answers Sessions	28/04/20, 05/05/20, 12/05/20, 19/05/20	attendees of all 4 sessions: 0	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-oh-portal-questions-answers-session-1#overlay-context=
LR4SSHOC: LREC2020 workshop about Language Resources for the SSH Cloud	Workshop	Workshop about Language Resources for the SSH Cloud (LR4SSHOC)	Planned 11/05/20 (postponed due to Covid-19)	Postponed due to COVID-19	-	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-repositories-quality-certification#overlay-context=
6th SSHOC webinar: Tools and Resources for FAIR Data (online)	Webinar	Tools and Resources for FAIR Data	18/05/20	Attendees 136, recordings seen 153 times	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-emm-survey-data-fair#overlay-context=
Mini Bootcamp SSHOC Training Toolkit	Workshop	Mini Bootcamp SSHOC Training Toolkit	02/06/2020	Attendees 17	SSHOC Training Community members	-
LIBER 2020 (online)	Workshop	SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp for Librarians	23/06/20	Attendees 51	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-train-trainer-bootcamp-librarians#overlay-context=
ICTeSSH workshop - Agile development of the SSH Open Marketplace	Workshop	Agile development of the SSH Open Marketplace	30/06/20	Attendees 246, recordings viewed 10 times	SSH research Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/agile-development-ssh-open-marketplace-user-workshop
SSH Open Marketplace - DARIAH consultation	Webinar	SSH Open Marketplace - DARIAH consultation	03/07/20	Attendees 25, recordings views: 69	SSH research Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/ssh-open-marketplace-public-consultation-dariah-community

DH2020	Workshop	Twin Talks 3 understanding and Facilitating collaboration in DH	23/07/20	Attendees 64, recordings views: 86	SSH research Community	https://www.clarin.eu/event/2020/twintalksdh2020 https://www.clarin.eu/sites/default/files/twin-talks-3_intro.pdf https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6Dcerw7a5TA&feature=youtu.be
SSHOC Online Information Sessions 1	Workshop	SSHOC Online Information Sessions: Open-Source Vocabulary Hosting and Management Platforms - First session: Wikibase	03/09/20	Attendees 41, Recordings views: 25	SSH Research Community	https://www.clarin.eu/event/2020/sshoc-sessions-open-source-vocabulary-hosting-and-management-platforms
4th SSHOC Consortium meeting (online)	Consortium meeting	4th Consortium meeting	08-09/09/20	Attendees 80	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/4th-sshoc-consortium-meeting
SSHOC Online Information Sessions 2	Workshop	SSHOC Online Information Sessions 2	14/09/20	Attendees 61, Recordings views: 45	SSH Research Community	https://www.clarin.eu/event/2020/sshoc-sessions-open-source-vocabulary-hosting-and-management-platforms
SSHOC Webinar – Discussion meeting about requirements of DARIAH community for a Dataverse repository	Webinar	SSHOC Webinar – Discussion meeting about requirements of DARIAH community for a Dataverse repository	28/09/20	Attendees 52, recordings views: 36	SSH Research Community	https://www.dariah.eu/2020/09/01/sshoc-webinar-discussion-meeting-about-requirements-of-dariah-community-for-a-dataverse-repository/
SSHOC Online Information Session 3	Workshop	SSHOC Online Information Session 3	30/09/20	Attendees 57 recordings views: 23	SSH Research Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-online-information-sessions-open-source-vocabulary-hosting-and-management-platforms-t

						hird
2nd ESFRI RIs-EOSC Workshop	Workshop	Hosting a Session Break out: Cross-fertilisation between thematic and horizontal projects	07/10/20	10 invited attendees	ESFRI cluster projects & EOSC ecosystem	https://drive.google.com/file/d/14ansJbRBPEx676WwoWIn6n8xgeg-hn2a/view?usp=sharing
Proposal discussion/validation with the ESFRI cluster projects	Workshop	Workshop on Metadata catalogues integration for Interdisciplinary Research /II	09/10/20	20 invited attendees	ESFRI cluster projects	https://bit.ly/MDCWS
SSHOC webinar	Webinar	Putting Data Protection into Practice: GDPR and the DARIAH ELDAH Consent Form Wizard	13/10/20	Attendees 61, recordings views: 63	SSH Research Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/putting-data-protection-practice-gdpr-and-dariah-eldah-consent-form-wizard-0 https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/webinar-notes-gdpr-and-dariah-eldah-consent-form-wizard
SSHOC webinar	Webinar	SSHOC Webinar: Sharing Datasets of Pathological Speech	14/10/20	Attendees 74, recordings views: 31	SSH Research Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-webinar-sharing-datasets-pathological-speech
DARIAH Annual Event	Presentation	Building trustworthy repositories: Introduction to CoreTrustSeal certification workshop during DARIAH AE	14/10/20	Attendees 20, recordings views: 58	SSH Research Community	https://dariah-ae-2020.science.sconf.org/309393
SSHOC webinar	Webinar	SSHOC webinar: Introducing the newly launched Ethnic and Migrant Minorities (EMM)	26/10/20	Attendees 120, recordings views: 98	SSH Research Community	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UFRj6Lz0v_w https://zenodo.org/record/4134061#.XZaPhRNKhZQ

Survey Registry						
SSHOC Virtual Workshop - consideration for the vocabulary platform	Workshop	SSHOC Virtual Workshop - SSHOC Consideration for the vocabulary platform	06/11/20	Attendees 82, recordings views: 221	SSH Research Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-considerations-vocabulary-platforms
Joint EOSC-hub, FREYA and SSHOC 4 day conference with 29 sessions organised	Conference & Virtual EOSC Expo	Realising EOSC. Towards a FAIR research data landscape for the social sciences and humanities and beyond	16-19/11/20	690+ Participants, From 45 Countries, including from 20 countries outside the EU 33 booths from EOSC projects, visited over 3780 times, 880 video views, 1520 document views	Universities & Research Institutes, Researchers, Research Funders, Research and e-Infrastructures, EOSC thematic clusters, Policy Makers, Citizen Scientists, Research Libraries & Archives, Private Sector and Industry	https://sshopencloud.eu/realising-european-open-science-cloud

M13-M24 (Year 2020)						
SSHOC attended events						
Conference	Activity	Title	Date	Stake holders	Target Stakeholder	Link
Roundtable presentation in workshop on Big Data synthesis, Society for Historical Archaeology, USA	Participation to a Workshop		10/01/20	20	Scientific Community	
"International migration data: advances and challenges" Workshop, Bologna, IT	Participation to a Workshop, Presentation by Laura Morales (Lead of T9.2) of the EMM Survey Registry	"The Ethnic and Migrant Minorities Survey Metadata Registry: a new tool for understanding data on migration", Session 1. Advances in migration data usage and collection	13/02/20	25	Scientific Community	https://eventi.unibo.it/workshopcassini-bologna-2020
CLOSER Conference 2020, Preparing for the future II: international approaches to challenges facing the longitudinal population studies, Woburn House, London (UK)	Presentation of Mari Kleemola	Challenges and successes of CESSDA ERIC	16/01/20	N.A	Scientific Community	https://www.closer.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/Data-discoverability-and-issues-of-interoperability-C3-Kleemola-Mari.pdf
EOSC French days	Participation to a Workshop	SSHOC presentation at EOSC French days	22/01/20	100	Scientific Community	
Dataverse Workshop	European Use Cases Round table discussion	SSHOC Dataverse	24/01/20		Scientific Community	https://www.sshopencloud.eu/european-dataverse-workshop-2020

NCCR - On the Move Public Lectures Series, Neuchâtel, CH	Participation to a Workshop, Presentation by Laura Morales (Lead of T9.2) of the EMM Survey Registry,	Mapping Contemporary Patterns of Mobility, Migration and Integration: What Survey Data Can We Use?	20/02/20	15	Scientific Community	https://nccr-onthemove.ch/events/mapping-contemporary-patterns-of-mobility-migration-and-integration-what-survey-data-can-we-use/
CSDI2020	Workshop	2020 International Workshop on Comparative Survey Design and Implementation Program	11-13/03/20	cancelled	-	https://csdiworkshop.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/2020-CSDI-Program-2_20.pdf
EOSC-hub Week 2020 goes virtual	Poster presentation	EOSC-hub Week 2020	18-20/05/20	800	Scientific Community	https://sshopencloud.eu/eosc-hub-week-2020-goes-virtual#overlay-context=
RDA global adoption week 2020	presentations in 2 sessions	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) adoption story of CoreTrustSeal across European SSH repositories	17/06/20	100	Scientific Community	https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-global-adoption-week-15-19-june-2020
17th IMISCOE Annual Conference	Via a panel session, present working paper that analyses survey-level metadata from the EMM Survey Registry	EMM survey registry	01/07/20	20	Scientific Community	https://www.imiscoe.org/events/imiscoe-events/1027-17th-imiscoe-annual-conference
	Via a roundtable, present EMM Survey Registry (beta version) to potential users	EMM survey registry (beta version)	02/07/20	30	Scientific Community	https://www.imiscoe.org/events/imiscoe-events/1027-17th-imiscoe-annual-conference

Workshop on Metadata catalogues integration for Interdisciplinary Research	Presentation	Workshop on Metadata catalogues integration for Interdisciplinary Research	11/09/20	60	Scientific Community	https://bit.ly/MDCWS
Open Access Tage 2020	Presentation	Presentation of SSH Open Marketplace at the Open-Access-Tage 2020	16/09/20	30	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/record/4009121
EOSC & SRIA, Clusters, SSHOC Tier-1 Meeting, virtual, 16.09.2020	Presentation	EOSC & SRIA, Clusters, SSHOC Tier-1 Meeting, virtual, 16.09.2020	16/09/20	10	Scientific Community	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1nyLwjrutDljTgeAMxsh0eKi3Bs-OLsId/view?usp=sharing
RESILIENCE Community Meeting	Presentation	Presentation of SSHOC Project at RESILIENCE community meeting	18/09/20	6	Scientific Community	general SSHOC presentation provided by WP2
CLARIN Annual Conference 2020	Pitch	mention of SSHOC project at CLARIN Annual Conference 2020	06/10/20	N.A	Scientific Community	https://www.clarin.eu/blog/clarin2020-visual-wrap-day-2 https://www.clarin.eu/sites/default/files/clarin2020_stat_eoftheinfrastructure_dejong.pdf
	Booth	Bazaar booth at the CLARIN Annual Conference		N.A	Scientific Community	https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-bazaar-2020#CLARIN%20in%20SSHOC
2nd ESFRI RIs-EOSC Workshop		presentation at 2nd ESFRI RIs-EOSC Workshop	06/10/20	250	Scientific Community	https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/DeJong_Session-4_ESFRI-EOSC_07.10.20.pdf

TRIPLE project Consortium meeting	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Presentation of SSHOC Services at the TRIPLE project Consortium meeting	13/10/20	24	Scientific Community	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1X9lgdjncC-dIUO6TfPQ-Q2wAevj7zrAPx/view?usp=sharing
General Assembly EURHISFIRM	Participation in activities organized jointly with other EU project(s)	SSHOC at EURHISFIRM, General Assembly EURHISFIRM, virtual, 16.10.2020	16/10/20	50	Scientific Community	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1qgr5X_LW5hzCO_nv8An52wjlm7GFdDb/view?usp=sharing
Presentation was conducted as part of ETHMIGSURVEYDATA's Management Committee and Work Groups meeting	Participation in activities organized jointly with other EU project(s)	Provide updates on the development of the EMM Survey Registry and the QDB pilots (to test the feasibility of including EMM surveys in the CESDDA-led EQB), which are being jointly developed by SSHOC (T9.2) and ETHMIGSURVEYDATA	29/10/20	50	Scientific Community	
21st ESS ERIC Core Scientific Team Meeting	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	21st ESS ERIC Core Scientific Team Meeting	29/10/20	20	Scientific Community	
ICMI2020	Workshop presentations	Speech, Voice, Text, and Meaning about Oral History and Technology	29/10/20	18	Scientific Community	http://icmi.acm.org/2020/index.php?id=workshops#workshop10
OPERAS Conference	Presentation	Opening up Social Sciences and Humanities, OPERAS conference, virtual, 04.11.2020	04/11/20	80	Scientific Community	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1qgr5X_LW5hzCO_nv8An52wjlm7GFdDb/view?usp=sharing

BigSurv20 conference	Presentation	Improving SHARE translation verification	06/11/20	40	Scientific Community & Industry	https://www.bigsurv20.org/glance ; https://www.bigsurv20.org/conf20/uploads/138/197/SSHOC_ATV_Pettinicchi.pdf
	Presentation	Developing a tool suite for managing large scale cross-national web surveys within the framework of the European Open Science Cloud - Demonstrate the "Web panel sample management service" first use case with CRONOS2	20/11/20	N.A	Scientific Community	https://www.bigsurv20.org/conf20/program/?sess=33#136
			21/11/20	N.A	Scientific Community	https://www.bigsurv20.org/conf20/program/?sess=33#137
SSHOC Training community call	Presentation	Presentation "TRAPD: Online Review Discussion in International Survey Translation Projects"	10/11/20	12	Scientific Community	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1LHxwDfalW2Tp6dX4MQxpMiglXzDZwaPT
15th ESS ERIC National Coordinators Forum	Participation	15th ESS ERIC National Coordinators Forum	11/11/20	50	Scientific Community	
Meeting with EC DG RTD	Presentation	Presentation of SSHOC Project at meeting with EC DG RTD	01/12/20	5	Policy Makers	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1mBdFMDk2e0OQ4MhneIRUgalvubuHahiO/view?usp=sharing

DDI2020	Presentation	As part of session 6, give a presentation (Reusing and sharing metadata: A case study of quantitative survey research on the integration of ethnic and migrant minorities (EMMs) across Europe) about how the EMM Survey Registry promotes the re-use and sharing of EMM surveys via metadata	02/12/20	40	Scientific Community	https://eddi20.sciencesconf.org/program; http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4305692; https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YtB14nQn79Q&list=PLo7wmLY6eAWlwMy8uoGCvYyCc4uQSRrZh&index=2&t=30s
French Data SHS 2020	Presentation	Present the EMM Survey Registry and the French EMM surveys that will be included in the registry	10/12/20	N/A	Scientific Community	http://migrinter.labo.univ-poitiers.fr/semaine-data-shs/
French Data SHS 2020	Presentation	Present the EMM Survey Registry and the French EMM surveys that will be included in the registry	11/12/20	N/A	Scientific Community	https://progedo.hypotheses.org/1184
ESFRI Strategic Working Group and EEASH Community	Presentation	Presentation of SSHOC Project at a meeting with ESFRI Strategic Working Group and EEASH Community	18/12/20	4	Research Infrastructures	closed meeting

M13-M24 (Year 2020)					
SSHOC Scientific Publications					
Title	Authors	Type	Conference/Journal	Date	Link or DOI
Interoperability in an Infrastructure Enabling Multidisciplinary Research: The case of CLARIN	de Jong, Franciska; Maegaard, Bente; Fišer, Darja; Van Uytvanck, Dieter; Witt, Andreas (CLARIN ERIC).	workshop proceedings	LREC 2020 - Proceedings of The 12th Language Resources and Evaluation Conference	May 2020	https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.lrec-1.417.pdf
Stretching Disciplinary Boundaries in Language Resource Development and Use: a Linguistic Data Consortium Position Paper	Cieri, Christopher (University of Pennsylvania, Linguistic Data Consortium)	workshop proceedings	LREC 2020 - Proceedings of The 12th Language Resources and Evaluation Conference	May 2020	https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.lr4sshoc-1.8.pdf
LR4SSHOC: The Future of Language Resources in the Context of the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud	Broeder, Daan; Eskevich, Maria (CLARIN ERIC), Monachini, Monica (Institute of Computational Linguistics - CNR)	workshop proceedings	LREC 2020 - Proceedings of The 12th Language Resources and Evaluation Conference	May 2020	https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.lr4sshoc-1.6.pdf
Mining Wages in Nineteenth-Century Job Advertisements. The Application of Language Resources and Language Technology to study Economic and Social Inequality	Ros, Ruben (Utrecht University), van Erp, Marieke (KNAW Humanities Cluster DHLab), Rijpma, Auke (Utrecht University & International Institute for Social History The Netherlands), Zijdeman, Richard (International Institute for Social History, The Netherlands & University of	workshop proceedings	LREC 2020 - Proceedings of The 12th Language Resources and Evaluation Conference	May 2020	https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.lr4sshoc-1.5.pdf

	Stirling, Scotland)				
Verbal Aggression as an Indicator of Xenophobic Attitudes in Greek Twitter during and after the Financial Crisis	Pontiki, Maria; Gavriilidou, Maria; Gkoumas, Dimitris; Piperidis, Stelios (ILSP-Athena RC)	workshop proceedings	LREC 2020 - Proceedings of The 12th Language Resources and Evaluation Conference	May 2020	https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.lr4sshoc-1.4.pdf
From the attic to the cloud: mobilization of endangered language resources with linked data	Nordhoff, Sebastian (Leibniz-Zentrum Allgemeine Sprachwissenschaft-ZAS Berlin)	workshop proceedings	LREC 2020 - Proceedings of The 12th Language Resources and Evaluation Conference	May 2020	https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.lr4sshoc-1.3.pdf
Store Scientific Workflows Data in SSHOC Repository	Concordia, Cesare; Meghini, Carlo; Benedetti, Filippo (CNR-ISTI)	workshop proceedings	LREC 2020 - Proceedings of The 12th Language Resources and Evaluation Conference	May 2020	https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.lr4sshoc-1.1.pdf
Crossing the SSH Bridge with Interview Data	Van den Heuvel, Henk (CLS/CLST, Radboud University)	workshop proceedings	LREC 2020 - Proceedings of The 12th Language Resources and Evaluation Conference	May 2020	https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.lr4sshoc-1.9.pdf
Agile development of the SSH Open Marketplace: User Workshop	Laure Barbot, Tracey Biller, Daan Broeder, Ron Dekker, Matej Durco, Irene Vipavc, Marieke Willems	Workshop proceedings	ICTeSSH 2020	August 2020	https://doi.org/10.1051/itmconf/20203304001